
DELIVERABLE 3.3

Pilot Action Results

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Table of contents

Glossary.....	6
1. Introduction.....	7
1.1 Project description.....	7
1.2 Purpose and scope of the deliverable.....	8
1.3 Links to other tasks and work packages.....	9
2. Methodological background.....	10
2.1 Overview.....	10
2.2 Redesign Process.....	11
2.3 Summative Evaluation.....	12
3. Results of the Pilot Actions.....	16
3.1 Technological University of Dublin (TU Dublin).....	16
3.2 Frederick University (FredU).....	29
3.3 Sofia University (UNISOFIA).....	41
3.4 Le Mans University (UM).....	53
3.5 AGH University of Science and Technology (AGH).....	69
3.6 Bay Zoltán Nonprofit Ltd. for Applied Research (BZN).....	80
3.7 University of Niš (UN).....	94
3.8 Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia (IIT).....	109
3.9 Koç University (KU).....	121
4. Overall Analysis.....	135

5. Summative Evaluation Report	144
5.1 Technological University of Dublin (TU Dublin)	146
5.2 Frederick University (FredU)	148
5.3 Sofia University (UNISOFIA)	150
5.4 University of Le Mans (UM)	152
5.5 AGH University of Science and Technology (AGH)	154
5.6 Bay Zoltán Nonprofit Ltd. for Applied Research (BZN)	156
5.7 University of Niš (UN).....	157
5.8 Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia (IIT)	159
5.9 Koç University (KU)	161
6. Annexes Documentation Submitted to the project’s SharePoint	166
References	169

Glossary

ATHENA SWAN – It is an equality charter mark framework and accreditation scheme for higher education and research institutions

DEI – Diversity, Equity and Inclusion

GBV – Measures against gender balance violence including sexual harassment

GEAM – Gender Equality Audit and Monitoring

GEP – Gender Equality Plan

NGO – Non Governative Organization

RPO – Research Performance Organization

1. Introduction

1.1 Project description

The NEXUS project aims to bridge inclusivity gaps in nine research organizations and their respective ecosystems by designing, implementing, monitoring, and evaluating targeted actions. These efforts focus on fostering institutional change through inclusive Gender Equality Plans (GEPs), leveraging both intersectional and intersectoral approaches. Intersectionality addresses overlapping inequalities such as race, gender, age, and socio-economic status, while intersectorality emphasizes partnerships across sectors, including universities, NGOs, and private organizations, to enhance impact.

The project employs a context-sensitive strategy for action piloting in various regions across Member States and Associated Countries, promoting geographical inclusiveness. By establishing structures in less experienced institutions, NEXUS enables them to exceed Horizon Europe's minimum GEP requirements through a participatory, multi-stakeholder process supported by a Twinning scheme of three "Twin Trios." Tailored capacity-building and training programs ensure comprehensive support.

Structured in three phases (Figure 1)—inclusiveness assessment, solution co-creation, and implementation with GEP refinement—NEXUS actions aim to enhance research excellence and drive institutional and cultural change that is realistic, sustainable, and impactful. This deliverable centers on the third phase of the project, specifically activities within Work Package (WP) 3, which encompass pilot action implementation, evaluation, and GEP refinement through monitoring and redesign processes.

Figure 1: NEXUS Phases

1.2 Purpose and scope of the deliverable

WP3 focused on the implementation of the solutions co-developed during WP2. Each partner was responsible for delivering a minimum of five inclusive actions. Over a 13-month period (M9–M21), a total of 45 pilot actions were implemented and closely monitored through regular task tracking.

After describing the methodology deployed (section 2), section 3 of this deliverable “*Results of the Pilot Actions*” presents a synthesis of progress based on feedback collected during the implementation phase, integrating the outcomes of the formative evaluation as well as of the redesign process. These activities, including surveys, interviews, focus groups, workshops, and coordination meetings—have been essential for monitoring development, identifying challenges, and informing any necessary adjustments to ensure consistency with the project’s overall objectives. They have also supported partners in aligning their initiatives with broader inclusivity goals and contribute to the refinement of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) conducted in the last months of the NEXUS project.

Following an overall analysis of these pilot action results (section 4), section 5 presents the outcomes of the summative evaluation for each organization, offering a more comprehensive overview of the results achieved.

1.3 Links to other tasks and work packages

Alignment with WP3 Objectives

WP3 is dedicated to implementing the solutions co-created in WP2, monitoring their progress, and evaluating their outcomes. D3.3 is closely aligned with the objectives and methodologies outlined in D3.1 and is part of a broader framework within WP3. While D3.1 provided the foundational monitoring and evaluation methodology for the project, D3.2 builds upon this by focusing specifically on the mid-term results of formative evaluation activities.

D3.3 outlines the key aspects of the five actions undertaken by each partner, particularly concerning monitoring and evaluation tools (redesign and first and second formative evaluations). Each section starts with a comprehensive summary table detailing each partner's activities, highlighting their engagement with monitoring and evaluation. For each action, a detailed report is provided, including the **key objective** of the action, **findings from the second round of formative evaluation, planned and achieved outcomes**, and a thorough explanation of the details of **redesign process**.

Connections to WP3 -Deliverable D3.4 – GEPs' refinement and next steps

D3.4 - GEP's refinement and next steps will build on the experiences gained by partners during the implementation of the NEXUS project. Drawing on the feedback collected for D 3.3, D3.4 will outline a comprehensive overview of each organization's GEP, based on insights about the GEP areas that have been improved or changed (and how), as well as future GEP directions in terms of sustainability and feasibility.

2. Methodological background

2.1 Overview

The NEXUS project has implemented 45 actions across 9 different partners. Over the past months, each partner has monitored the progress and implementation of these actions using a range of evaluation and redesign tools.

The entire analysis process began with a quarterly reflection by each partner on the main achievements related to their specific actions. Using a Monitoring Spreadsheet Template (Annex 2), every four months partners reported the progress status of each action and provided updates on advancement in relation to a set of monitoring indicators. In September (optional) and November 2024, February (optional) and May 2025, each partner completed and submitted the progress report for their actions, updating on their status until full implementation was achieved. Parallel to this activity, partners used a set of complementary tools to support their monitoring and evaluation processes, which included evaluation and redesign workshops and formative evaluation activities. The formative evaluation was conducted internally by each implementing partner in two rounds, involving evaluation and redesign workshops. These workshops addressed cross-cutting issues and enabled partners to make timely adjustments based on their organizational, cultural or logistic situation, while ensuring that activities remained aligned with the project's overarching objective. In parallel, the summative evaluation was conducted by Smart Venice (SV) as a program of in-depth, online interviews and focus groups. The aim of the summative evaluation activities was to assess three components: institutional commitment, institutional change, and the overall co-creation and intersectoral collaboration process. In contrast to the formative evaluation, the summative evaluation focused on the overall implementation process rather than assessing each action implementation individually.

A detailed description of these monitoring and evaluation tools deployed in NEXUS was included in D3.2 - Formative Evaluation Mid-Term results, available at this [link](#). The formative evaluation activities provided more in-depth insights into the effectiveness and progress of the actions. The methodology deployed combined qualitative and quantitative approaches, drawing on tools such as

pre and post intervention surveys, focus groups, stakeholder consultations, and document analysis. These activities took place in two rounds: the first (M14/15) provided insights into the first half of the implementation process, while the second (M21) provided insights into the second half of the implementation process. People engaged in the formative evaluation process were not only GEP and NEXUS teams, but also stakeholders that supported the implementation of the action. By capturing real-time feedback, these activities supported the ongoing refinement of actions and helped ensure they effectively addressed inclusivity gaps. The results of the first round were also reported in D 3.2 Formative Evaluation Mid-term Results, available at this [link](#).

The second round of formative evaluation activities, reported by each partner in the “**Formative Evaluation Reporting**” (Annexes Documentation Submitted to the project’s SharePoint page. 169) was carried out only for actions that were still ongoing and offered additional insights into how far the expected outcomes were achieved through the actions implemented. The main objective was to highlight the contribution of each action, while also examining the role of stakeholders involved, as well as other contextual elements, in influencing the outcomes. The second round of formative evaluation placed special emphasis on the following questions:

- *Which outputs and outcomes (intended and unintended), in terms of gender equality, resulted from the action?*
- *Which intersectional and/or intersectoral outcomes (intended and unintended) were the result of the action?*
- *To what extent were the expected outcomes of the action achieved?*
- *Which facilitating and hindering contextual factors affected the outcomes of the action?*

2.2 Redesign Process

The monitoring and evaluation process was designed to ensure that implementation was reflexively accompanied by a continuous adjustment and re-design of the actions, informed by the outcomes of the formative evaluation. Each partner conducted **four Evaluation and Redesign Workshops** to ensure a continuous adjustment and redesign of the actions, integrating also the results of the formative evaluations activities. The actions developed by the NEXUS Twin trios were also evaluated collectively in the frame of ad-hoc evaluation and redesign workshops which took place every three

months. A reporting template on activities carried out during the evaluation and redesign workshops is available in Deliverable 3.1 Monitoring and Evaluation Methodology Annex 3.

The four Evaluation and Redesign workshops **aimed to sustain a reflexive redesign process and continuous adjustment of the actions to accompany the implementation**: 36 Evaluation and Redesign workshops were carried out.

On the one hand, Twin trio participants met to evaluate jointly designed actions. On the other hand, GEP working groups within partner institutions meet to evaluate actions designed outside the Twin trios. Workshops were scheduled every three months: M13, M15, M18, and M21. Each workshop addressed the following cross-cutting topics: evaluation of the action's design, discussion of the action's monitoring indicators, and analysis of resistances to implementation. In addition, each workshop included a timeline-specific discussion aligned with the current stage of implementation. Lastly, each workshop concluded with a discussion of how to adjust the course of action based on ideas exchanged during the session.

The evaluation of the action's design was conducted by answering the guiding questions defined for each cross-cutting topic and available on the D 3.1 Monitoring and Evaluation Methodology.

2.3 Summative Evaluation

Summative Evaluation

The full monitoring and evaluation methodology of the NEXUS project can be found in D3.1. This methodology foresaw two types of evaluation, the formative evaluation and the summative evaluation. The summative evaluation of the NEXUS project was designed and implemented to assess the project's institutional impact across three key dimensions: **institutional commitment, institutional change, and intersectoral collaboration/co-creation**. Unlike the formative evaluation—conducted internally in two rounds during the implementation of pilot actions aimed at improving delivery—the summative evaluation took place at the end of the implementation phase to assess broader, systemic change and sustainability prospects. While the formative evaluation was conducted internally by each implementing partner in two rounds, also accompanied by evaluation and redesign workshops, the summative evaluation was conducted by Smart Venice (SV) as a

program of **in-depth, online interviews and focus groups**, conducted in each of the nine implementing partner organizations.

The summative evaluation engaged not only NEXUS Team members at each implementing partner organization, but also members of top and middle management, as well as selection of external stakeholders engaged in collaborative actions and/or other internal stakeholders who were either involved in or familiar with the NEXUS actions or other components of the NEXUS project (e.g., capacity building sessions).

The summative evaluation (M22) involved:

- **2 to 4 semi-structured interviews** per partner with middle and senior management staff not directly involved in the NEXUS project team.
- **1 focus group per partner** with a mix of NEXUS and non-NEXUS team members.

In total, 22 interviews and 9 focus groups were conducted across the consortium. The sessions were anonymized and analyzed using a thematic template based on the evaluation framework outlined in D3.1. Each discussion was structured around four thematic blocks: implementation experiences, collaboration/co-creation, institutional commitment, and institutional change.

Deviations from the original plan laid out in D3.1 included the decision not to involve external stakeholders or direct beneficiaries in the summative evaluation, given logistical complexities and the broader scope of inquiry (which focused on institutional impact rather than individual actions). Instead, the evaluation captured insights from organizational actors familiar with DEI (Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion) topics and institutional processes.

The results of summative evaluation activities were summarized and analyzed by SV into an overall summative evaluation report per implementing partner, covering institutional commitment, institutional change, and co-creation/intersectoral collaboration. All reports were shared with IIT as input for D3.3. Each report was also shared bilaterally with the respective implementing partner for transparency.

Interview structure and questions

Online semi-structured interviews were carried out between 09/06/2025 and 04/07/2025.

Following introductory questions regarding the interviewee's perception of potential challenges and overall views on the project's impact, the interview was structured in four key sections:

1. **Inclusiveness and the GEP:** the organization's approach/policies towards inclusion, and how they may have changed over the past two years.
2. **Institutional commitment:** leadership engagement in the project and initiatives supporting gender and intersectional equality generally.
3. **Institutional change processes:** the project's impact, for instance in relation to the GEP, the integration of NEXUS actions in existing frameworks, or new approaches to data collection.
4. **A view to the future:** gaps that could be addressed in the future through new steps or actions.

Focus group structure and questions

The agenda was structured into four blocks. A Mentimeter question was used as an engaging starting point/icebreaker for each block, to collect initial responses from each participant and provide potential topics for discussion, where relevant. The four key sections of the discussion were:

1. **Implementation:** the implementation process, including challenges experienced and observed, the formative evaluation and re-design process, and responses observed by stakeholders internally to the organization (e.g., staff, students).
2. **Collaboration:** the co-creation and overall collaboration process, including collaboration in the twin trios and engagement of external stakeholders.
3. **Institutional commitment:** for instance, in relation to resources made available for project activities, engagement of middle and senior management, general commitment and institutional steps towards the sustainability of NEXUS actions.
4. **Institutional change:** the project's impact on the institution, for instance in relation to changes in the GEP, the promotion of an intersectional approach, alignment with existing frameworks and policies, and next steps.

To develop the summative evaluation reports, quotations from the transcripts were grouped under the template questions. However, not all questions were touched upon in the interviews and focus groups; as a result, the reports were structured in the three original macro-blocks (institutional commitment, institutional change and co-creation/intersectoral collaboration), without including specific questions. Where necessary, further headings were included for clarity and structure (e.g., contextual information, barriers to institutional change processes, changes in organizational data

collection practices). Relevant quotations were synthesized and summarized thematically, and direct quotations were used throughout the reports.

3. Results of the Pilot Actions

3.1 Technological University of Dublin (TU Dublin)

The following table summarizes the monitoring, evaluation, and redesign process of the pilot actions carried out by the Technological University of Dublin within the NEXUS project.

TU Dublin				
GEP'Areas	# Pilot Actions	#Formative Evaluation I round	#Formative Evaluation II round	#Actions adjusted following the Redesign Process
Work-life balance and organizational culture	3	3	3	1
Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment	1	1	1	1
Gender balance in leadership and decision making				
Data Collection				
Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	1	1	1	1
Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content				
Total	5	5	5	3

The following describes their 5 pilot actions, the findings from the second round of formative evaluation activities, and the redesign process carried out.

Action 1 – Bystander Intervention (Twin Trio Action)

The action consists in the development of a training module on Bystander intervention in cases of GBV. The key objectives are: 1) to provide participants with a better understanding of the links between harmful social norms and sexual violence and harassment and highlight the danger of normalising such norms and accepting abusive behaviour; 2) to help participants recognise acts of

sexual violence and harassment and to better understand their capacity to intervene as active bystanders; 3) to empower students and staff to safely respond to witnessed sexual assault and abuse in the moment this occurs; 4) to raise awareness about the important role of active bystanders in countering sexual violence and harassment in our university; 5) to create a safer and more inclusive environment both on-campus and off-campus to develop a skill and knowledge-based online module to educate and raise awareness on GBV and provide strategies that will both deal with and combat GBV in the partner institutions and beyond.

Key objective: to develop a skill and knowledge-based online module to educate and raise awareness on GBV and provide strategies that will both deal with and combat GBV in partner institutions and beyond.

Implementation: June 2024 – March 2025. There was a delay in relation to the launch of this action. While this was initially foreseen to take place on 8 March 2025, it was postponed to mid-May 2025 due to longer time needed for the development of the module than anticipated during the planning stage. This did not constitute a barrier at all, but a challenge given that 3 institutions were involved in the development of the action.

Formative evaluation First Round

The first round of formative evaluation activities for this action was conducted as part of a Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) workshop held during the Trio's study visit at TU Dublin on 26 November 2024. The workshop included members of the Gender Equality Plan (GEP) working group from each Trio institution, with a total of six participants, six females. The activities focused on evaluating the implementation progress, reviewing challenges, and identifying key areas for refinement. The M&E workshop was merged with the formative evaluation workshop at the institutional level to address actions 1, 2, and 3, ensuring alignment with institutional priorities and involving the relevant stakeholders. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative Evaluation Second round

The second round of Formative Evaluation was conducted through monthly trio meetings, complemented by regular meetings held with GBV Lead at TU Dublin EDI Office and a monitoring &

evaluation workshop with trio partner teams and institutional experts/persons responsible for the implementation of action. This Monitoring & Evaluation workshop was held on 15 April 2025 and included trio partner teams.

The design and development of the online training module presented several challenges, particularly following the agreement on content across partner institutions. At TU Dublin, the GBV Lead conducted multiple rounds of review, resulting in substantial revisions to the module's presentation, language and phrasing, visual elements, and exercises. These iterative improvements contributed to delays in publication: although the module was initially scheduled for launch on 8 March 2025, it was ultimately released in mid-May 2025. While this delay did not constitute a barrier to implementation, it reflected the complexity of coordinating across three institutions and the commitment to ensuring quality and alignment with institutional standards.

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

The action has the full support of the EDI Director who is a member of the University's Executive Team. The primary implementation challenge for Action #1 relates to the level of resources—both financial and expert—required to develop a training module of professional quality, comparable to those produced by other Irish universities. Achieving this standard demanded a depth of expertise and investment that exceeded initial projections, highlighting the resource-intensive nature of high-quality module design within a competitive institutional landscape. The presence of a dedicated staff member at TU Dublin with exclusive responsibility for addressing GBV has served as a significant facilitator in the implementation of this action. No actors external to TU Dublin were involved in the development of this action.

No resistances and unexpected outcomes have been observed in relation to the action designed. Yet there were several challenges mainly related to the development of the online module once the content had been agreed. The GBV lead undertook multiple reviews of the action, which was not launched until she was entirely happy with it. This involved multiple changes on the overall presentation, language used/phrasing, illustrations, exercises etc. The sustainability of the action after the end of the project is assured because GBV training is institutionalised in TU Dublin, with multiple trainings on this issue, each with varying focus and target groups. The main sustainability risk is if the current anti-gender political climate affects Irish universities.

Outcome foreseen: Consultation meeting held; meeting report, describing feedback; professional networks developed through which the module can be disseminated through; 30 people per partner institution have completed the module (May 2025); increased awareness and understanding of GBV.

Outcome achieved: Consultation meeting with external stakeholders was discarded in this M&E workshop because this could delay the launch of the action.

As the action has been launched recently, the following medium-term outcome indicator (“30 people per partner institution completing the module; increased awareness and understanding of GBV”) has only been partially achieved.

Redesign process

The Redesign Process of the action was discussed in 3 different workshops: a first workshop on 25 September 2024, a second workshop on 26 November 2024 and a third workshop on 15 April 2025. During the first and second workshops, it was decided that TU Dublin would refocus this action on bystander intervention.

During the second workshop (26 November 2024), trio partners agreed on the objectives and scope of the action, making adaptations to fit each institution’s needs. These revisions were carried out with the support of the GBV training manager at TU Dublin and a member of the GEP Working Group. Each partner, in turn, reviewed the timeline for the implementation of the action, and a new timeline for each was agreed.

During the third Workshop (15 April 2025), the following modifications were made:

- After some changes to the module content, it was decided that the title should change to “Bystander intervention awareness training”.
- The launch date was delayed to early May.
- No consultation with stakeholders prior the launch of the course was carried out due to time constraints following delays. The course was advertised internally through DEI newsletters, as well as externally.
- The inclusion of a post-module evaluation (exit survey) was discarded.

No sustainability issues have been identified as this is an action to be embedded in a current GBV training program that is well-established already. No resistances to implementation have been experienced so far, and none were foreseen either. This is because tackling GBV is an institutional priority for the university, and training is regarded as an essential tool for achieving this.

**Action 2 – Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression –and action 3 - A need Analysis;
Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression and Success (Twin Trio Action)**

Action 2 consists of collecting the needs in relation to mentoring programs in partner institutions. This action will serve as a basis for the development of an inclusive mentoring program. Action 3 consists of developing a training program/manual for mentors with inclusivity at its core using the data gathered in the action “Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression - a Needs Analysis.

Key Objective Action 2: To ascertain the baseline needs in relation to mentoring in partner institutions and to subsequently develop a mentoring program.

Key Objective Action 3: To develop a training program/manual for mentors with inclusivity at its core using the data gathered in the action “Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression - a Needs Analysis”.

Implementation Action 2: June 2024 – November 2024

Implementation Action 3: November 2024 – March 2025

Formative Evaluation First Round

Actions 2 and 3 focus on enhancing inclusivity within the existing mentoring program for early-career researchers (ECRs) at TU Dublin. Given their interconnected nature, these actions were evaluated together through formative evaluation activities conducted during the Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) workshop held by the Trio on 26 November as part of the Study Visit at TU Dublin. The workshop included six female participants from the Gender Equality Plan (GEP) working groups of the Trio institutions. The evaluation explored the current state of the mentoring program, its inclusiveness, and opportunities for improvement. The formative evaluation activities included a shift from the initially planned survey to a qualitative approach using semi-structured interviews with mentors and mentees. This adjustment was informed by discussions at the workshop and aimed to

yield deeper insights into the mentoring program's effectiveness and inclusivity. Interview guides were developed based on a literature review and best practices, and feedback was collected from institutional stakeholders to refine the process. A minimum of seven interviews were conducted with current and past participants of the mentoring program, ensuring that the data reflected the experiences of both mentors and mentees. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative Evaluation Second Round

The second round of Formative Evaluation was made with monthly trio meetings, Monitoring & Evaluation workshops with trio partner teams and institutional expert/ persons responsible for the action implementation. An added activity in this round was a workshop held with mentors and mentees acting as respondents in the interviews conducted to gather data. Actions 2 and 3 were discussed and disseminated internally, and internationally through the presentation of these actions at an inclusive mentoring conference organized by Eument-net VOICES. (University of Dusseldorf. Conference title: “Inclusive Research Cultures through mentorship: A Practitioner research dialogue”). The last Monitoring & Evaluation workshop was held on 15 April 2025. This workshop was held online and the NEXUS Team of trio partners participated in the meeting

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

The main decision-making bodies involved actions 2 and 3 were Human Resources (People’s Development Team). Both actions advance inclusive dimensions in an existing mentoring program for researchers with training to both mentors and mentees, so commitment from the top management as well as sustainability of the action is assured.

The responsibilities for the implementation of the actions were distributed among:

- The TU Dublin Researcher Career Development Manager, the main person responsible for the implementation of the action.
- NEXUS staff members responsible for the development of the action.

The activities foreseen were the following:

- Interviews conducted with both mentors and mentees who are currently participating, or have participated, in the mentoring program for ERCs (7 people minimum) (Achieved)
- Interview guides for mentors and mentees constructed; feedback and suggestions from institutional stakeholders to improve the survey (Achieved)

- Data collection results - in infographic format - disseminated on social media via professional networks and within the Trio group institutions (not achieved as this indicator has been dropped).
- Results analyzed and ready to be included in a report to demonstrate the findings (Achieved)
- Target users (mentors and mentees) informed, in a dedicated session, of the main results of the analysis of needs assessment and how these have been integrated into the manual (action 3) (achieved)
- Survey results integrated into action 3 (achieved)

There were no major issues with the timeline. At the end of June 2025, the action was implemented at the mentoring session for researchers.

Outcomes foreseen Action 2 and 3: enhanced materials available for mentors; sustainability of mentorship program; enhanced university-industry relations (intersectoriality); enhanced career prospects of early career researchers; experienced mentors; expanded networks of mentors.

Outcome for Action 3 achieved: The short and medium-term outcome indicators for each activity have been achieved except for the one related to enhanced university-industry relations.

Launch of Action 2: February 2025

Launch of Action 3: June 2025.

Section Redesign process

The Redesign Process of action #2 and #3 were discussed in 3 different workshops: a First Workshop on 25 September 2024, a Second Workshop on 26 November 2024, and a third Workshop on 15 April 2025.

Action 2

During the first workshop (25 September 2024), it was decided that data collection would be conducted through semi-structured interviews with both mentors and mentees from the current mentoring program for ECRs at TU Dublin. During the second workshop (26 November 2024), the action implementation was evaluated and redesigned by the trio partners with the support of the

Researcher Career Development Manager (TU Dublin). While in KU and UNISOFIA the needs assessment targeted mentees, in TU Dublin it targeted both mentors and mentees. The type of activities also changed depending on institution (TU Dublin: interviews and UNISOFIA, KU: survey). The output indicator: “Survey results Infographic format - disseminated on social media via professional networks and within the Trio group institutions” was discarded as this was deemed sensitive information to be kept within each trio institution and only shared with relevant stakeholders and participants in the data collection and analysis research. No sustainability issues were identified either in TU Dublin or UNISOFIA as this is an action to be embedded in a current mentoring program that is well-established already. No resistances have been encountered in all workshops. Action 2 was modified as detailed above

Action 3

The evaluation activities selected for this action included a consultation with internal and external mentoring experts. Challenges envisioned in terms of the monitoring and evaluation process included involving intersectoral actors. During the second Workshop (26 November 2024), it was decided minimal adjustments of the time frame. Trio partners went through each of the monitoring indicator reviewing the current status of the action and deciding whether new indicators should be added or else whether there were indicators that should be deleted. During the third Workshop (15 April 2025), the key objective of this action changed depending on the trio institution. In TU Dublin, the action is aimed at providing inclusive mentoring guidelines which are embedded in an already existing mentoring program. The training component of this action only remains in TU Dublin, where the intersectoral component is missing because the program includes mentors only from the university. No sustainability issues have been identified in TU Dublin as this is an action to be embedded in a current mentoring program that is well-established already. No resistances have been encountered.

Action 4 – EDI Info-Hub (Partner Action)

This action is aimed to increase awareness of EDI initiatives, resources and policy throughout the institution. The action’s implementation requires the creation of a new section on the Info Hub on the EDI website

Key objective: To increase awareness of EDI initiatives, resources and policy throughout the institution.

Implementation: initially June 2024-September 2024, extended to June 2025.

Formative Evaluation First Round

The formative evaluation activities for Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) Information Hub action were conducted through regular meetings with institutional experts and EDI staff members. The NEXUS team at TU Dublin engaged with the entire EDI Directorate team (7 members) on multiple occasions to discuss the implementation of this action. Progress was also reviewed during monthly DEI meetings, providing a collaborative platform to align efforts and address challenges. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative Evaluation Second Round

The formative evaluation activities for Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) Information Hub action were conducted through regular meetings with institutional experts and EDI staff members. The main decision body is EDI Directorate. There was a confirmed commitment from the EDI Director. Responsibilities for this action were distributed in accordance with the areas of work/expertise in relation to each of the different sections of the info-hub. There are no external actors involved.

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

The materials and resources to include in the Info Hub have been compiled and a new section for the Info Hub in the EDI website has been created. The required skills are present among the organisers, and the activities have been carried out as follows:

- The documents to populate the 'EDI Info Hub' have been edited and revised (achieved).
- The database of material is completed, with description and links to documents/data (achieved). At TU Dublin the launch of the info-hub is an action in charge to web developers
- Info-hub has been created (achieved).
- The EDI Information Hub is fully functioning on the EDI website (achieved).
- Staff throughout TU Dublin have increased awareness of EDI initiatives, resources and policy throughout the institution (achieved)

The original timeline set was not realistic due to the time required to coordinate activities among the EDI team. Given their regular work commitments and tight agendas, the completion of their activities in relation to this Action#4 took longer than originally planned. After 2 reviews of the info-hub content and structure with the EDI Directorate's team, it was agreed that important restructuring was needed. As a result, the sections and the content that was to be included in each was changed substantially. The NEXUS team held several subsequent meetings with members of the EDI team to agree how the redrafting work was to be redistributed and agree on a timeline/deadline.

The activities foreseen have been achieved. The implementation is aligned with the objectives and with intersectional goals. No other barriers are identified other than lack of time on the part of the EDI staff members who held the information to be included in the Info Hub. No inhibiting factors to achieving the action's objectives have been identified. Promoting factors include the fact that EDI is being currently embedded across the university (through e.g. the EDI Champions Network) so the Info-Hub is a resource much needed and welcomed. No resistance and unexpected outcomes have been encountered. Therefore, the sustainability of the action beyond the project's lifetime is ensured because the contents of the info-hub are regularly updated by the staff team at EDI.

This action contributes to institutional change by increasing awareness of staff throughout TU Dublin of the EDI initiatives, resources and policy throughout the institution.

Outcome foreseen Action 4: Increased clarity about EDI at TU Dublin; Database of material to be uploaded, with description and links to documents/data; Staff throughout TU Dublin increased awareness of EDI initiatives, resources and policy throughout the institution.

Outcome Achieved Action 4: All outcomes achieved.

Section Redesign process

The action didn't require any adjustment following the redesign process.

Action 5 - DEI Champions (Partner Action)

Key objective: To create an EDI champion network throughout TU Dublin thus embedding individuals who have an interest in, and commitment to, advancing EDI within their school/department/unit and, where appropriate, across the University. EDI Champions: 1) Are

familiar with how to access or get advice on relevant policies, procedures and legislation; b) Are visible and proactive on EDI principles, policy and practices within their department/unit.

Implementation date: June 2024 – November 2024 extended to June 2025.

Formative Evaluation First Round

The formative evaluation activities for the action to establish a network of Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) Champions at TU Dublin were conducted through regular bi-weekly meetings between the NEXUS staff members and the EDI lead. These meetings provided a platform to discuss progress, plan further steps, and ensure alignment with the action's objectives. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative Evaluation Second Round

The formative evaluation activities for the action to establish a network of ED) Champions at TU Dublin were conducted through regular bi-weekly meetings between the NEXUS staff members and the EDI lead. An additional activity was a meeting with the person responsible for the development of another network at TU Dublin (Employee Engagement Network) to gather feedback and fresh ideas. The main decision-making body involved with the implementation of the action is the EDI Directorate. There is a commitment from top management as the EDI Champions Network is an action included in the Athena Swan action plan. There are no external actors directly involved. However, external actors have been involved in providing training to the EDI Champions Network through seminars.

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

The activities foreseen have been all achieved, and the action has been right on target:

- Handbook launched (achieved).
- Handbook used in DEI champions trainings (achieved)
- An EDI champions network -promoting and communicating equality, diversity and inclusion information about key events, news, training opportunities, issues, policy developments and best practice established throughout TU Dublin (achieved).
- EDI champions embedded throughout the university (achieved).

- Approximately 5 trainings for EDI champions, with approximately 10 participants in each (achieved). These training sessions have been followed by other sessions but not particularly geared towards training (rather towards planning). Additionally, network members have been encouraged to undertake EDI training provided at university level.
- Increased awareness of EDI champion role; increased awareness of potential challenges regarding embedding EDI champions at TU Dublin (achieved).
- EDI champions promoting and communicating equality, diversity and inclusivity embedded throughout TU Dublin (achieved)
- Support structures in place to provide direction/scaffolding for EDI champions (achieved).
- EDI champions embedded in a network throughout the university who contribute to broader cultural change and awareness raising of EDI issues by engaging with staff networks, the EDI office and other relevant EDI structures/groups (achieved).
- Increased awareness of good EDI practices highlighted across the University (not yet achieved, but ongoing, as this is more like a long-term outcome).

The implementation has not changed over time. There have been no delays in the timeline. The implementation is aligned with the action objectives. No inhibiting factors have been identified so far. Promoting factors are the amount of interest from people across the university to fulfil the EDI Champion role. No barriers and resistance encountered. The action is part of the Athena Swan action plan which has full endorsement by the top management. Progress is regularly reported to the University Executive Team, and that ensures sustainability. It is too early to assess the results and improvements of the action in terms of gender equality and inclusivity dimensions.

Outcome foreseen Action 5: Handbook used in EDI champions training; EDI champions embedded throughout the university; EDI champions promoting and communicating equality, diversity and inclusivity embedded throughout TU Dublin; increased awareness of EDI champion role; increased awareness of potential challenges regarding embedding EDI champions at TU Dublin; increased awareness of good EDI practices highlighted across the University.

Outcome achieved Action 5: All achieved, except for increased awareness of good EDI practices highlighted across the University (not yet achieved, but ongoing, as this is more like a long-term outcome).

Section Redesign process

The action didn't require any adjustment following the redesign process.

3.2 Frederick University (FredU)

The following table summarizes the monitoring, evaluation, and redesign process of the pilot actions carried out by Frederick University within the NEXUS project.

Frederick University				
GEP'Areas	# Pilot Actions	#Formative Evaluation I round	#Formative Evaluation II round	#Actions adjusted following the Redesign Process
Work-life balance and organizational culture	1	1		
Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment	1	1	1	
Gender balance in leadership and decision making	1			
Data Collection				
Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	1	2	2	
Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content	1	1	1	
Total	5	5	4	0

The following describes their 5 pilot actions, the findings from the second round of formative evaluation activities, and the redesign process carried out.

Action 1 - E-course on Gender Equality and Intersectionality (Twin Trio Action)

This action consists of the creation of an e-course on Gender Equality and Intersectionality. AGH University is offering an e-course on GE in Polish. The aim of the action is to 1) translate the e-course in English 2) localize it according to the cultural aspects of each partner 3) make it intersectional and

finally 4) disseminate it to the three partner organizations urging researchers, faculty and students to study the material.

Key Objective: Create an e-course with a Gender Equality and Intersectionality approach; Increase/Improve equality and diversity in research content

Implementation Date: January 2025

Formative Evaluation First Round

The first round of formative evaluation for the E-Course on Gender Equality and Intersectionality action involved discussions with stakeholders, including members of the ENAF committee and university officers, to assess the usefulness and cultural adaptability of the e-course. These discussions were held in October 2024 and focused on the technical aspects of translation, cultural localization, and the inclusion of intersectional elements in the course content. Aggregated feedback was collected from researchers and teaching staff, with Frederick University representatives from NEXUS coordinating the evaluation process. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative Evaluation Second Round

This action is finished by the end of January 2025; the course is finalised. The formative Evaluation second round was made through a last activity: sending e-mails to participants. In April 2025 the emails have been sent to participants.

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

On the Formative Evaluation Report of Frederick University there is no further information about the second round of formative activities.

Outcome foreseen for action 1: increase awareness of researchers, staff and students on Inclusive Gender Equality.

Outcome achieved for action 1: increase awareness of researchers, staff and students on Inclusive Gender Equality.

Section Redesign Process

During the first and second Workshop Evaluation and Redesign (25 and 26 September 2024) all the points, files and topics that need to be improved (intersectionality, translation etc) were identified. During the workshop there was a discussion about the action's monitoring indicators: feedback, review comments, number of recruited participants. It was confirmed that feedback from the enrolled participants to follow the course is the main evaluation tool. There was no resistance from any partner. Feedback from the enrolled participants to follow the course was the main evaluation tool for the second round of formative activity. During the third Evaluation and Redesign Workshop (10 April 2025), it has been found that the e-course is finished. The respond rate was satisfactory. Results from the GEAM survey at Frederick University is already sent to the top administration. It was decided that emails should be sent to potential participants and disseminate the e-course as much as possible. During the workshop it we discussed the action's monitoring indicators: feedback, review comments, number of recruited participants. At this point the most important point was the number of recruited participants.

During the fourth Evaluation and Redesign Workshop (3 June 2025), it was mentioned that the action and the dissemination of the e-course are completed. . The e-course is open and free of access for anyone. No resistance has been encountered. No further adjustment has been required.

Action 2 - Implementation of the Gender Equality Auditing and Monitoring Tool (Twin Trio Action)

This action consists of the implementation of the Gender Equality Auditing and Monitoring Tool [<https://geam.act-on-gender.eu/>] in order to map the situation regarding Gender Equality in Frederick University, to create an updated database, and to be able to make comparisons inside the University and between the trio, keep track of changes, improvements or pitfalls, since Frederick has implemented the GEAM tool before. In May 2024, training was delivered to the people who were to implement the questionnaire. Once the training was finished, the NEXUS team from Frederick decided which sections of the questionnaire to send and to whom, as there were three target groups: academics, administrative staff and students.

Key Objective:

- Gather data from the GEAM Survey
- Map the situation regarding gender equality in FredU
- Create an updated database for each Institution
- Be able to make comparisons, keep track of changes, improvements or pitfalls

Implementation Date: April 2025

Formative Evaluation First Round

The formative evaluation activities for this action included a review of the GEAM survey with the University's top management and members of the ENAF committee. Conducted in October and November 2024, the review involved discussions on selecting questions, target groups (academics, administrative staff, and students), and strategies to ensure high response rates. The NEXUS FredU team participated in training on the tool to enhance their skills in survey design and analysis. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative Evaluation Second Round

The formative evaluation's second round has been done through a GEAM survey launched in March 2025 and closed in April 2025. The targeted participants were all members of Frederick University. The results from the GEAM survey at Frederick University has been already sent to the top administration. This action was finished in April 2025.

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

On the Formative Evaluation Report of Frederick University there was no further information about the second round of formative activities.

Outcome foreseen for action 2: Increase awareness on the topic.

Outcome achieved for action 2: Increase awareness on the topic.

Section Redesign Process

During the first and second Workshop Evaluation and Redesign (25 and 26 September 2024), there was an agreement among partners regarding the sections to use and it was decided that the same action will be implemented in different partners' contexts. Thanks to the monitoring indicators of the GEAM tool, the progress of the action was evaluated avoiding any delay. Frederick University couldn't launch the survey in November 2024 because of these issues a formal review by the University was required. In fact, Frederick University had some resistance to two issues: the non-binary option on the gender question and the revealing of some financial aspects through some questions. By now the final evaluation tool for the effectiveness of the action is the number of participants to complete the questionnaire.

During the third Evaluation and Redesign Workshop (10 April 2025), Frederick University informed the other two partners of the respond rate of the survey and the initial results. The respond rate was satisfactory. Results from the GEAM survey at Frederick University have already been sent to the top administration. No resistance as far as implementation is concerned. In fact, the university wanted to run the GEAM survey to assist the application of the Athena Swan in November 2025. By now the final evaluation tool for the effectiveness of the action is the number of participants to complete the questionnaire. FredU had 233 responses.

During the fourth Evaluation and Redesign Workshop (3 June 2025), the action was declared completed. The GEAM tool is expected to be implemented every 4-5 years. No other resistance or adjustment has been encountered.

Action 3 - Fostering participation in work-related training through data collection with a Gender Equality and Intersectional perspective (Twin Trio action)

This action concerns data collection and analysis to map the situation and establish the short-term trends of staff participation in professional training by gender and other inequality areas. A monitoring and evaluation action will follow the internal training taking place for three years, 2022-23, 2023-24, 2024-25 at each trio-partner and will map the trends using an intersectional perspective. For FredU data have been gathered for the year 2022-2023 and have been analyzed. The analysis is done based on gender, type of training, rank of the academic, and position (academic/administrative personnel).

The same analysis has been conducted for the year 2023-2024. Both these results were available in December 2024. For the academic year 2024-2025 data has been gathered for the first semester of the academic year 2024-2025 (Fall24) and analyzed at that point. Once data are gathered for the 2.5 academic years, a comparative analysis is conducted, and the results are given to the top management for further action.

Key Objective: Data collection and analysis to map the situation and establish the short-term trends of the participation of staff in professional training in gender and other inequality areas

Implementation date: April 2025

Formative Evaluation First Round

Data collection and analysis of training participation by gender and role were central to the first round of evaluation for this action. The NEXUS FredU team collaborated with the P2DF secretariat to access anonymized data from past training sessions. This evaluation, conducted in October 2024, provided insights into participation trends, focusing on variables such as training type, gender, and job rank. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative Evaluation Second round

The formative evaluations second round has been done through the examination of the data gathered in the previous months. This activity ended on 30 April 2025. Data for 4 semesters (2 academic years) have been gathered.

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

On the Formative Evaluation Report of Frederick University there is no further information about the second round of formative activities.

Outcome foreseen for action 3: improved the diversity in the participation in training

Outcome achieved for action 3: improved the diversity in the participation in training

Section Redesign process

During the first and second Evaluation and Redesign workshop (25 and 26 September 2024), all partners presented what they had already achieved until September 2024 and their challenges. Partners agreed that the initial design of the Action will be followed but implementing it according to partners' contexts (availability of data and others). The main monitoring indicator for the Action was the gathering of the data. FredU did not face any resistances. The main evaluation tool is the gathering of the data for a minimum of 2 years.

During the third Evaluation and Redesign Workshop (10 April 2025) the results achieved until April 2024, and their challenge were presented. Frederick University had a delay in sending the data for Fall 2024 due to a change in the management of the office responsible for collecting the data of the training. It was expected that the data for the training series of Fall 2024 would complete the action. As it was not foreseen when the data would be sent to the NEXUS team, Frederick University had considered the action completed. There was no resistance to the implementation of action-gathering data. The FredU NEXUS team had data from 4 semesters. The main evaluation tool was gathering data for enough time, that is a minimum of 2 years, which is already achieved.

During the last Evaluation and Redesign Workshop (3 June 2025), the FredU NEXUS team asked the GEP team whether it was possible to receive the data of the 5th semester on time before the Project finishes.

No further adjustments were required. There was no resistance in the implementation of the action-gathering the data. The delay mentioned above was the only resistance faced by Frederick University.

Action 4 Inclusive communication guidelines (Twin Trio Action)

This action aims to provide the community with practical guidance on internal and external communication patterns for inclusive language and set standards for internal and external communication. Students' and researchers' desk research and short interviews with staff and students will take place. The trio discussed the progress and status in Cyprus during the second study visit. At the end, authorities at Frederick University will review the guidelines, and a final version will be disseminated.

Key Objective:

- Design guidelines to make communication within and outside the university fairer and more inclusive.
- Enhance competencies: knowledge, skills, and attitudes.
- Provide the community with a practical guidance on communication patterns in English for inclusive language.
- Set standards for internal and external communication.
- Share lessons learned and support mutual learning among the Trios

Implementation Date: August 2025

Formative Evaluation First Round

The first round of evaluation involved reviewing draft guidelines with top management and ENAF committee members in October 2024. These discussions focused on ensuring the inclusion of intersectional perspectives and tailoring content to address diverse needs, including those of LGBTQI+, neurodiverse, and disabled individuals. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative Evaluation Second Round

The formative evaluation second round was done on 3 June 2025. The activity conducted was a discussion on the implementation of the guidelines with top management. The meeting was composed of 4 participants (2 males and 2 females) belonging to administrative, research and teaching staff. A representative of the NEXUS Team at Frederick University joined the meeting.

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

The gender inclusive language guide has been already implemented. The discussion with top management focused on the implementation of the guide in English language. At Frederick University, top management is the decision-making body for the implementation of this action. For this action, external actors were involved: a group of students from AGH, representatives of the ENAF, and Frederick University Equality committee. The team at the local level had the necessary skills required for the implementation of the action and in addition the same is valid at the twin trio level. This action is a little behind the other actions because the developing of the English version of the

guide is ongoing. It is expected that the action will finish on time. The implementation of the action aligns with its objectives. and meets its intersectional objectives: the guidelines include intersectional perspectives and address topics like, LGBTQI+, religion, race, people with disabilities, older people, etc. There are no deviations from the planned activities either in relation to design of the action, the monitoring and evaluation plan, the content, or the timeframe. Most of the expected outcomes of the action have been achieved. What remains to be seen is the implementation of the guidelines. The trio's good cooperation facilitated the outcomes of the action while some resistances and delays hindered the action. The main barrier was the resistance to the English version: due to the Greek version of the guide, some resistance from the university, to implement the English version was foreseen. The NEXUS Team at Frederick University worked on convincing the implementation of the guidelines because this action can contribute to an inclusive university, and gender equality. Finally, the two main issues of this action are the delays and the resistance of the university. The guidelines, once they are implemented, will be permanently used at the university and will be improved and enriched in a way to keep them relevant and sustained.

Outcome foreseen for action 4: increased awareness among the top management in FredU; implementation and usage of Inclusive Communication in FredU.

Outcome achieved for action 4: increased awareness among the top management in FredU; the outcome related to implementation and usage of the Inclusive Communication in FredU is not yet achieved.

Section Redesign Process

During the first and second Evaluation and Redesign workshop (25 and 26 September 2024), FredU informed the partners that the Greek version of the guidelines was under preparation. The English version was awaited from AGH and BZN and FredU provided feedback and comments. For all partners this is a new Action. It was agreed that each partner should have a section on their native language. The main monitoring indicator is the draft guidelines. Some partners have already elaborated the guidelines in their own language while others have not. Nevertheless, no delays were foreseen. No resistance was encountered. Once the guidelines are finished, an evaluation indicator could be feedback from selected members of the universities.

During the Evaluation and Redesign Process held on 10 April 2025, FredU informed the partners that the Greek version of the guidelines was finished and FredU provided feedback and comments to the draft of AGH. It was decided to change the structure of the guidelines. Both BZN and FredU expressed their concerns about the universities accepting the guidelines. The main monitoring indicator was the draft guidelines. The documents were almost finished. The Greek version was already designed, and a training was foreseen. The English one which includes the non-binary gender might not be accepted to be used by the university. During the last Evaluation and Redesign workshop held on 3 June 2025, it was discussed that the action was still in progress. All partners, especially BZN and FredU, are experiencing resistance. The University has already launched a Greek version of some guidelines therefore it would be strange to implement new guidelines. The only action that might be at risk for sustainability is the guidelines on inclusive and gender-neutral language.

Action 5 - Annual training from an external speaker on GE and intersectionality under the Personal and Professional Committee (P2DF) (Partner Action)

This action concerns annual training from an external speaker on Gender Equality and intersectionality under the P2DF Committee to increase awareness on the specific topic, to inform the faculty of the university about their rights, to improve the personal and professional development of the faculty, and to follow the trends in other European universities. This action has been implemented in the first or second semester of the academic year 2024-2025. An external stakeholder was invited to the university to provide training, using intersectional lenses, on topics on gender equality and intersectionality, and fall under one of the five thematic areas of the Frederick University GEP.

Key Objective

- Provide annual training to staff and faculty on how to facilitate either disabled student, minorities, LGBTQI+, migrants etc.
- Increase awareness of the topic.
- Inform the decisions of the policy makers of the university.
- Inform the faculty of the university about their rights.

- Improve the personal and professional development of the faculty.
- Follow the trends on GE and intersectionality in other European Universities.

Implementation Date: December 2024

Formative Evaluation First Round

The first round of formative evaluation activities for action 5 included preparatory meetings with the selected trainer, an experienced NGO-accredited specialist in gender and intersectionality. The agreed training sessions were conducted on 9 and 12 December 2024. These sessions were held across the two campuses of the University to maximize accessibility and participation. The trainer delivered focused sessions on topics such as menopause, ageism, and well-being. The training was designed to promote awareness of intersectional challenges faced by individuals in academic and professional environments. Participants included administrative staff, teaching staff, and researchers, reflecting a diverse range of roles and perspectives. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative Evaluation Second Round

This action ended in December 2024. Training on menopause was provided successfully on both campuses at Frederick University.

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

On the Formative Evaluation Report of Frederick University there are not further information about the second round of formative activities.

Outcome foreseen for action 5: increase the awareness among the members of FredU on the topic.

Outcome achieved for action 5: increase the awareness among the members of FredU on the topic.

Section Redesign process

The first Evaluation and Redesign Workshop for this action was held on 3 October 2024 among the members of the Equality and Awareness at Frederick (ENAF) Center and the Members of the Self-Assessment Team (SAT) for the Athena Swan application. During the workshop, the GEP-ENAF group

discussed various topics and various speakers. The NEXUS team suggested training on Menopause and wellbeing and a trainer specialized in the topic. The GEP-ENAF group agreed to the suggestion. It was decided that the training was delivered to both campuses, in Nicosia and Limassol, before the end of the year 2024. The dates were 9 and 12 of December 2024. This was the first time that the university had offered training of this type, and the number of participants has been monitored. An exit questionnaire was delivered to the participants as a tool for the evaluation of the action. There was no major resistance to this action. The monitoring indicators for this action are:

- A list of suggested topics provided to P2DF-done.
- Topic and title name of the trainer -done.
- Dates of the training -done.

Number of evaluation questionnaires-not yet done.

3.3 Sofia University (UNISOFIA)

The following table summarizes the monitoring, evaluation, and redesign process of the pilot actions carried out by Sofia University within the NEXUS project.

Sofia University				
GEP'Areas	# Pilot Actions	#Formative Evaluation I round	#Formative Evaluation II round	#Actions adjusted following the Redesign Process
Work-life balance and organizational culture				
Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment	2	2	2	1
Gender balance in leadership and decision making				
Data Collection	1	1	1	
Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	2	2	2	2
Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content				
Total	5	5	5	3

The following describes their 5 pilot actions, the findings from the second round of formative evaluation activities, and the redesign process carried out.

Action 1 - GBV Training and Awareness Online Module (Twin Trio Action)

The action includes an assessment of individuals' understanding and awareness of GBV. It is meant to improve awareness and understanding of what GBV's manifestations are and provide strategies and information how about to deal with experiences of GBV (observed & experienced personally).

The online module about GBV was also planned to function as a resource for those working in partner institutions (and beyond) to improve their practice

The development of this action started in June 2024 with the design of a concrete project plan. Until the end of July 2024, the training materials were compiled. Work on putting together the module content took place between August and November 2024, with the leading role of TU Dublin. At the same time online meetings and discussions on refining the contents and the focus of the module were carried out within the trio. It was agreed within the trio that KU was responsible for the design of an awareness video to be inserted in the training module, while Sofia University designed the interactive part, undertaking the graphic design to put the whole module contents in a visual format. The deadline for the finalization of the module was 31 January 2025.

Key Objectives: to provide a skill and knowledge-based e-course meant to educate and develop strategies for adopting an active position in a bystander situation; to raise awareness of various manifestations of GBV; to provide strategies to both deal with and combat GBV in partner institutions and beyond.

Implementation date: May 2025

Formative Evaluation First Round

The formative evaluation activities for the GBV Training and Awareness Online Module action were conducted through a workshop during the Trio Study Visit at TU Dublin on November 26, 2024. This workshop involved members of the NEXUS team, including key institutional representatives from UNISOFIA, TU Dublin, and KU (6 participants, all females). These sessions facilitated discussions on the action's design, content, and implementation of progress. The evaluation activities ensured that diverse insights from the participating institutions were incorporated into the development of the module. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative Evaluation Second Round

The second round of the formative evaluation activities for the GBV Training and Awareness Online Module action was conducted through a monitoring and evaluation workshop held on 15 April 2025.

This workshop involved members of the NEXUS team (5 participants, all females). In Sofia University, the main body involved in the implementation of the action is the NEXUS team: Albena Yarcheva, Svetlana Dimitrova, Valentina Mitkova and Natalia Rekova. Members of the NEXUS team at the university have led the development of the module. Meetings with institutional experts have been planned for the implementation of action.

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

No institutional body was established to implement the action. No external actors were involved in the implementation of the action. No formative evaluation in May has been planned.

Activities have been carried out as follows:

- Accumulation of training materials for the online module (Achieved) provided by TU Dublin
- Video for the module – TU Dublin, Koch University, SU
- Construction of an easy-to-navigate platform for the module (this activity has been dropped as the module will be hosted by the NEXUS website and made available on YouTube)
- Development of professional networks through which the module can be disseminated (Achieved)
- Record/documenting of the number of people signing up and completing the module (not achieved)
- 40 people per partner institution to complete the module (May 2025) (Not yet achieved)
- Increased awareness and understanding of GBV (not yet achieved)

The original timeline set at the beginning (action planning stage) was not realistic due to the complexities associated with the development of the action. In consequence, the timeline was modified. The implementation of the action is aligned with its objectives, but it is aligned with its intersectional goals. There have been deviations both in the content of the action and in the timeframe. These deviations are as follows:

It was agreed within the trio that the GBV module will focus on bystander situations. TU Dublin developed module content, with inputs from GBV experts in TU Dublin, Sofia University and KU reviewing and updating module content. KU designed an awareness-raising video to be inserted in the course, while Sofia University was responsible for the graphic design of the rest of the module. The time for launching the module was rescheduled for 7 February 2025. Changes were made both

in relation to the focus of the module and the time frame of its implementation. The factors that inhibit the action were technical expertise because the organizers of the action do not possess the technical skills necessary to develop the action. Main barrier was the need for a high level of resources to develop a module that is of professional quality. These barriers have been overcome by transferring the budget from Sofia University to KU for the design of an awareness video produced by professionals. This video was inserted into the module. At the same time, Sofia University relied on in-house expertise in graphic design. No resistance has been experienced so far, and no one is envisaged. The action did not have unexpected outcomes. After the NEXUS project ends, the module will be hosted by the NEXUS website.

Outcome foreseen action 1: increased awareness and understanding of GBV

Outcome achieved action 1: increased awareness and understanding of GBV has been partially achieved

Section Redesign process

The Redesign Process of action 1 has been discussed in 3 different workshops: a First Workshop on 25 September 2024, a Second Workshop on 26 November 2024 and a third Workshop on 15 April 2025. During the first workshop and second workshop (25 September 2024 and 26 November 2024), It was decided that TU Dublin will continue to focus on bystander intervention, raising awareness and developing skills/ strategies to adopt an active position in such situations. The material for the online module was in the process of being gathered and compiled into a module. No resistance has been encountered. Challenges envisioned were (in terms of monitoring and evaluation process) related to providing GBV experts to review and evaluate the module. Basic worries/ doubts were related to the design of the module and the level of interactivity.

During the second workshop (26 November 2024), Trio partners agreed on the objectives and scope of the action, making adaptations to fit each institution's needs. TU Dublin developed module content, with inputs from GBV experts in TU Dublin, UNISOFIA and KU reviewing and updating module content. It was decided that KU designed an awareness-raising video to be integrated into the e-course, while UNISOFIA is responsible for designing the interactive part of the module. For UNISOFIA implementation of the action specifically, the following modifications were made in these

sections: Activities; Timeframe; Outputs; Outcomes; Impact. The timeframe was modified, postponing the release of action to February 2025. The materials were gathered and compiled into the structure of a module. No resistance was encountered. Tracking was done at the national level, not at the institutional level. The quality of the module was measured by post module evaluation completed by individuals who have taken the course. The contribution of each partner institution to the construction of the GBV module was clarified. During the third Workshop (15 April 2025), the following modifications were made: the launch date has been delayed to early May. No resistance was found. No sustainability issues have been identified in UNISOFIA as this is an action to be embedded in a current mentoring program that is well-established already.

Action 1 was redesigned as detailed above.

**Action 2 - Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression - a Needs Analysis and
Action 3 - Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression and Success (enhancing the existing
Mentoring program) – (Twin Trio Actions)**

Action 2 and Action 3 (thematically co-related and planned to be subsequently released): Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression - a Needs Analysis (Action 2) and Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression and Success (Action 3), inspired by TU Dublin and Sofia University mentoring programs. The development of these related actions began in June 2024 (with preparations for Action 2) and the completion of the implementation of this action was planned for November 2024. As for Action 3, the implementation of this action was originally planned to be completed in March 2025, and this has been changed to an earlier time, namely February 2025. Activities completed so far are as follows: 1) construction of questionnaires (in two versions and in Bulgarian and English) to be disseminated among PhD students and young researchers 2) Dissemination of the questionnaires through email invitations/reminders 3) Data analysis based on the responses to the questionnaires.

Key Objectives Action 2: Collection of data to provide information and a baseline of the needs for mentoring in partner institutions. Analysis of the data collected (about mentoring needs of doctoral students and early career researchers). Final goal: to ascertain the baseline needs of PhDs and young researchers in relation to mentoring at Sofia University.

Key Objectives Action 3: - Operating with the data gathered and analyzed to enhance the existing mentoring programs in partner institutions, advancing the career prospects of PhD students and early career researchers and developing their self-confidence on transversal skills and transitions to industry. Final goal: to ascertain the baseline needs of PhDs and young researchers in relation to mentoring in Sofia University

Implementation Date Action 2: December 2024

Implementation Date Action 3: June 2025

Section Formative Evaluation First Round Results

The formative evaluation activities for the Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression actions were conducted through surveys and discussions during the M&E workshop between Trio at TU Dublin on November 26, 2024. These activities engaged NEXUS team members and institutional experts (6 participants, all females) to assess mentoring needs and inform the design of a tailored mentoring program for PhD students and young researcher. Full analysis is reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#)

Formative Evaluation –Second Round

The Formative Evaluation second round was made with monthly trio meetings. Monitoring & Evaluation workshops with trio partner teams and institutional experts/persons responsible for the implementation of action. The last Monitoring & Evaluation workshop was held on 15 April 2025. In addition to the monthly trio meetings, the formative evaluation activities for this action were conducted as part of the Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) workshop held online with Trio Partners on 15 April 2025. The workshops included trio partner teams. Meetings with institutional experts were planned for the implementation of the action.

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

The main decision-making bodies involved and responsible for the implementation of Action 2 and Action 3 implementation were Human Resources Department (for contacting PhD students/ young researchers and dissemination of the surveys via e-mails), NEXUS team members (for accumulating data and their analysis), NEXUS team members and Career Progression Department (for enhancing

the existing Mentoring Program with new courses/ mentors to respond to the needs outlined). No external actors were involved in Action 2. As per Action 3, mentors from business/industries/NGOs were envisioned to be engaged as well. The actions didn't request the involvement of institutional bodies because they built an existing mentoring program. For Sofia University, the timeframe was clarified and fixed (adjusted to the start of the academic year and the period new PhD students are enrolled). The action aligned well with its objectives and met its intersectional goals by promoting inclusivity for non-Bulgarian speakers and mobile students. There were no delays, barriers, or resistance. The implementation of the action was fully supported by top management, with one of the Vice-Rectors actively participating as a mentor. Responsibilities were distributed among the NEXUS team. Activities were carried out as planned, including conducting a bilingual survey that led to updates in the Mentoring Program, such as the inclusion of gender-sensitive topics and accessibility for international students. These actions contribute to the advancement of inclusiveness in career progression of PhD students/ young researchers in university institutions. It is also meant to stimulate integration of gender dimension in scientific research by studying the extent to which this aspect has been covered so far (Action 2) and implementing such content (training courses, experts) in the Mentoring Program (Action 3). The program has increased awareness of gender perspectives in research and contributed to institutional change through activities like training and podcast development. While the expected outcomes were achieved, continued efforts are needed, particularly to attract more mentors. The Mentoring Program is ongoing, with clear plans for its future improvement and expansion to ensure long-term sustainability. As the action will be fully integrated into the existing mentoring program for researchers, its sustainability is guaranteed if the program continues.

Outcome foreseen action 2: baseline needs assessment in relation to mentorship; understanding of the base line needs in relation to mentoring in the partner institutions.

Outcome foreseen action 3: mentees will have the opportunity to go through a mentoring program (that will include solutions to skill enhancing)

Outcome achieved action 2: baseline needs assessment in relation to mentorship; understanding of the base line needs in relation to mentoring in the partner institutions.

Outcome achieved action 3: the achievement is ongoing.

Section Redesign process

UNISOFIA did the redesign process for this action twice, the first time in Nicosia on 25 September 2024 and during the trio visit at TU Dublin on 26 November 2024.

In the TU Dublin Evaluation and Redesign Workshop, the participation of UNISOFIA was declared at the third workshop held on 15 April 2025, but this workshop is not indicated in the UNISOFIA Report.

In this workshop for Action 3 UNISOFIA highlighted that:

- The action was aimed at providing inclusive mentoring guidelines which are embedded in an already existing mentoring program.
- The action doesn't have an intersectoral dimension because it involves mentors only from university
- In UNISOFIA, their mentoring program in which these inclusive mentoring guidelines will be embedded has less than 20 mentors. (the indicator is reduced).

The following action 2 and action 3 have been reported together as already done for Twin Trio partners above, due to their simultaneous implementation during the project and the deep correlation.

First Evaluation and Redesign Workshop on 25 September 2024.

Action 2

The redesign process of this action defined the construction of survey in English and Bulgarian, and the creation of two different surveys for those who have already attended the existing Mentoring program in Sofia University and for those who have not. In addition, UNISOFIA in accordance with the Trio planned the timeframe of the single activities:

- June-September – constructing the survey
- October 1st - November 15th – disseminating the survey
- November 15th - December – analysis of the survey.

The material for the online module was in the process of being gathered and compiled into a module. No resistance has been encountered.

Action 3

Manual/guidelines will be produced drawing from the data gathered in action 2 (questionnaires completed by PhD students/ young researchers and their analysis). No resistance was encountered. The monitoring and evaluation plans for this action included ensuring that the materials available for mentors guarantee that the inclusive mentoring practice is increased.

Second Evaluation and Redesign Workshop 26 November 2024**Action 2**

No resistance was encountered.

Action 3

The redesign process modified the timeframe, postponing the implementation of the modified mentoring program in June 2025. Trio partners went through each of the monitoring indicators reviewing the status of the action against those indicators and deciding whether new indicators should be added or else whether there were indicators that should be deleted. No resistance was encountered. Action 2 and Action 3 were redesigned as detailed above.

Action 4 - Data collection and percentage monitoring among students, PhDs, academic and administrative staff in Sofia University, related to gender, age and professional position.**(Partner Action)**

The action is related to collecting data about gender, age, socioeconomic status, disabilities, gender balance in leadership and decision making, gender equality in recruitment and career progression, work-life balance, social inclusiveness of the institution. The goal of data collection was analysis of the data collected.

Key Objectives: To strengthen the University's reputation as an inclusive educational institution and workplace; to establish and sustain a tolerant institutional culture where everyone is treated equally and where diversity is interpreted as a strength rather than a challenge.

Implementation Date: December 2024

Section Formative Evaluation First Round Results

The formative evaluation activities for action 4 were conducted through collaboration between the HR department and the NEXUS team. Data on demographic and professional metrics were collected and analyzed to identify gaps in gender equality and inclusiveness. This effort involved institutional experts and NEXUS project members. More feedback is reported in the [deliverables 3.2](#).

Formative Evaluation Second Round

The formative evaluation activities for action 4 were conducted through the focus group of participants at the NEXUS team and experts responsible for the implementation of the action. The focus group was composed by 4 participants all females.

Overview formative evaluation second round

The working group of the GEP is responsible for the implementation of the action and the top management of the university was involved. No external stakeholder was involved. The action was successfully carried out: the activities have been carried out as foreseen; the analysis of the data was already made and it will be compared to the analysis from the next year, in order to monitor and detect problems if there are any and will serve to monitor gender-related trends, particularly in male and female career progression. This data is included in the annual reports of the Rector and Faculty Deans, reinforcing institutional accountability. All activities were completed on time, without any deviations, delays, or resistance. The implementation is fully aligned with both the general and intersectional objectives of the action. The commitment from top leadership and facilitated access to institutional data were key enabling factors. The action is now embedded in the GEP as a recurring measure, ensuring long-term sustainability and ongoing contributions to gender equality and institutional transformation. This action will be carried out every year.

Outcome foreseen action 4: strengthening the University's reputation as an inclusive educational institution and workplace

Outcome achieved action 4: strengthening the University's reputation as an inclusive educational institution and workplace

Section Redesign process

The action didn't require any adjustment following the redesign process.

Action 5 - Promotion of the University Center for Psychological Counseling and Research in relation to counseling/psychological support in cases of gender-based violence. (Partner Action)

This action is an additional counseling topic related to combat gender-based violence. Through inclusion of additional counseling topics related to combating gender-based violence in the Center's services it is meant a set of psychological and social tools for overcoming traumas and negative experience with GBV to be offered to students, academic and administrative staff at the university. Timeframe: Permanent

Key Objective: To establish a safe and supportive university environment for everyone who has faced gender-based violence; to provide psychological and social tools for overcoming traumas and negative experiences.

Implementation Date: December 2024

Section Formative Evaluation First Round Results

The formative evaluation activities for action 5 were conducted through focus groups with institutional experts and Counseling Center representatives. These sessions evaluated the addition of gender-based violence (GBV) counseling services and awareness training ([deliverables 3.2](#))

Section Formative Evaluation Second Round

The formative evaluation activities for action 4 were conducted through the focus group of participants at the NEXUS team and experts responsible for the implementation of the action. The focus group was composed by 4 participants all females.

Overview of the Formative Evaluation Second Round

All planned activities have been carried out on time and in line with the initial objectives, without delays or deviations. While intersectional dimensions have not yet been fully addressed, the action effectively meets its core objectives, particularly in tackling gender-based violence (GBV) within the academic context. The voluntary commitment of the Centre's team, combined with institutional support, has been a key driver of successful implementation. To ensure sustainability, the Centre will continue its operations and enhance visibility through upcoming promotional materials. Overall, the action has contributed meaningfully to strengthening institutional support structures and fostering a safer, more inclusive university environment.

Outcome foreseen action 5: psychological help for successful re-integration in the working/ educational process; establishment of a safe and supportive university environment for everyone who has faced gender-based violence

Outcome achieved action 5: psychological help for successful re-integration in the working/ educational process; establishment of a safe and supportive university environment for everyone who has faced gender-based violence.

Redesign process

The action didn't require any adjustment following the redesign process.

3.4 Le Mans University (UM)

The following table summarizes the monitoring, evaluation, and redesign process of the pilot actions carried out by Le Mans University within the NEXUS project.

Le Mans University				
GEP'Areas	# Pilot Actions	#Formative Evaluation I round	#Formative Evaluation II round	#Actions adjusted following the Redesign Process
Work-life balance and organizational culture	1	1	1	1
Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment	1	1	1	
Gender balance in leadership and decision making				
Data Collection				
Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	2	2	2	1
Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content	1	1	1	1
Total	5	5	5	3

The following describes their 5 pilot actions, the findings from the second round of formative evaluation activities, and the redesign process carried out.

Action 1 - Influence of biases in decision-making (Twin Trio Action)

The purpose of this action is to tackle biases in recruitment. A survey was designed inside the trio, and it was submitted to the universities' staff to understand their biases. It was decided to have two different training courses. A general one by Angelina Etiemble, open to all the staff. It took place in November 2024, and good feedback was received. The other training course was designed for people in charge of recruitment. It has been delivered in February 2025 and provided by an external stakeholder.

Key Objective: Tackling biases in recruitment

Implementation Date: February 2025

Formative Evaluation – First Round

The formative evaluation activities for the Influence of Biases in Decision-Making action were conducted using a post-training questionnaire distributed after the first training session led by Angéline Etiemble on November 26, 2024. The questionnaire gathered feedback from 32 participants (8 men, 24 women), including administrative staff, teachers, and teacher-researchers. The session aimed to assess participants' understanding of cognitive biases, focusing on their application in recruitment and career progression decisions. The feedback collected helped evaluate the training's relevance, content delivery, and alignment with institutional goals. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative Evaluation Second Round

The second round of the formative evaluation activities for this action was conducted through a focus group held on 16 May 2025. This focus group was composed of:

- 5 persons, all female, in charge with different roles (teachers, researchers, administrative staff)
- 2 people in charge of GEP working group

During the discussion it emerged that the Human Resources Directorate was the decision-making body for the action, and it validated and promoted the action. Internal and external experts were involved because internally there was only basic knowledge of sociology. The training delivered by

internal experts reached more than 30 people. The training delivered by external experts reached 22 people. According to the ex-post-test questionnaires and the oral feedback, the participants felt more aware of unconscious biases after the trainings and more equipped to reflect on their own biases and to fight them

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

Thanks to the ex-post-test questionnaire, it was possible to identify the areas of improvement, participants suggested having more interactive exercises and tips and the involvement of trainers that are themselves teachers-researchers and who know well all the specificities of higher education. The session delivered by the training firm was delayed. It was initially planned for December but took place in the beginning of February. It was difficult to recruit participants among the HR staff due to the busy schedule. The action has achieved its objectives and the intersectional goals: these training courses have been designed to be as intersectional as possible, including gender bias as well as other types of bias (reasoning, judgmental or personality bias, related to culture, language, social influence, etc.). The outcome foreseen has been achieved. Except for the delay detailed above, the action was implemented according to the initial design. The contribution of external partners, professionals and experts on the subject enabled more specialized training that met the expectations of participants, particularly HR staff. The participation of people from different parts of the university in these training courses has enabled enriching exchanges. In fact, the action has been appreciated by the academic community, due to the scientific aspect and the willingness to combat one's own biases. Understanding of challenges and obstacles in the courses: identifying at least 1 area of improvement in the training: thanks to the post-test questionnaire, areas of improvement were identified. More tools are needed to help people fight their own biases, more interactive exercises and tips to help them make their colleagues more aware. It would be better to call on different experts for teacher-researcher training, someone who is themselves a teacher-researcher and who knows well all the specificities of higher education. The action did not encounter barriers and resistances. No deviations and unexpected outcomes. The Gender Equality Mission will provide general training every year. Training for HR staff will be planned every year or every two years. We'd also like to offer a short training course in the form of a self-assessment lasting a few minutes before each recruitment panel. After the end of the project, the training is available in the gender equality

mission toolbox on the internal website. In general, the results in terms of gender equality are the increased awareness about gender bias for the staff in charge of recruitment.

Outcome foreseen for action 1: 50 recruiters in total (approximately) will be trained (10 from Serbia, 20 from France, 20 from Italy).

Outcome achieved for action 1: 50 recruiters in total (approximately) have been trained (10 from Serbia, 20 from France, 20 from Italy). 22 people reached for the training delivered by a company and 30 people with the training delivered by NEXUS Team.

Section Redesign process

The action didn't require any adjustment following the redesign process.

Action 2 - Gender Equality and Intersectional dimension in research (Twin Trio Action)

This action aims to foster a gender and intersectional approach in the research field. It consists of a guideline about gender and intersectionality in research, written in collaboration with the researchers. First, we organized interviews with researchers to take stock of their knowledge and motivation on the subject in different disciplines. The trio designed the guidelines. The first review was made at the end of 2024.

Key Objective: A Gender Equality and Intersectional Approach in the Research Fields

Implementation Date: May 2025

Formative Evaluation First Round

The formative evaluation for Gender Equality and Intersectional Dimension in Research action was minimal during the first round, as the action was still in its initial stages. However, a focus group within the Trio held on 4 November 2024, with six Trio members, was used to allocate responsibilities and establish a timeline for the completion of the Gender Equality and Intersectional research guidelines. Discussions during the meeting provided clarity on workload distribution and identified relevant resources, including five existing toolkits and guidelines for adaptation. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative Evaluation second round

The second round of the formative evaluation activities for this action was conducted through a focus group held on 16 May 2025. This focus group was composed of:

- 5 persons, all female, in charge with different roles (teachers, researchers, administrative staff)
- 2 people in charge of GEP working group

The university's laboratories relayed information about the publication of a guide and the organization of a training course for their researchers. Le Mans University also received communications support to spread the word.

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

The guidelines were designed in trio and adapted to each institution by the NEXUS local team. The presentation of the guidelines and the training session was provided by the NEXUS local team, helped by the materials of Smart Venice (train-the-trainers). The action involved only internal experts. Internal staff had the skills needed and didn't need to call on an external stakeholder. Interviews were conducted, a bibliographical work was realised, and the guidelines were written. Trainers' qualities were used to conduct the presentation of the guideline's session. A project officer from the Le Mans University European Research Support Office participated in the action. An interview with him was conducted during the first phase. Then, he presented Horizon Europe and the necessity of integrating the Gender Dimension in proposals during the presentation of the guidelines. Some resources produced by other universities and institutions and free of access were used for the design of the guidelines. Moreover, the participation of the Le Mans University International Research Support Office to the action, was fundamental. The action reached 25 scientists: the outcome planned for the trio was achieved. Thanks to the feedback, Partners identified areas of improvement. The action was implemented in compliance with the initial design. Only the timeline was not realistic, and the action was delayed with respect to the planning: it was the only change.

The action has reached its objectives and intersectional goals; the guidelines gave tips to integrate intersectional dimensions in researchers as well. It did not encounter barriers, but it encountered resistance from people that don't see the interest of integrating gender: some people had difficulties

understanding the purpose of integrating gender and intersectional dimensions in research. Some researchers are intrigued by the subject, wondering how they can integrate gender into their discipline. Sometimes this is a hindrance, sometimes a driving force, driven by scientific curiosity. What's more, the fact that gender mainstreaming is part of the European Union's research framework helps to demonstrate the value of such considerations. The hope is the gradual dissemination of the arguments and tools presented in the guide, through the people who took part in the presentation of the guide. The action works with the university's research laboratories to promote a culture of equality in research content. It also targets doctoral students, who are the future of research. The guidelines are updated every year, in line with the evolution of the European and French policies concerning research. A presentation of the guidelines/training session will be organized 1 or 2 times a year. The main result is that researchers are more aware of how to integrate gender and intersectional dimensions into their research content, and why it is important for social reasons but also for scientific reasons. The fact that the integration of the gender dimension is mandatory in Horizon Europe facilitated the outcome of the action. The guidelines will stay available on the Gender Equality Mission's toolbox, and it will continue after the NEXUS project.

Outcomes foreseen for action 2: 50 people from the trio group institutions will be aware of the importance of Gender Equality and Intersectional issues in research changed in “At least 15 people received the guidelines in Le Mans (sent by email or downloaded on the website)”

Outcomes achieved for action 2: “At least 15 people received the guidelines in Le Mans (sent by email or downloaded on the website)”. Outcome reached inside University of Le Mans.

Section Redesign process

The action was redesigned during the fourth Evaluation and Redesign workshop held on 16 May 2025. This was an internal workshop. The participants were Gender Equality and NEXUS Group, a teacher, an administrative employee and a project manager.

The redesign was oriented to two topics: activities and outcomes. In the first one, the UN added “collects the feedback of the scientists during the presentation session”. They understood the importance of feedback and comments by external reviewers through post-test questionnaire and oral feedback. On the other hand, the outcomes changed little from 50 people awarded the

importance of gender issues in research to 15, reached by email or downloaded on the website. The guidelines need to be updated every year in line with new European and French policies about gender in research. A presentation of the guidelines/training needs to be provided at least once a year. Resistance: some people had difficulties understanding the purpose of integrating gender and intersectional dimensions in research.

Action 3 - Parenting Resource Group (Twin Trio Action)

The purpose of the action is to reach a good work-life balance in the institution by improving the parenting and aidance organization culture. An event about work-life balance was organized during which information on the subject was provided and volunteers to become work-life balance referents were found. Their role will be to organize regular discussion and support groups about a precise work-life balance theme, focusing on parenting and caregiving.

Key Objective: Design open call for Community Builders

Implementation Date: June 2025

Formative Evaluation First Round

Formative evaluation activities for the Parenting Resource Group action included a focus group conducted on 21 November 2024, with three female participants representing administrative staff and a teacher-researcher. The focus group was held at the end of a regular meeting to review progress, reassess priorities, and refine the action's scope and timeline. This evaluation session provided a critical platform for discussing the changes that have emerged during implementation. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative Evaluation Second Round

The second round of the formative evaluation activities for this action was conducted through a focus group held on 16 May 2025. This focus group was composed of:

- 5 persons, all female, in charge with different roles (teachers, researchers, administrative staff)
- 2 people in charge of GEP working group

The main decision-making bodies involved in the action were different services including social action from the HR Department. In fact, different services were involved in the implementation of the action, including external actors like the local association on parenting and caregiving. In addition to that, different university units were reunited to provide the right information to the university community.

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

A community builder as initially planned was not found. The people that are the most concerned by the subject (parenting and caregiving) are the one who have the less time to offer. Consequently, the action was redesigned, and it was decided that it is the responsibility of different university component to organize at least one informative event per year, and 2 to 3 other times to discuss a more precise problematic through round tables or preventive staged reading.

The first redesign concerned the extension of the thematic: it was decided to address not only parenting but also caregiving. The second redesign was to change the form of the action, putting the focus not on finding community builders but on ensuring cohesion in the creation of a working group made of different university's units, to be sure that informative and awareness-raising events on the subject could be organized every year. A working group was formed with the gender equality mission, the sustainability development and social responsibility unit and the quality-of-life work unit. The action was initially supposed to be done in the end of 2024 but, because of difficulties of finding community builders, it was extended it until June 2025. The action achieved its objectives and intersectional goals, because it was addressed gender inequality in parenting but also socio economics disadvantages, taking care of a disabled person (Gender dimension, socio-economic dimension, disability dimension). The factor that promoted the implementation was the little time to look for information for people affected by the thematic: the action provides them information in a more helpful way during a dedicated time which they can identify easily, with a good communication.

The barriers encountered were the impossibility to find community builders. It was also trouble in attracting people to the events. The action was redesigned, but a new communication strategy was needed. This kind of actions needs to become a part of the university's culture to attract more people. If the event becomes annual, people will know what to expect and will dare to come see what it is. They will remember that it happened the year before and couldn't come and will try to come next year. The action is contributing to a culture of equality and inclusion at the University. It helps people understand that these issues are political and not just a private matter, that they can have an impact on the workplace, and that they are a concern for the university. This helps to make issues that were previously kept private more visible and highlights gender inequalities. After the end of the project, the working group will continue, and 2 to 3 events dedicated to parenting and caregiving will be organized each year, with local associations. Thanks to this action, the subject of work-life balance was highlighted within the university community.

Outcome foreseen for action 3: “Number of events planned by the pilot group for this year.

Outcome achieved for action 3: Number of events planned by the pilot group for this year

Section Redesign process

The action didn't require any adjustment following the redesign process.

First Workshop 23 September 2024.

In the framework of the twin trio evaluation and redesign workshop, it was decided to broaden the action and not limit it to the theme of parenthood. It allowed them to reach more people during the informative event. Related issues such as caregiving can be addressed. At Le Mans University, no resistance to implementation was encountered. It was difficult to fix meetings with the different services of the university concerned by thematic because they are very busy, and this subject is not their priority. The changes were the following:

- the frequency of the meetings that the referent should organize. The frequency of the meetings that the referent should organize were changed. It seems more realistic to us to have one meeting every two months on a specific subject related to work/life balance (like parenting or caregiving)

- The number of members: at least 5 people attending to those meetings. Persons should participate to those meetings according to their interest in the subject announced

The changes announced by Le Mans University are little and don't really change the course of the action.

Second Workshop 28 February 2025

This workshop was held with Trio partners during the onsite visit at the University of Le Mans in February 2025. It was too difficult to put a parenting resource group in place with community builders. It was decided to create a pilot group with different university services or departments that are already working on work-life balance related issues. The group was composed by the Gender Equality Mission, the Sustainable Development and Social and Environmental Responsibility Unit and the Quality of Life at Work unit. The new outcomes are the activities launched by the group in the first year. People who are interested by the subject don't have time to organize actions about it, to lead a parenting resource group or meet regularly. Indeed, they are struggling with work-life balance problematics (young children, caregiving). In certain institution, it is difficult to mobilise the people, in particularly in the voluntary context. Most of them don't have time to take new responsibilities.

Fourth Workshop 16 May 2025

This monitoring and evaluation workshop was an internal workshop with the Gender Equality and NEXUS Group, a teacher, an administrative employee, and a project manager. During this workshop, a few more adjustments were made: the University was able to organize only one more event after the informative one. It consisted in a preventive stage reading. It was a way for us to attract a new audience, curious people, during the lunchtime and put the spotlight on a topic related to parenthood. It was decided for the organization of only one more event after the informative one where local association joined, no roundtable with local associations. The resistance to the action was the difficulties to attract people. UM planned to organize 2 to 3 events each year. The action was already redesigned during the third workshop.

Action 4 - Fostering empowerment for women at work (Partner Action)

The purpose is to give women who work or study at Le Mans University more opportunities to develop their careers or future careers. A training-workshop program about empowerment and negotiating for university staff and students will be set up. The first one was planned in December and was a feminist physical and verbal self-defense workshop. Two sessions will be scheduled for the same day, one for the female staff and one for the female students.

Key Objective: To give women more opportunities to develop their careers at university

Implementation Date: May 2025

Formative Evaluation First Round

Formative evaluation activities for action 4 included a focus group held on November 5, 2024, with Coline Clément and Angéline Etiemble, who were involved in the organization of the action. The session reviewed the action's progress and implementation, focusing on the adjustments made to align the action more closely with participant needs and feedback received during preliminary discussions. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative Evaluation Second Round

The second round of the formative evaluation activities for this action was conducted through a focus group held on 16 May 2025. This focus group was composed of:

- 5 persons, all female, in charge with different roles (teachers, researchers, administrative staff)
- 2 people in charge of GEP working group

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

It was necessarily go back to the HR department and the Presidency to set up these workshops on working time. The answer has not always been clear, and while some of them have been able to take place on working time, single-sex workshops cannot be held on working time in the end, so as not to discriminate against some staff. The communication department promoted the workshop. External stakeholders and experts were contacted and involved for delivering the workshops in the implementation of the action:

- Volunteers from the business school Audencia, to give a salary negotiation workshop in non-mixity.
- A trainer for a feminist physical and verbal self-defence workshop.

The only change made was in the time frame because initially, the action was supposed to end up in December 2024. The action achieved its objectives and intersectional goals because the workshops are designed for women (cisgender and transgender), considering age, ethnicity, disability in addressing inequalities. Participants were sometimes able to discuss their own specificities in an intersectional way. The observation that some women are subjected to sexist remarks, particularly in services where they are in the majority, and the need to be empowered, represent the main factor to promote the action. The audience changed a couple of times. Initially, workshops were planned for students, then they were planned also for staff. One of the barriers encountered was the organization of the workshop during working hours, which limits the number of registrations. The main resistance encountered was the accusation of sexism towards men, coming from some male colleagues. The communication was adapted and responded with a pedagogical approach, trying to highlight the benefits of gender neutrality and its advantages, while insisting on the fact that most of our actions were accessible to men. The action contributes to a culture of equality by giving women the keys to resist to GBV. After the end of the project, the same workshops will be proposed, next year, for the people who need a refresher or who couldn't take part in the first sessions. The main outcome was that the workshops provided keys for women to resist to GBV but also a place to meet, exchange and talk about their experiences. The action achieved the outcome of a diffusion of a culture of equality, and it was affected by the need to resist in a context where DEI is threatened.

Outcome foreseen for action 4: At least 1 area of improvement identified in the training

Outcome achieved for action 4: At least 1 area of improvement identified in the training

Section Redesign process

The action was redesigned during the second Evaluation and Redesign workshop held on 18 November 2024. It was decided to align the indicators for female employees with those for female students; to increase the number of training courses and workshops on offer, setting the indicator at 'at least two'; to add an indicator of at least 15 female employees taking part in these workshops and trainings and 15 female students. The only resistance encountered was for a few people who didn't understand why the workshops offered as part of this initiative are single sex. The Formative Evaluation Activity allowed to rethink the way to approach the action. After the first bilateral call with Smart Venice, it was understood that the action wasn't clear and that it looked like it was two actions in one, one for the female employees at the University and one for the female students. It was decided to focus only on the female employees. But during the Formative Evaluation Activity, it was realized that it was a negative thing that the actions could not also benefit female students. Self-confidence must be built up as early as possible, and empowerment in the workplace must start as early as the student's studies. This is even more necessary for female master's and doctoral students.

Consequently, it was decided not to have two different activities for the female employees and for the female students; that's why the mentoring activity for students was delayed, but to double each session planned for the staff. For example, on 10 December 2024, we had a verbal and physical feminist self-defence workshop. The first session, in the morning, was for the women who work at the university and the second one, during the afternoon, was for the female students. It was decided to focus on female employees and on female students both and to double, for students, the session planned for the staff. This is more necessary for female master's and doctoral students. For this reason, the mentoring activity for students was delayed.

During the fourth Evaluation and Redesign Workshop (16 May 2025) a further redesign process was made, involving only the Gender Equality and NEXUS Group, a teacher, an administrative employee and a project manager. This was an internal workshop. UM decided that the indicators would concern only female staff. Female students can benefit from the proposed workshops if this is useful to them. For this reason, UM decided to evaluate only the number of trained personnel. In addition, it is difficult to reach students (partly because of their course schedules). The resistance encountered concerns the non-mixity of the workshops. Some male colleagues have complained about this. Due to the resistance encountered, it could be interesting to consider making these

workshops mixed, with the agreement of the people leading the workshops. These workshops will be repeated every year, and we will call on the same external stakeholders. Perhaps we could consider making these workshops mixed, with the agreement of the people leading the workshops.

Action 5 - Gender, health and well-being (Partner Action)

The key objective was to have a better understanding of physical and mental health issue among women and LGBTQIA+ people at the university. A working group was created focusing on specific themes such as menstrual leaves, trans-identity, sexual orientation, disabling pathologies (endometriosis) and partner will disseminate good practices to students and staff members.

Key Objective: To have a better understanding of physical and mental health issues among women and LGBTQIA+ people at the university.

Implementation Date: May 2025

Formative Evaluation First Round

The formative evaluation for the Gender, Health, and Well-Being action involved a focus group during a working group meeting on September 13, 2024. The six participants, including administrative staff, teachers, and a psychologist, reviewed progress on the action's objectives, which include exploring menstrual leave policies, supporting LGBTQIA+ staff and students, and addressing disabling health conditions like endometriosis. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative Evaluation Second Round

The second round of the formative evaluation activities for this action was conducted through a focus group held on 16 May 2025. This focus group was composed of:

- 5 persons, all female, in charge with different roles (teachers, researchers, administrative staff)
- 2 people in charge of GEP working group

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

In the implementation of the action different services and component are involved in the working group but there is no direct commitment from top management. The gender equality mission (NEXUS team) leads the group. Everyone can participate in the meeting they want according to the subject matter. The gender equality mission has knowledge about gender, but external experts were involved to go deeper in some knowledge:

- Trainers from local associations about LGBTQIA+ rights were invited to give a training to the group (and beyond).
- A speaker specialised in autism and gender gave a talk (online) to the group

The action was implemented as originally planned, with the only modification being the extension of the timeline: meetings continued until May 2025, instead of concluding in December 2024 as initially scheduled (no redesign of the action was necessary). The initiative successfully achieved its objectives and intersectional goals, addressing a wide range of topics including menstrual leaves, allyship for LGBTQIA+ people, the intersection of autism and gender, and the importance of not gendered toilets,). No barriers or unexpected outcomes were encountered during the implementation.

The action significantly contributed to fostering a culture of inclusion and increasing the visibility of the LGBTQIA+ individuals within the university community. Following the end of the project, the working group will continue to meet at least 3 times a year to assess ongoing needs. The tools co-developed during the process will remain in use during awareness-raising activities and will be included in the Gender Equality Mission's toolbox. This will help in achieving the main goals of the action who is a heightened awareness of gender-based violence (GBV), across the university community.

Outcome foreseen for action 5: Identify specific problems encountered by women and by LGBTQIA+ people and possible solutions; Identify possible solutions to the problems encountered by women and by LGBTQIA+ people.

Outcome achieved for action 5: A university community more aware of GBV

Section Redesign process

HORIZON-WIDERA-2022ERA-01-81

The action didn't require any adjustment following the redesign process.

3.5 AGH University of Science and Technology (AGH)

The following table summarizes the monitoring, evaluation, and redesign process of the pilot actions carried out by AGH University of Science and Technology within the NEXUS project.

AGH University of Science and Technology				
GEP'Areas	# Pilot Actions	#Formative Evaluation I round	#Formative Evaluation II round	#Actions adjusted following the Redesign Process
Work-life balance and organizational culture	1	1	1	1
Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment				
Gender balance in leadership and decision making	1	1	1	
Data Collection	2	2	2	2
Gender equality in recruitment and career progression				
Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content	1	1	1	1
Total	5	5	5	4

The following describes their 5 pilot actions, the findings from the second round of formative evaluation activities, and the redesign process carried out.

Action 1 E-course on Gender Equality and Intersectionality (Twin Trio Action)

Key Objective:

- Create an e-course with a Gender Equality and Intersectionality approach.
- Increase/Improve equality and diversity in research content

Implementation Date: May 2025

Formative evaluation First Round

The formative evaluation activities for the E-Course on Gender Equality and Intersectionality involved a focus group conducted on 24 September 2024. The participants included eight females and one male, comprising three instructional designers from AGH and six NEXUS Trio partners involved in evaluating the intersectionality of the e-course. The session aimed to identify gaps in course content, assess its alignment with objectives, and enhance its intersectional dimension. Additionally, an evaluation survey for the pilot participants of the redesigned e-course was planned for January 2025. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative evaluation Second round

The AGH team did a Focus group with the team involved in evaluation of the intersectionality in the e-course (authors, instructional designers) during the Budapest trio meeting.

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

On the Formative Evaluation Report of Frederick University there is no further information about the second round of formative activities.

Outcome foreseen for action 1: Increase in course available for next cohorts of participants;
Increased number of people applying intersectional approach in their research proposals

Outcome achieved for action 1: Increase in course available for next cohorts of participants;
Increased number of people applying intersectional approach in their research proposals

Section redesign process

A redesign workshop took place on 25-26 September 2024. During the workshop partners identified all the points, files and topics that need to be improved (intersectionality, translation etc.). This Action is inspired by AGH. During the workshop partners discussed the action monitoring indicators: feedback, review comments, number of recruited participants. Partners believe that the action is not delayed, and it could be finished by the end of January 2025. No resistance from any of the partners. They decided to use feedback from the enrolled participants as the main evaluation tool.

In the Evaluation and Redesign Report AGH has not mentioned other evaluation and redesign workshop for this action.

Action 2 Implementation of the Gender Equality Auditing and Monitoring Tool (Twin Trio Action)

Key Objective:

- Gather data from the GEAM Survey
- Map the situation regarding gender equality in AGH
- Create an updated database for each Institution in the trio
- Be able to make comparisons, keep track of changes, improvements or pitfalls

Implementation Date: January 2025

Formative evaluation First Round

The first round of formative evaluation activities for action 2 involved an open lab conducted on 22 November 2024. Eight participants (five females and three males), including AGH staff and PhD students, collaborated to refine the intersectional question sets in five themes. This activity focused on aligning existing research tools with the new wave of research objectives and adapting the GEAM survey to AGH's Context. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative evaluation Second round

AGH planned a focus group with 10 participants (5 male and 5 female) on 19 February 2025. The participants were researchers, professors and NEXUS Team members.

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

The implementation of the action at the Faculty of Humanities at AGH has involved key decision-making bodies, including the Dean and the AGH Rector, who demonstrated commitment by encouraging the university community to participate in surveys. Responsibilities have been shared between the AGH Gender Equality Plan (GEP) team and the NEXUS team, with the establishment of a quantitative research team to support implementation. While no external actors were explicitly

involved, internal coordination has been strong. Activities have largely followed the initial plan, although the survey was distributed two weeks later than scheduled due to technical challenges adapting the GEAM tool to AGH's context. Despite this delay, the timeline remained realistic, and the action is aligned with both its general and intersectional objectives. No major deviations from planned activities have occurred. One of the main barriers to implementation has been resistance from the male student community toward gender inequality research, which is being addressed through complex interventions. The required expertise in gender, equality, and quantitative research was present within the organizing team. The outcomes of the action were still under analysis, and no unexpected results have been reported so far. Contextual challenges, particularly cultural resistance, have influenced the pace and reception of the action.

Outcome foreseen for action 2: GEAM questionnaire, Report summarising pilot study and discussion

Outcome achieved for action 2: still under analysis

Section redesign process

The first Evaluation and Redesign Workshop was held on 25 – 26 September 2024 among trio partners during the site visit in Cyprus. There was a substantial discussion on the GEAM Tool during the workshop. Partner agreed on the sections to use, the common and the individual sections and that the same action will be implemented in different partners' contexts. The Action is new to AGH. The monitoring indicators of the GEAM tool helped the partner to evaluate the progress of the action and not to have any delays. Creation of accounts, participation in trainings, creation of surveys on GEAM website, and modification of the surveys were some indicators for monitoring and evaluation of the Action before the implementation of the tool. By November 2024 AGH has already launched and finished the survey with other partners. By November 2024 AGH has already launched and finished the survey. By now the final evaluation tool for the effectiveness of the action is the number of participants to complete the questionnaire. In AGH more than 1400 people have already answered the questionnaire.

In the Evaluation and Redesign Report, AGH has not mentioned any other evaluation and redesign workshop for this action.

Action 3 - Fostering participation in work-related training through data collection with a Gender Equality and Intersectional perspective (Twin Trios' action)

Key Objectives: The aim of the action is to gather data about who (in terms of demographic characteristics) participates in work-related training. The process requires gathering data and analyzing it in terms of participants and types of offered training with the aim of identifying patterns of participation and possible gaps.

Implementation date: February 2025

Formative evaluation First Round

This action focuses on analyzing data on participation in work-related training sessions to identify patterns and gaps. An exploratory data analysis conducted in November 2024, as a formative evaluation activity, highlighted challenges related to the fragmented nature of training records at AGH. The evaluation involved reviewing data from various units to determine participation trends and obstacles in obtaining a comprehensive record. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative evaluation Second round

In February 2025, a second round of formative activity was carried out through an activity related to data collection practices: Categorizing the training; Collecting data on participants; Identifying gaps as this activity related to data collection. As this activity relates to data collection practices, the activity consists of analysis of received data and obstacles in obtaining it. Kinga Sekerdej did an analysis of received data and obstacles in obtaining it.

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

The action aimed at collecting data on work-related training at AGH has faced structural challenges due to the absence of a central unit responsible for such data. Only middle management was involved, and data across units was inconsistent, fragmented, and often incomplete. Responsibilities were handled by the NEXUS team, with partial data shared by internal units and insights from a few external stakeholders during an info day. No new bodies were created, though the lack of a central HR unit was identified as a major gap. The action's short and medium-term goals

HORIZON-WIDERA-2022ERA-01-81

included identifying training offers, participation patterns, and gaps, but progress was limited by data quality, privacy concerns (GDPR), and lack of access to microdata. While the timeline was realistic and there were no major delays or deviations, the scope was reduced due to these constraints. The implementation only partially met its objectives; intersectional analysis was especially hindered. Barriers included lack of standardized data collection, legal/ethical concerns, and the absence of institutional data strategy. While basic data analysis skills were present within the team, systemic issues had limited impact. There was no active resistance, but privacy and internal practices restricted data sharing. The inhibiting factors are the lack of common institutional strategy to data collection practices and the lack of a central unit (such as the professional HR department) that could be responsible for keeping track of work-related trainings among the AGH faculty and staff. There is also the inherent ethical factor, namely how much personal information the institution really requires, and it is safe to share by individuals. Disaggregating the data in terms of gender is possible; it is also possible to have a basic view of position within an organization's structure and hierarchy. However, there are other dimensions that the university gathers on other occasions (such as the income per person in household), but the data isn't wrangled, because of the concerns regarding privacy and potential vulnerability. So, data that potentially can provide useful insight into the knowledge of who participates in training (and who does not), was missing. Another potentially important for intersectionality data was not gathered at all yet again inhibiting gaining knowledge of the Gender Equality and Intersectional dimension in the dynamics of work-related training. As mentioned earlier, the major barriers are the lack of a central unit that would collect relevant data and the fact that data is fragmentary and dispersed. Also, it is important to note that due to privacy concerns, sharing all the datasets with NEXUS was not possible. Also, the lack of data standards was visible. However, this was an issue that possibly will be changing, as the problem of data becomes widely pressing and movements towards standardizing data formats in science and beyond are gaining momentum. AGH was implementing training for data stewards. And although this concerns mainly research data, the awareness of proper data practices and data storage according to the FAIR principle is rising. Possibly this will also affect institutional practices regarding organizational data. Nonetheless, the ethical dimension of keeping track of sensitive information remains a challenge for gaining intersectional insights. This action, mainly because of the limitations mentioned above, probably won't result in improving inclusivity. However, combining the knowledge gained about organizational culture with the results of GEAM allows partners to identify, at least

partially, problems related to work-related training. In a way, this could be seen as a pilot's action, given the scarce and dispersed data. So, it speaks more about data collection practices than the possibly analysis of the data in terms of gender and intersectionality. The most hindering contextual factor is the lack of unified data collection practices within the organization. Although the action didn't result in immediate improvements in gender equality, it produced useful outputs (lists of training, categories, and data gaps) and shed light on institutional practices. Sustainability is expected through the ongoing work of the Equality Team, participation in equality networks, and AGH's broader policy efforts (e.g., HRS4R). The action serves as a pilot, revealing more about data handling at AGH than about training participation patterns.

Outcome foreseen for action 3: Further analysis of differences among training participants; Identifying potential ethical challenges in gathering information on training participants

Outcome achieved for action 3 Further analysis of differences among training participants; Identifying potential ethical challenges in gathering information on training participants.

Section redesign process

On 25-26 September 2024, Trio partner only underlined problems in collecting data for AGH and BZN, and in relation to indicators the main evaluation tool was the gathering of the data for enough time, that is minimum 2 years. During the workshop all partners presented what they had already achieved until September 2024 and their challenges. Trio agreed that we follow the initial design of the Action but implement it according to partners' contexts (availability of data etc). For all partners this is a new Action. The main monitoring indicator for the Action is the gathering of the data. AGH has some problems in gathering data.

In the Evaluation and Redesign Report, AGH has not mentioned any other evaluation and redesign workshop for this action.

Action 4 - Inclusive communication guidelines (Twin Trio Action)

Key Objectives: Development and dissemination of a document defining the principles of inclusive communication in the academic community.

Implementation Date: May 2025

Formative evaluation First Round

A focus group conducted on 29 November 2024, involved seven participants (four females, three males) who carried out desk research and developed initial draft guidelines for inclusive communication. The activity emphasized understanding the academic community's needs and analyzing existing recommendations for inclusive language. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative evaluation Second round

The second round of the formative evaluation activity in AGH was carried out through a Survey for recipients of the guidelines, participants were 9 (4 male, and 5 female). The survey was delivered on May 2025.

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

The action, led by the AGH GEP Team, Equality Advocate, and Faculty of Humanities, created an inclusive communication guide with institutional support but without formal top-level endorsement. Activities were completed as planned, with strong team coordination and student involvement (Increased student awareness of inclusive communication; Identification of knowledge gaps in available materials; Creation of a practical tool for education and internal communication).

The guide promotes intersectionality, covering multiple diversity dimensions, and has raised awareness among staff and students. No delays occurred.

Improvements:

- Developed a widely accessible tool to foster inclusive communication
- Raised awareness of linguistic sensitivity and inclusion
- Set foundations for institutional culture change

Key outcomes include a publicly available guide, increased sensitivity to inclusive language, and a foundation for cultural change. No major barriers impeded progress, though some explicit resistance, mainly from students, was addressed through education and advocacy.

Facilitating: team commitment, student engagement, external inspiration; Hindering: resistance to language-related equality topics, lack of coordination between some university units. Main barrier was the organizational resistance to language-focused research. Explicit resistance from some students, including online criticism and lack of awareness about the impact of language on social structures. The impact of the action is ensured with training sessions, webinars, and embedding the guide in AGH's internal communication systems. The outcome for gender equality was:

- A publicly available guide for inclusive academic communication
- Increased awareness among staff and students
- Resource for training and institutional discourse

The guide was successfully created and is awaiting full dissemination. Facilitating items were the dedicated team, students' participation, and inspiration from peer institutions. Hindering items were fragmented institutional cooperation, criticism of terminology, limited awareness of inclusive language relevance. Sustainability was planned via training and integration into internal systems. The project achieved its goals, despite minor institutional cooperation challenges.

Outcome foreseen for action 4: Increase in materials available for next iteration of guideline; Improved guideline

Outcome achieved for action 4: Increase in materials available for next iteration of guideline achieved partially; Improved guideline (in progress)

Section redesign process

During the Evaluation and Redesign Workshop held on 25-26 Settembre 2024 among trio partners, in occasion of the site visit in Cyprus, trio partners only underlined that once the guidelines will be finished, the feedback from selected members of the universities could be the feedback. No resistance. In the Evaluation and Redesign Report AGH has not mentioned any other evaluation and redesign workshop for this action.

Action 5 - Information campaign about intersectionality and equality (Partner Action)

Key Objectives: The goal was to prepare an information campaign on gender, inequality, and intersectionality. The campaign consisted of:

- social media activities (rolls, FB, Instagram)
- posters in physical space
- organization of the AGH + UJ Equality Day

Implementation Date: May 2025

Formative evaluation First Round

The formative evaluation activities for action 5 involved an open lab held on November 25, 2024. The session involved 14 participants, including members of the AGH academic community (students and employees), university alumni, external experts, and university recruiters. The activity focused on evaluating and summarizing promotional efforts related to the campaign and assessing the recognition of its initiatives to date. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative evaluation Second round

The second round of formative activity was carried out through a focus group with experts (3 female and 1 male) on 10 June 2025. The participants were not part of the NEXUS Team.

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

The action, led by the NEXUS and GEP teams at AGH University of Krakow, received strong top management support, including the Rector's honorary patronage of Equality Day. An inter-institutional team of staff, academics, and students were formed, with responsibilities distributed across event coordination, social media management, graphic design, and promotion. All planned activities were implemented on time, successfully raising awareness of gender equality and intersectionality, particularly in STEM fields. The campaign aligned with its objectives and benefited from cooperation with Jagiellonian University (UJ) and active student engagement. The team possessed all the necessary skills such as inclusive communication, graphic design, and event coordination. The expected outcomes are in the process of being achieved. However, explicit resistance, especially from some male STEM students, emerged via hostile online comments. This was addressed through educational strategies and internal alliances. The action strengthened institutional capacity around equality issues, enhanced inter-university collaboration, and laid the

groundwork for cultural change. Sustainability will be ensured through follow-up initiatives (e.g., another Equality Day), increased institutional visibility, and integration of outcomes into AGH's internal communications.

Outcome foreseen for action 5: Increased number of people aware of the intersectionality and equality

Outcome achieved for action 5: Increased number of people aware of the intersectionality and equality (still ongoing)

Section redesign process

The action didn't require any adjustment following the redesign process.

3.6 Bay Zoltán Nonprofit Ltd. for Applied Research (BZN)

The following table summarizes the monitoring, evaluation, and redesign processes of the pilot actions carried out by Bay Zoltán Nonprofit Ltd. for Applied Research within the NEXUS project.

Bay Zoltán Nonprofit Ltd. for Applied Research				
GEP'Areas	# Pilot Actions	#Formative Evaluation I round	#Formative Evaluation II round	#Actions adjusted following the Redesign Process
Work-life balance and organizational culture	1	1	1	1
Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment	2	2	2	2
Gender balance in leadership and decision making				
Data Collection				
Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	2	1	1	1
Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content	1	1	1	1
Total	5	5	5	5

The following describes their 5 pilot actions, the findings from the second round of formative evaluation activities, and the redesign process carried out.

Action 1 E-course on Gender Equality and Intersectionality (Twin Trio Action)

Key Objective:

- Create an e-course with a Gender Equality and Intersectionality approach.

HORIZON-WIDERA-2022ERA-01-81

- Increase/Improve equality and diversity in research content

Implementation Date: June 2025

Formative Evaluation First Round

The formative evaluation activities for the E-Course on Gender Equality and Intersectionality included a workshop conducted on 15 November 2024, attended by two female stakeholders: the project leader and the head of HR responsible for institutional surveys. This session focused on reviewing the e-course content to ensure the inclusion of intersectional perspectives on age, disability, sexual orientation, gender identity, and ethnicity. Discussions addressed cultural localization, intersectoral collaboration, and the technical feasibility of translating the e-course into Hungarian. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative Evaluation Second Round

BZN planned a workshop as part of the third trio visit, 6 female and one male joined it on 10 April 2025.

Overview of the Formative Evaluation Second Round

The action is being implemented by the NEXUS team at BZN, with AGH acting as the main responsible and coordinating partner within the trio. While the top management is informed about the action, there is no explicit commitment from their side. The other members of the trio support the process on demand and are responsible for implementation within their own institutions. No external actors or institutional mechanisms have been involved or established for the implementation. The short-term outcomes have been fully achieved: the revised text now better reflects local and intersectoral aspects (100%), an e-course has been implemented with registered users (100%), and awareness has been raised regarding the importance of considering gender, ethnicity, and age in research design and implementation (100%). The action aligns both its general and intersectional objectives, thanks to planned content updates during the course revision. There were no major deviations in design or implementation, except for the timeline adjustment (launching the final version in May-June 2025). The trio benefits from complementary skills, which support successful execution. However, challenges were encountered in engaging internal staff due to

ineffective initial communication. These were addressed by redesigning the message. Resistance was observed, stemming from a perceived lack of relevance to the course and poor communication strategies (e.g., a mass email with unappealing content). The course content strongly emphasizes gender equality and inclusivity and holds the potential to foster institutional change if widely adopted. There have been no unexpected outcomes. To ensure sustainability, BZN plans internal dissemination and will inform the National Agency for Research, Development and Innovation.

Outcome foreseen for action 1: Increased awareness of diversity and equality in research, with a better understanding of intersectional dimensions. Diversity and equality issues increasingly applied in new research projects

Outcome achieved for action 1 No visible effect of contextual factors regarding outcomes.

Section redesign process

The first Evaluation and Redesign Workshop was held on 25 and 26 September 2024 in Cyprus. During the workshop all the points, all files and topics that need to be improved (intersectionality, translation etc) were identified. During the workshop we discussed the action's monitoring indicators: feedback, review comments, number of recruited participants. No resistance from any of the partners. Feedback from the enrolled participants to follow the course is the main evaluation tool. Trios only reported that the timeline has been anticipated by the end of January 2025 (ripetizione del rigo sopra)

The second Evaluation and Redesign Workshop for this action, was held on 10 April 2025 as part of the trio visit. No change in the design. Suggestions and requested modifications from partners, submitted during March, are implemented. The final course is now available at the Open AGH platform, ready for use. No change in monitoring. Partners discussed the mechanics of reporting:

- Trio members keep track of disseminating the course (target groups and numbers, e.g. reach)
- AGH provides user statistics upon reporting (extracted from the online platform)

No resistance experienced. BZN focus on dissemination within the organisation, but informing the National Agency for Research, Development and Innovation about the availability of it. The action is progressing as anticipated, but the timeline has been expanded to cover also May-June 2025.

The third Evaluation and Redesign Report was held on 28 May 2025 among the trio partners. In the institutional workshop, participants identified two factors resulting in resistance: 1. the perceived lack of relevance of the course to the addresses and 2. the inefficient communication message and channel used to raise awareness about the course (mass e-mail with an unattractive text).

As a result, the text promoting the course internally was fully rewritten to address these concerns and to highlight the novelty, the added value and the relevance of the course to personal career paths. The course is now being promoted internally using the rewritten text. This is a joint action with limited space for repetition or adjustment outside the project scope, since the content is owned by another entity and technically it is hosted outside Bay Zoltán.

Action 2 - Implementation of the Gender Equality Auditing and Monitoring (GEAM) Tool (Twin Trio Action)

Key Objective:

- Gather data from the GEAM Survey
- Map the situation regarding gender equality in BZN
- Create an updated database for each Institution in the trio
- Be able to make comparisons, keep track of changes, improvements or pitfalls

Implementation Date: May 2025

Formative Evaluation First Round

Formative evaluation for the GEAM Tool action involved a training session on 29 – 31 May 2024, followed by a workshop on 15 November 2024, with two females' participants: the project leader and the head of HR. The workshop aimed to finalize the Hungarian translation of the questionnaire and tailor it to institutional needs. Participants also discussed strategies for promoting high response rates and integrating intersectional elements into the survey. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative Evaluation Second Round

Partner planned a workshop as part of the third trio visit; there were 7 participants (6 female and 1 male) on 10 April 2025. The activity was conducted by Adam Molnar.

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

The action was implemented by the NEXUS project team at BZN, with support from the international department (responsible for NEXUS Project) and HR departments, and with the backing of top management. External collaboration was ensured through FUOC (Open University of Catalonia), which provided expertise in survey management and data analysis. Statistical skills were needed and missing for analyzing the results of the action. This was provided externally by the survey managing partner FUOC (Open University of Catalonia). Key activities such as customizing and launching the GEAM survey with intersectional content were completed as planned, though the response rate was lower than expected (under 30% vs. the targeted 50%).

No institutional structures were newly established, and no deviations or delays occurred. While short-term impacts on gender equality and inclusivity were limited due to the low response rate, the results will inform the next GEP update in 2026. No change in the timeline. All trio partners have already implemented the GEAM survey in their own institutions. The intersectional content of the GEAM survey was fully used in the BZN implementation. The action is aligned with its objectives and will be sustained through regular repetition of the GEAM survey every four years. A notable unplanned outcome was the translation of the survey into Hungarian, now available for open access. The inhibiting factor is the response rate, which was lower than expected. A barrier was the low response rate: less than 30% as opposed to the foreseen 50%. In connection with the GEAM, both the lack of interest and the lack of trust were cited by workshop participants as probable resistances preventing a higher response rate. The sensitivity of the topic and the abstractness of the areas covered by the GEAM were also cited as obstacles. The low interest in filling in the survey contributed to a lower response rate than planned. The results are not visible in the short term: The expectation is that the survey results will be used for the next update of the institutional GEP in the second half of 2026, to inform updated/new actions. Unplanned outcome: the GEAM survey text had to be translated to Hungarian first as the survey was launched in Hungarian and the translation did not exist yet. The translated survey questions were handed over to the survey managing partner to be

available with open access for any further use. Outcomes reached, as the survey was intended in BZN as a pilot (first instance of implementing it within the institution).

Outcome foreseen for action 2: Increased awareness on the thematic areas of Inclusive GEP; Data available to address institutional gaps and problem spots.

Outcome achieved for action 2: Increased awareness on the thematic areas of Inclusive GEP; Data available to address institutional gaps and problem spots.

Section redesign process

The redesign has been done many times. Firstly, the 25 and 26 of September 2024 as part of the second Trio Visit. There was a substantial discussion on the GEAM Tool during the workshop. We all agreed on the sections to use, the common and the individual sections, and that the same action will be implemented in different partners' contexts. The Action is new to BZN. The monitoring indicators of the GEAM tool helped us to evaluate the progress of the action and not to have any delays. Creation of accounts, participation in trainings, creation of surveys on GEAM website, and modification of the surveys are some indicators for monitoring and evaluation of the Action before the implementation of the tool. BZN is redesigning some of the socioeconomic questions (including income level) and work position questions (on scientific area, job and seniority) to avoid resistance in answering and to get more usable data. By now the final evaluation tool for the effectiveness of the action is the number of participants to complete the questionnaire. In BZN, the target was to get a 50% response rate.

The second Evaluation and Redesign report was held on 15 November 2024 among the BZN NEXUS Team and the HR Department. The main discussion point involved tailoring action to institutional reality. The full questionnaire content was discussed, and the template modified when needed – altogether modifications or omissions affect less than 10% of the original questions. The timeline was set and the steps reviewed, all questions from the GEAM tool were intended to be used in the questionnaire. However, following a review by the institution's top management, it was decided that a redesign was necessary. As a result, a few questions from the tool were omitted and several questions for demography were redesigned, with the final selection adjusted to the research centre's specific needs and priorities follow for successfully completing the action, without much change to the overall timeline.

The third Evaluation and Reporting Workshop was held on 10 April 2025 among the trio partners. It was decided to not make change because All trio partners have already implemented the GEAM survey in their own institutions. BZN only reported a low response rate that affecting the impact of the action. GEAM survey will be periodically repeated (every 4 years) by each institution in the trio. No adjustments needed, the action is progressing as anticipated.

In the redesign workshop on 28 May 2025, held between the NEXUS Team and the head of HR Department, BZN reported both the lack of interest, and the lack of trust were cited by workshop participants as probable resistances preventing a higher response rate. The sensitivity of the topic and the abstractness of the areas covered by the GEAM were also cited as obstacles. The GEAM survey had a low response rate which prevents the results from being used and interpreted as representative of the staff's views or opinion. Moreover, cross-analysis of answers to individual questions by demographic variables (gender, age, time in institution etc.) were not possible due to the low samples. This limits the impact and to make the action sustainable, even taking the intention to repeat the survey as granted, work needs to be done to ensure a higher response rate for the next round of the survey.

Action 3 - Fostering participation in work-related training through data collection with a Gender Equality and Intersectional perspective (Twin Trio action)

Key Objectives: Data collection and analysis to map the situation and establish the short-term trends of the participation of staff in professional training by gender and other inequality areas.

Implementation date: May 2025

Formative Evaluation First Round

This action aims to address disparities in participation in professional training sessions through a Gender Equality and Intersectional perspective. Preparatory activities for formative evaluation included a workshop held on 15 November 2024, with the project leader and the head of HR. Discussions focused on defining variables for data collection and identifying Trends in training participation from 2022 to 2024. Participants also reviewed the institutional training plan to align it

with inclusive objectives, identifying potential gaps due to reduced training sessions in 2024 resulting from budget constraints. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative Evaluation Second Round Results

The formative was done on 1 April 2025, as part of the third trio visit with a workshop in which joined 6 female and 1 male participants of the NEXUS teams partners.

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

The action was jointly overseen by the HR and International departments at BZN, with no external stakeholders involved. Initially aimed at analyzing diversity in training participation, the action was reoriented after a mid-term evaluation due to the lack of available institutional data. The revised focus shifted to producing internal recommendations for future data collection, which include gender and intersectional perspectives. While short-term goals such as raising awareness were fully achieved, medium-term goals like modifying training plans to improve inclusivity have not yet been realized. The outcomes will be visible and measurable over a longer period, extending beyond the project lifetime, as visible in the table above. There were no delays, deviations, or resistance during implementation, though the absence of training data significantly had a limited impact. The action outcomes were expected to contribute to institutional change in the long term, especially if the recommendations are integrated into future training and policy planning. Changes in the action occurred during implementation, due to the limited amount of training data available at BZN. The action, especially its implementation in BZN, was re-designed after the first round of evaluation, focusing on recommendations for future data collection. This was discussed and confirmed by the trio partners in the third trio visit in Budapest in April 2025, as follows:

- The different trio partners have different data that were available to be analyzed in their implementation of the action.
- Therefore, the three partners agreed on a common approach to producing the results of this action:
 - Identify the results (whether full or partial) and the challenges with existing data
 - Produce detailed recommendations for internal use

- Produce a joint short summary highlighting in brief the most prominent challenges and the proposed solutions (up to 3-4 points per partner)

An inhibiting factor was the scarcity of institutional data that was needed for the originally planned action but not available at BZN. This necessitated a redesign of the output action. A major barrier was the lack of institutional data collected on previous annual training plan implementations. No resistance encountered. On the longer term, if the recommendations will be considered, the action has the potential to contribute to institutional change. However, now management did not express an opinion about the action, so their endorsement or contrary opinion is not available yet. Outcome was partly achieved, but the focus of the outcomes was shifted from the analysis of available data to the recommendations for collecting future data, to adjust to the realities of BZN.

Outcome foreseen for action 3: increased awareness of the importance of diversity and inclusion in the various training; Plan for improving diversity in the participation in trainings

Outcome achieved for action 3: increased awareness on the importance of diversity and inclusion in the various training; Plan for improving diversity in the participation in trainings achieved partially.

Section redesign process

The first workshop took place the end 25-26 September 2024, during the workshop all partners presented what they had already achieved until September 2024 and their challenges. They all agreed in following the initial design of the action but implementing it according to partners' contexts (availability of data etc). The main monitoring indicator for the action is the gathering of data. BZN didn't foresee any resistance but data for the last year (2024) may be very limited because non-mandatory training was cancelled for the year (despite advance planning) due to financial difficulties. In BZN, data from the past 3 years have been analyzed.

In the Evaluation and Redesign workshop held on 10/04/2025, trio partners had different data available to be analysed in their implementation of the action, and they agreed on a common approach to produce the results of this action:

- Identify the results (whether full or partial) and the challenges with existing data
- Produce detailed recommendations for internal use

- Produce a joint short summary highlighting in brief the most prominent challenges and the proposed solutions (up to 3-4 points per partner)

No change in monitoring. No resistance experienced. BZN, FredU and AGH recognized the recommendations for internal use in each institution as an important output of the action and meant to contribute to the sustainability of the action. Adjustments made by the partners include a shared approach to reporting the outcomes of the action, as detailed above.

Action 4 - Inclusive communication guidelines (Twin Trio Action)

Key Objective:

- Design guidelines to make communication within and outside the university fairer and more inclusive
- Enhance competences: knowledge, skills and attitudes
- Provide the community with a practical guidance on communication patterns in English for inclusive language
- Set standards for internal and external communication

Share lessons learned and support mutual learning among the Trio.

Implementation Date: June 2025

Formative Evaluation First Round

The first round of evaluation for the Inclusive Communication Guidelines action included a workshop on 15 November 2024, with two female participants: the project leader and the head of HR. The session focused on drafting guidelines and incorporating feedback from Trio partners. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative Evaluation Second Round Results

The formative was done on 10 April 2025 during the third trio meeting, with 7 participants (6 female, 1 male).

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

The action was led by BZN's HR Department with support from the International Department, without the involvement of external actors. It focused on developing Inclusive Communication Guidelines as a joint effort with trio partners. The content of the Guidelines has been modified before the third trio meeting: the content has been expanded, both in the existing sections and by adding two new sections. Trio members agreed that the final English guidelines will be a standalone document, the result of the joint action, even though each institution will decide individually if and how to use it, alongside a parallel version in the national language. While the final document is complete and incorporates intersectoral and gender-sensitive content, it has not yet been officially adopted or broadly shared within BZN. Short-term objectives such as raising awareness among partners were fully met, while medium-term goals like adoption by management and institutional usage are only partially achieved. Significant theoretical knowledge of gender, linguistics and intersectionality as well as knowledge of promoting gender equality in language use were required. Most of this knowledge could be provided by the trio partners so once again the advantage of working as a trio (as opposed to BZN alone) was demonstrated through this collaboration.

No major deviations occurred, though the content was expanded to better reflect institutional relevance. Political sensitivity surrounding gender equality in Hungary is a potential barrier to full implementation. No resistance experienced yet; however, the trio has taken steps to ensure that the Guidelines were as relevant for the institutions as possible:

- Expand the Introduction section, explaining the relevance of the Guidelines
- Reorder the sections, based on perceived relevance (from most relevant to the most niche topic)
- Restructure each section, organizing the content and simplifying it along two main points: How to communicate and how not to communicate
- Revise the examples and change those less relevant to more relevant, using European examples where applicable

For BZN, the action is a pilot since no similar guidelines in English have yet been introduced in the organization. It is an important first step to try to introduce recommendations in an area that has not been targeted before. BZN is not planning to develop or use a Hungarian version but may need to produce an altered variant of the shared English version (still in English) based on the decision and

approval of the management. Participants in the institutional formative evaluation saw potential for sustainability despite the identified risks of resistance. In fact, the additional action, to be implemented after the end of the NEXUS project, was designed as a follow-up to this action. Hindering factor: the contested status of gender equality discourse in the public sphere. Despite no resistance so far, the action is seen as a pilot and an important first step for institutional change, with long-term sustainability expected through a planned follow-up action and possible adaptation of the English version of the guidelines.

Outcome foreseen for action 4: Increased awareness among the trio-partners; Increased awareness among the top management in BZN; Increased awareness on the importance of Inclusive Communication and incorporation in the internal regulations of BZN

Outcome achieved for action 4: Increased awareness among the trio-partners; Increased awareness among the top management in BZN (achieved partially); Increased awareness on the importance of Inclusive Communication and incorporation in the internal regulations of BZN (achieved partially).

Section redesign process

The partner did different workshops; the first one took place on the 25-26 September 2024 and the second in April 2025. Trio members agreed that the final English guidelines will be a standalone document, the result of the joint action, even though each institution will decide individually if and how to use it, alongside a parallel version in the national language. It will not be fully public (i.e. not to be placed in an open repository), but institutions may decide to promote it at different levels. Accordingly, a Creative Commons license has been added, but the document is not foreseen to be shared widely. BZN was not planning to develop or use a Hungarian version but maybe to produce an altered variant of the shared English version (still in English) based on the decision and approval of the management.

The initial document included the categories of Gender, LGBT+ Community, Races and Ethnicities, Disability, Neurodivergence and Mental Health, and Religion and Worldview. To enhance the document's intersectionality and comprehensiveness, it was redesigned to include two additional categories: Appearance and Age. An extensive introduction was also added as part of the

redesign. Once the guidelines are finished, an evaluation indicator could be feedback from selected members of the universities.

For BZN, the action is a pilot since no similar guidelines in English have yet been introduced in the organization. It is an important first step to try to introduce recommendations in an area that has not been targeted before.

Action 5 - Eliminating prejudices, improving corporate culture - everyone is important! (Partner Action)

Key Objective: The objective is to implement an attitude formation program via equal opportunity training as lead activity and then link to an already running institutional initiative (i.e. the Undercover webinar series).

Implementation date: in progress

Formative Evaluation First Round

The formative evaluation activities for action 5 involved a workshop held on 15 November 2024 with the participation of the project leader and the head of the HR Department, who is responsible for institutional surveys. The action is in its preparatory stage and thus, no direct implementation of training or evaluation has occurred yet. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative Evaluation Second Round

On 28 May 2025, the partner planned an internal formative evaluation workshop. 3 participants joined (2 female and 1 male) components of the NEXUS Team and the HR Department.

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

The action, initially managed by the NEXUS project team, faced major delays and had to be redesigned due to a lack of financial support from top management. Originally planned as a training session, it was restructured into a science café event focusing on inclusivity in research settings scheduled for August 2025. The follow-up activities (e.g., Undercover information sessions) will be implemented later in 2025, beyond the NEXUS project's lifetime. Despite changes in format and

timeline, the original objectives, including intersectional aims, have been retained. No resistance has been encountered so far, and external collaboration with Hungarian research organizations was expected to enhance the action's reach and effectiveness. Intersectional objectives are still valid. As the new version has not yet been implemented, no outcomes are currently visible, and sustainability planning has not yet been addressed. The main barrier has been financial constraints, which were partially overcome through redesign. The sustainability aspect has not been discussed due to the need to focus on more imminent aspects of the action implementation. The outcome is not achieved as the action is still to be implemented.

Outcome foreseen for action 5: Increased awareness and improved work culture regarding diversity and equality within the organization, with a better understanding of intersectional dimensions; Increased awareness of personality differences from the perspective of diversity; Overall job satisfaction improved by at least 5% over 2 years

Outcome achieved for action 5: no outcome achieved as the action has still been implemented

Section redesign process

The redesign workshop took place on 28 May 2025; the action has been redesigned due to financial and organisational difficulties impeding the implementation as it was foreseen in the design phase. The redesigned action took place as a science café event, instead of a training, in collaboration with the Researchers' Night project focusing on inclusivity in a research environment. Participants were foreseen to attend in person both from within Bay Zoltan and from partner research organisations. Preparation for the redesigned event began in June 2025, shortly after the redesign workshop and the event itself took place in August 2025. The second part of the action, i.e. follow-up with the Undercover information sessions, will be implemented as originally intended, but beyond the lifetime of the NEXUS project (most probably in the 4th quarter of 2025). A potential resistance identified was the lack of interest in the topic, mitigated by broadening the scope to include wider aspects of the organisational culture and career progression in research performing organisations.

3.7 University of Niš (UN)

The following table summarizes the monitoring, evaluation, and redesign process of the pilot actions carried out by the University of Niš within the NEXUS project.

University of Niš				
GEP'Areas	# Pilot Actions	#Formative Evaluation I round	#Formative Evaluation II round	#Actions adjusted following the Redesign Process
Work-life balance and organizational culture	2	2	2	2
Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment	1	1	1	1
Gender balance in leadership and decision making				
Data Collection				
Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	1	1	1	1
Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content	1	1	1	1
Total	5	5	5	5

The following describes their 5 pilot actions, the findings from the second round of formative evaluation activities, and the redesign process carried out.

Action 1 - Influence of biases in decision-making (Twin Trio Action)

This action was co-designed by the Trio. It aimed to contribute to more transparent and objective recruitment, reducing discrimination and biases. The target audience was staff members involved in the employment process. The action should be implemented by the end of 2024, so that the impact can be monitored. The design process involved a survey based on which the training course would be designed. This action involved organizing training for people who can make decisions about employment at the faculty. The goal of the action was to introduce decision-makers, through training, to unconscious biases, so that they can recognize and avoid them when making decisions about employment. The training was attended by 19 people from the faculty management, heads of departments and professional services, and members of the NEXUS team.

The first step in the activity was the development and implementation of a survey on unconscious biases, which served to create an agenda for a workshop where participants would be trained on biases in general and biases in employment. The list of participants was created so that it would include all those who can decide about employment at the faculty.

Key Objective: Tackling biases in recruitment

Implementation Date: April 2025

Outcome foreseen for Action 1: reducing unconscious bias in recruitment at the faculty; raising awareness of unconscious bias among 15 potential decision-makers

Outcome achieved for Action 1: raising awareness of unconscious bias among 15 potential decision-makers; reducing bias in recruitment decisions, has been evaluated over time as new hiring processes take place

Formative evaluation First Round

Formative evaluation activities for action 1 included a pre-training questionnaire completed by 21 participants and a workshop conducted on 29 November 2024, with 16 participants (43% male, 57% female). Participants included faculty management, department heads, and members of the NEXUS team. The pre-training survey evaluated participants' baseline knowledge of cognitive biases, while the workshop addressed the recognition and mitigation of biases in recruitment decisions. The

workshop was facilitated by an expert from the National Employment Agency. The results are available on [Deliverable 3.2 Formative Evaluation Mid-Term Results](#).

Formative evaluation second round

The formative evaluation activity second round was carried out through an ex-post- survey delivered after the workshop training. The ex-post-training survey was designed by Marko Mancic from the NEXUS team. The project team established collaboration with the National Office for employment, which helped with the Cognitive Bias knowledge and skills which lacked at the faculty. Participants included the management of the faculty, heads of departments, heads of professional services and members of the NEXUS team: attendance 16 employees M=7 (43%), F=9 (57%).

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

The action was successfully implemented with strong support from the Dean's office and faculty management. A management representative was actively involved in the workshops, demonstrating a clear commitment from leadership to the project's goals. Gordana Stefanovic led the implementation, supported by team members for logistical tasks. An external expert from the National Employment Service was engaged in designing and delivering for the workshop and for the post-survey. All planned activities were carried out on time and according to schedule, with no deviations. The short-term goal of raising awareness of unconscious bias among 15 potential decision-makers was surpassed, with 16 participants: considering that all invited employees attended the workshop and actively participated in it. The planned short-term outcomes had been achieved. The medium-term goal, reducing bias in recruitment decisions, has been evaluated over time as new hiring processes take place. Despite a temporary student blockade that caused a minor delay in survey preparation, the team managed to achieve its objectives. No major barriers or resistance were encountered during implementation. The action significantly improved awareness of gender equality and cognitive bias within the institution. Although recent hiring has been paused due to ongoing blockades, the project team plans to repeat the workshop for staff who have not yet participated. Discussions with the trainer and faculty of leadership about future sessions are already in progress.

The action met its objectives and intersectional goals. There is no deviation from the planned activities. No significant changes were made. No resistance or barriers were encountered. No

unexpected outcomes. The level of awareness was raised and the knowledge on GE and cognitive bias in recruitment was raised at the institution. There was a commitment from management to further support such actions. The informal feedback of the employees which participated in the events organized by NEXUS was very positive. The workshop can be repeated for employees who have not been involved so far. We have already discussed this with the trainer and the faculty management. The workshop included department heads and management. A facilitating factor was the institutional support that gave the opportunity to hire an external trainer and to have all foreseen participants in the workshop. The topic was unexpectedly very interesting to everyone. Especially since many were not even aware that they had unconscious prejudices, which were illuminated by the training. The disruptive factors were the highlights of the topic of prejudice in general as well as prejudice in employment.

Section redesign process

In the redesign of the 23 September 2024, the UN worked on this action: timeframe, outputs, impact didn't change but instead decided to differ significantly in terms of audience, approach, implementation, and clarity of expected results. Initially, the intervention targeted recruiters directly involved in screening and evaluation processes, using a collaborative and participatory approach that included the co-development of a survey, shared content design among partners, and a clear timeline from June 2024 to January 2025. The outputs and outcomes were clearly defined, aiming to train at least 16 recruiters per university and to promote more transparency and objectivity in recruitment processes. In contrast, the re-design shifted the focus to higher-level administrative and management staff (such as deans' offices, legal secretaries, and heads of departments), delegated the design and delivery of the course to an external expert from the National Office for Employment. No resistance was encountered. The output indicators were a survey established by the TRIO, workshop agenda, list of participants, workshop summary report, survey report after the workshop. The indicators were met. The exit survey was not filled with all the participants, just 9 of them.

Indeed, to follow what has been reported in the above, the second workshop of the GEP group (15 November 2024) UN decided to invite the trainer from the National Employment Service to a meeting to create the course topics. They agreed that the first part should be an introduction to prejudice and biases, and that the second part should present biases in employment. It is also suggested that the trainer should present more practical examples and encourage discussion. Partners also proposed

inviting 16 employees from all sectors that influence hiring decisions: Faculty management, heads of departments, service managers, and the entire legal service. There were no resistances. The collaboration with the National Employment Service provided us with good insights.

The last Redesign workshop was held in May 2025 by the NEXUS team and experts in the field of action. It would be good if the workshop on uncooperative biases were repeated several more times in the future

Action 2 - Parenting group (Twin Trio Action)

The aim of the action is to build on the work-life balance by improving the parenting organization's culture. To achieve this, it is envisaged that a parent information and experience exchange group will be formed. To achieve this, it is necessary to detect and engage volunteers – community builders, who will build the parenting community and organize future events, with respect to the interest and motivation among parents at the institution. The first meeting was organized for the 2nd of December 2024, when two community builders were identified.

Key Objective: Identify and engage 2 community builders

Implementation Date: December 2024

Formative evaluation First Round

Formative evaluation activities for the Parenting Resource Group action involved a meeting on December 2, 2024, with 14 participants, including teaching, research, and administrative staff. The meeting aimed to identify community builders to lead the parenting group and facilitate future activities. Two community builders, Sasa Pavlovic and Dusan Petkovic, were selected to organize subsequent meetings and engage with Parents. The results are available on [Deliverable 3.2 Formative Evaluation Mid-Term Results](#)

Formative evaluation Second Round

The second round of the Formative Evaluation Activity was carried out in December 2024 through the e-mail confirmation of community builders and a meeting with Employees of the University of Nis, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering which are parents (or soon to be parents).

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

There was no commitment from Management. The Union of employees of the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering has helped. The Head of the Union was one of the community builders. Marko Mancic was responsible for this action. The Union of employees of the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering has helped. They communicated with the parents by e-mail, since they had information about who the parents are among the employees. No institutional body involved. Two community builders were identified at the first meeting in December 2024, Dusan Petkovic and Sasa Pavlovic, which confirmed by e-mail that they accepted this role and that they will be responsible for future actions. Action was successfully implemented on time and as planned, with strong support from the Faculty's Employees Union, which played a key role in reaching employee parents and identifying two committed community builders. A parenting group meeting was held, where participants discussed their needs and agreed to stay in touch via a Viber group. Topics of interest included workshops on child-related issues (like cybersecurity), extracurricular activities, and entertainment. The group was inclusive across gender and staff roles, aligning with intersectional goals. No major barriers or resistance were encountered, and the action is considered sustainable thanks to ongoing support from the Union and the identified community leaders. While no institutional change has occurred yet, the initiative has laid the groundwork for improving work-life balance. This action may lead to improved work and life balance, but not during the project.

Outcome foreseen for Action 2: identified the needs of Parent society, increased availability of knowledge and problem solutions for parents

Outcome achieved for Action 2: identify the needs of Parent society, increased availability of knowledge and problem solutions for parents

Section redesign process

The first redesign of this action has been conducted on 23 September 2024 in Nicosia at Trio level. In the original design (D2.2), scheduled from July to December 2024, the initiative targeted employee parents to establish a Parenting Resource Group. Key outputs included a single informational event attended by 15 participants, recruitment of two community builders, and ongoing engagement from seven regular members through bi-monthly meetings. The primary outcome was at least 50% participant interest and the identification of one improvement area via questionnaires. The re-design,

implemented from September 2024 to February 2025, expanded the scope to include both staff and students under a Work–Life Balance Support Group. Although retaining most core objectives, such as one informational event with ≥ 15 attendees, two community builders, and $\geq 50\%$ engagement, the re-design adjusted meeting frequency to one session every two months and setting a minimum of five regular participants. Overall, the re-design widened the audience while maintaining impact, but shifted to less frequent, more targeted meetings. Another redesigns workshop was held on 15 November 2024 by the NEXUS Team and experts in the field of action. The UN decided to engage union representatives and agreed to create 2 parent groups, one for parents with children under 12 years old, and the other for parents with children over 12 years old. There were no resistances. The last redesign workshop was held on 8 May 2025 by the NEXUS Team and experts in the field of action. The UN NEXUS team decided to include the action in the gender equality plan. Thematic workshops should be included in the plan at least 2 times a year. The goal was achieved.

Action 3 - Gender Equality and Intersectional dimension in research (Twin Trio Action)

The aim of the action is to improve the skills of the researchers, so that the gender equality and intersectional dimensions would be embedded in the research projects from the proposal preparation phase thus affecting the implementation and reporting phase. For this purpose, a practical toolkit for researchers has been prepared. The target groups were teaching and research staff. The expected delivery date was the end of 2024, for the first draft of the document. The interviews with PIs were performed to help define the contents of the Guidelines. The contents were defined as part of the Trio activities, and tasks were distributed among Trio partners.

Key Objective: A gender and intersectional approach in the research fields

Implementation Date: April 2025

Section Formative evaluation First Round

Formative evaluation activities for the Gender Equality and Intersectional Dimension in Research Action included interviews with three principal investigators (PIs) to gather input on integrating gender and intersectionality in research projects. A focus group meeting with the Trio partners (IIT, UM, and UN) was also conducted to finalize the structure and content of the guidelines. These

activities informed the development of a draft document, which is on track to be completed by the end of January 2025. The results are available on [Deliverable 3.2 Formative Evaluation Mid-Term Results](#).

Section Formative evaluation Second round

NEXUS group planned a focus group moment with research and academic staff on 11 April 2025. Participants invited were the entire university population from young researchers and PhD students to the Management. People positively reacted to the gender guidelines underlined its value in terms of usability and efficiency.

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

The action focused on promoting gender equality and intersectionality in research guidelines, which were developed with Trio partners and supported by faculty management, who approved their publication on the faculty website. Marko Mancic coordinated the action, with other NEXUS members assisting. Although there was a slight delay in promotion—carried out in April 2025, the guidelines were developed together with the Trio Partners and completed as planned. Yes, it was a slight delay with the guidelines, and their promotion was conducted in April, which was slightly delayed. The guidelines were, however, finished according to plan. The promotion and training were done in April 2025. No institutional body involved. The guidelines included content on gender equality and intersectionality, aimed at improving research and project planning, particularly national and EU proposals. There were no major barriers or resistance, and the implementation aligned with the original objectives. The Guidelines are available online on the website of the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering in Nic as a help tool, which will lead to increased knowledge regarding Gender Equality and intersectionality for research planning in general but also for the national and EU project proposals. They are free to use and are available in the future. The employees were informed about this fact, and interested researchers could get more information on how to benefit from the guidelines for the promotional event. The online availability of the guidelines ensures their continued use, and interested staff were informed during a dedicated promotional event. The key enabling factor was the interest of employees in using the guidelines, and all expected outcomes were fully achieved, contributing to long-term awareness and capacity-building in inclusive research

practices. The outcomes were achieved. The interest of employees in using the guidelines facilitated the implementation.

Outcome foreseen for Action 3: Draft guide document with examples; increased knowledge and skills for preparation of EU projects in terms of Gender Equality.

Outcome achieved for Action 3: Draft guide document with examples; increased knowledge and skills for preparation of EU projects in terms of Gender Equality.

Section redesign process

The first redesign process was done on 23 September 2024 in Nicosia with the Trio. For the UN, the action was not redesigned. It went according to plan. The Trio agreed that each of the partners would have their own Gender Equality and intersectionality in research guidelines, with some parts tailored based on the research areas relevant for each institution. The output indicators were the following: meeting summary document (based on feedback from the IP researchers from the institutions), Existing Gender Equality and intersectionality guidelines available on the institutional SharePoint, Draft guidelines document designed, revised draft guidelines document, 1 web portal document publication. The UN published their Gender Equality and intersectionality in research guidelines approximately 1 month after the other partners; apart from this, there were no challenges. On 8 May 2025 at organizationa level, UN partner did the forth redesign workshop, they decided that the manual that was created could be distributed every year to new researchers. This could be done through the Doctoral Studies Service. The workshop of redesign was held on 15 May 2025 by the NEXUS Team of Trio Partner. Based on the feedback from the community, the UN NEXUS team was motivated to pursue further funding opportunities, form partnerships and apply for grants to further improve the working and studying environment in terms of Gender Equality and intersectionality. The management of the faculty has expressed intentions to support this formally, but not financially. The actions performed during NEXUS have helped UN better understand and define the current status in terms of Gender Equality and intersectionality, and seth goals and pathways for further improvements. In addition, at the meeting a questionnaire was created to collect researchers feedback to understand their needs during the writing of projects related to Gender Equality and intersectionality in research.

Action 4 - Informing employees and students about the existence of the Regulation on Prevention and Protection from Sexual Harassment at FMEUNI (RonPPfromSH) – (Partner Action)

This action aimed to raise awareness about regulations and prevention measures against gender-based violence. Additionally, creating a safer work environment and enhancing the effectiveness of all employees and students is one of the objectives. This was achieved through regular circular notifications that had already been sent to all students and employees. For the 210 new students, the same notification was provided in written form during the distribution of their student IDs. Furthermore, all senior students and employees have been regularly reminded about the prohibition of sexual harassment and the existence of an appropriate policy. The presence of a designated contact person and the form of communication with him/her was publicly announced and easily accessible on the faculty's website. The number of visits to this form and the active "Equality" submenu on the faculty's website was monitored through the site's analytics.

Key Objective: Wellbeing in the workplace and study environment

Implementation Date: April 2025

Formative evaluation First Round

Formative evaluation activities for action 4 included distributing printed and digital materials about the Regulation on Prevention and Protection from Sexual Harassment (RonPPfromSH) and updating the faculty website with a dedicated section on the policy. A total of 883 students and 155 employees received email notifications, and new students received printed copies during orientation. The results are available on [Deliverable 3.2 Formative Evaluation Mid-Term Results](#)

Formative evaluation Second round

The second round of formative activity was carried out through an ex-post survey delivered to university staff and students. The survey was prepared during the workshop Gender- Based Violence (21 participants 10M/11F) on 14 April 2025, and survey distribution happened via MS Teams invitation on 15 May 2025 (approx. 100 Staff members with 33% F).

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

The implementation of the 4th action was led by the HR officer, NEXUS representatives, and a web administrator, with strong commitment from the Dean. While no external actors were involved, an internal working group coordinated the development of a survey on awareness of sexual harassment policies (RonPPfromSH), supported by prior training and legal guidance. A Gender-Based Violence (GBV) workshop, delayed slightly due to a student blockade, helped test and refine survey content. Despite limited staff participation (12.7%) and no student involvement due to ongoing protests, early results indicate increased awareness of institutional regulations—especially among women and early-career staff. There were some deviations from the planned activities. During the GBV workshop the preparation of the survey materials was reviewed. There was a slight delay in holding the Gender-Based Violence workshop because the faculty was blocked by students, and only formal activities were taking place. The implementation of the action aligns well with its objectives. The action met its gender equality and intersectional objectives by engaging a demographically diverse group and highlighting the need for continued awareness raising. The implementation has changed slightly over time due to the current student blockade. The members of the UN NEXUS representatives were already trained to prepare the workshop, discuss the needs, and analyze the survey content. All the knowledge gained during the NEXUS workshops was necessary. The faculty secretary ensured legal compliance and GDPR adherence, while an external psychologist reviewed and adjusted the questions from sociological and psychological perspectives. No major barriers occurred. There have been no unexpected or unplanned outcomes. These initiatives are crucial for promoting gender equality and inclusivity, contributing to institutional change. Though hindered by logistical challenges, the action laid the foundation for sustained impact, with plans to repeat the survey annually and integrate GBV awareness into institutional culture. The survey will be regularly distributed every May to all new employees and students, who have already been informed about the policy (RonPPfromSH) through a circular message. Facilitating Factors were the institutional support, the existence of formal regulations on the prevention and protection from sexual harassment provided a structural foundation for the action; the relevance of the topic, particularly for women and early-career academic staff (e.g., PhD students); the positive reception of workshops because participants who attended workshops rated them highly (average score 4.83/5), indicating that well-designed educational activities can effectively raise awareness and engagement. Hindering Factors were the faculty blockade that significantly limited the reach and visibility of the

HORIZON-WIDERA-2022ERA-01-81

action, reducing opportunities for broader participation; the low response rate (only 12.7% of the total employee population responded to the survey); the limited student involvement due to the blockade, with the exclusion of a key stakeholder group from the evaluation process.

Despite these challenges, the action managed to initiate a small but meaningful shift in awareness and engagement, suggesting that with more stable conditions and continued effort, broader and deeper impact will be achievable.

Outcome foreseen for Action 4: Better informed community on Sexual Harassment and transparency of measures on its prevention

Outcome achieved for Action 4: Despite the challenging circumstances, namely, the ongoing blockade of teaching and examination activities at the faculty, the action still managed to achieve some of its intended outcomes.

Section redesign process

The first workshop was held on 12 September 2024 with the faculty management was planned how to raise the visibility of the Regulations on the Prevention and Protection from Sexual Harassment of Students and Faculty Employees. Partner agreed in:

- Sending information via faculty e-mail: all employees and all students once a year
- Distributing information in paper form to all newly enrolled students every October during the index award ceremony.

The number of e-mails sent to both employees and students was 400, and the number of flyers was 200. In the last workshop (8 May 2025), UN partner reported that on the Equality website, there is a possibility to report violence anonymously. They also are aware that workshops dealing with sexual and other forms of violence must be repeated.

Action 5 - Better environment for Roma students at the faculty (Partner Action)

The main goal of this action was to increase the number of Roma students at the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering. This action included constant contacts with high school principals to obtain data on the number of Roma students. Meetings with students graduating from high school were planned. Students of the Roma population are admitted to the faculty according to affirmative

measures which is an advantage that the Roma population could use in the education process. Also, constant contact is maintained with Roma associations. Their support was expected to increase the number of Roma students interested in further education at the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering. The main result of the activity was publication of the document in the Romani language on the faculty's website. Students of the Roma population also participate in this process of translation into the Romani language. There were nine Roma students at the faculty of mechanical engineering.

Objective: Increased number of Roma students at the faculty

Implementation Date: June 2025

Formative evaluation First Round

Formative evaluation activities for this action included visits to high schools, meetings with principals and educators, and collaboration with Roma associations. A key achievement was the creation of a webpage in the Romani language to provide information and resources for prospective students. The results are available on [Deliverable 3.2 Formative Evaluation Mid-Term Results](#)

Formative evaluation Second Round

The second round of formative evaluation activity was carried out through an interview with head of student affairs department to check on Roma student studies status and changes.

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

The implementation of Action actively involved the NEXUS project staff at the University of Niš, the webmaster, and Jelena Janevski, with strong support from the top management. The action promoted cooperation with Roma associations and NGOs, aiming to increase inclusivity and improve access to higher education for the Roma population. Institutional contacts were established, official communications prepared, and technical arrangements made for a participatory meeting, which experienced a slight delay due to a student's blockade. The results include 80% completion of the action, the activation of a dedicated section on the faculty website for Roma students and strengthened collaboration with Roma associations and NGOs. The medium-term outcome will be monitored through the number of Roma association students who will take the

exam at the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering. There was a slight delay in holding meetings with members of the Roma population because the faculty was blocked by students, and only formal activities were taking place. The implementation has changed slightly over time - the agreement signing on cooperation was at the end of May, but with the possibility of the first days of June. The results of the action are:

- To increase the number of Roma students at the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering.
- Students of the Roma population are admitted to the faculty according to affirmative measures which is an advantage that the Roma population could use in the education process.
- In the future - constant contact will be maintained with Roma associations.

The most important results of the action are the creation of a link on the faculty's website, which contains all the information about the study of the Roma population at the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering; intensification of cooperation with non-governmental organizations; intensifying cooperation with the Roma association; employees in the collective raised their interest in this action to a higher level. The action met its objectives regarding gender equality and social inclusion, laying the foundation for sustainable institutional change through future targeted promotions in secondary schools and regular updates on the website. No significant barriers or resistance were encountered; non unexpected outcomes; the action impact will be sustained by consolidating relationships with Roma communities and actively promoting the educational opportunities offered by the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering. Each subsequent promotion of faculty in secondary schools will include much stronger contacts with students of the Roma population. All representatives of the Roma population will be informed in much more detail about the advantages of studying at the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering. The faculty website will regularly update news about events and activities related to students of the Roma population. The established cooperation with Roma representatives at the level of Serbia will continue. Facilitators factors were the interest of employees to get involved in faculty promotions with the aim of paying special attention to potential students from the Roma population, the excellent cooperation with representatives of non-governmental organizations and representatives of the Roma population in Serbia.

Outcome foreseen for action 5: increased visibility and availability of information for Roma students; increased level of integration of Roma students in the engineering society

Outcome achieved for action 5: increased visibility and availability of information for Roma students; the second outcome is ongoing, and it is too early for measurement; it will be monitored through the number of Roma association students who will take the exam at the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering.

Section redesign process

The first Evaluation and Redesign Workshop was held on 12 September 2024. UN partner discussed with the faculty management how to improve the stay of Roma students at our faculty, as well as how to increase the number of enrolled Roma students. The faculty agreed to support 2 places in the dormitory for Roma students and signed letters of cooperation with 2 NGOs dealing with the Roma issue.

The second Evaluation and Redesign Workshop was held on 8 May 2025. It was discussed what have been achieved for this action in the previous months, it was agreed the workshops suggested by Smart Venice and NGOs and external stakeholder engagement to improve Roma people experience at the university. At the suggestion of SV, a webinar was organized with the title: "Creating better environments for Roma students in HE with a gender and intersectional perspective". The Roma Education Fund (REF) representative proposed 3 topics:

- The position of young Roma men and women in higher education - guidance towards quality education
- The position of young, highly educated Roma women in society - inclusion, trends and employment policies
- Faculty of Mechanical Engineering in Niš - promotional opportunities for young Roma men and women in higher education

The Roma Education Fund (REF) will invite groups and individuals from its network and NEXUS Team will invite several organizations. The webinar will take place in October 2025.

3.8 Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia (IIT)

The following table summarizes the monitoring, evaluation, and redesign process of the pilot actions carried out by Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia within the NEXUS project.

Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia				
GEP'Areas	# Pilot Actions	#Formative Evaluation I round	#Formative Evaluation II round	#Actions adjusted following the Redesign Process
Work-life balance and organizational culture	1	1		1
Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment	1		1	1
Gender balance in leadership and decision making				
Data Collection	1			1
Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	1	1		
Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content	1	1	1	
Total	5	3	2	3

The following describes their 5 pilot actions, the findings from the second round of formative evaluation activities, and the redesign process carried out.

Action 1 - How to handle harassment in the workplace (Partner Action)

This action will focus on promoting an organizational culture awakening issues of harassment in the workplace, including sexual violence, through the development of a training course for middle

managers' roles at the institute. In this activity, the starting point was an internal survey assessing the level of knowledge on the topic and the participants' expectations about the training. In the implementation phase, the training course and the logistic aspects (schedule, transport, venue, and so on) were set up as well as the delivery of the training course and its evaluation by the participants. In all these activities, the number of participants was tracked using the attendance lists, photos/videos, questionnaires of knowledge and satisfaction on the topic, and materials collected to create the training.

Key Objective: Wellbeing in the workplace

Implementation Date: March 2025

Formative Evaluation First Round

The action did not require a formative evaluation in the first round.

Formative Evaluation Second Round

The formative evaluation was conducted through a form for the experts, designed to evaluate their experience in implementing the initiative and this specific activity. This online form has been shared among the following people with the idea of valuating the implementation of the action: Lina Donnarumma and Martina Cicaloni (NEXUS Team); Vanessa De Luca (D&I Office); Massimo Servadio, Psychotherapist and Work and Organizational Psychologist, expert in Organizational Health Psychology; Susanna Schivo, Civil Lawyer of the Genoa Bar and Trusted Advisor of the IRCCS San Martino Polyclinic Hospital; Alessandra Bissacco, Management Consultant and Soft Skills Trainer. Three main areas have been analysed: skills and knowledge applied, most appreciated aspects, and suggestions for improvement. Each area was linked to an open-ended question, allowing participants to respond freely and in Italian. In terms of skills and knowledge applied, participants contributed based on their professional expertise, personal experiences, and research on the topic. Some highlighted their legal background, while others emphasized their ability to facilitate discussions and manage networks. Prior knowledge of harassment-related issues and experience in organizing similar initiatives also played a role in shaping the workshop. Participants valued the opportunity to engage in discussions with experts and professionals. The workshop fostered

meaningful exchanges and dynamic interactions, making it both an educational and enriching experience. The collaborative environment, along with the depth of the debates, was particularly well received. Many noted that the workshop helped them enhance their understanding of the topic while also improving their communication and critical thinking skills. In conclusion, in relation to the improvement, participants proposed expanding the audience and, in some cases, making the workshop mandatory to increase its impact. Others suggested integrating it into structured training programs for a more continuous learning experience. Additionally, there were calls for strategies to boost engagement, such as interactive formats and improved communication methods to encourage active participation

Overview of the Formative Evaluation Second Round Results

The action is aligned with its objectives, both in terms of content delivery and promoting an intersectional understanding of harassment. The workshop introduced intersectionality as a framework for analysis and emphasised the compounded impact of discrimination based on multiple identity factors. This enriched participants' understanding and equipped them with tools for navigating and addressing harassment in academic and research environments. Facilitating factors included strong collaboration with external experts and a clear organisational desire to introduce the topic formally for the first time. The workshop contributed to institutional change by raising awareness and initiating structured dialogue on workplace harassment. It was the first initiative of its kind within IIT, and its outcomes has been incorporated into the upcoming revision of the Gender Equality Plan (GEP) in May 2025 to ensure continuity and long-term impact. Outputs and outcomes included increased awareness, enhanced internal knowledge, and strengthened intersectoral collaboration, with contributions from law, psychology, and organisational management. The intersectional approach highlighted the diverse experiences of harassment and the need for inclusive strategies within the workplace

Outcomes foreseen for Action 1: among all the topics and aspects covered during the course, one single theme (likely psychosocial risk) is selected and explored in depth. Tool: internal focus group involving various HR roles; Inclusion of the topic of psychosocial risk in the training related to health & safety measures. Tool: training course syllabus

Outcomes foreseen for Action 1: Among all the topics and aspects covered during the course, one single theme (likely psychosocial risk) is selected and explored in depth. Tool: internal focus group involving various HR roles; the second outcome is not yet achieved.

Section Redesign Process

The first Evaluation and Redesign workshop for this action was held on 6 November 2024. It was a focus group among the NEXUS Team. Indicators did not change, because the activities are the same but at different times.

The timeline for implementation was only changed and postponed with respect to the initial design, due to the overlap with other workshops on biases in decision-making.

The second evaluation and redesign workshop was held in May 2025 with a focus group among the NEXUS Team. The action was implemented in March 2025, but a revision outcome has been made:

- Short-term outcomes: Among all the topics and aspects covered during the course, one single theme (likely psychosocial risk) is selected and explored in depth. Tool: internal focus group involving various HR roles
- Medium-term outcomes: Inclusion of the topic of psychosocial risk in training related to health and safety measures. Tool: training course syllabus

No resistance but low participation rate

Action 2 - Designing ways to collect non-binary data (Partner Action)

The second action focuses on improving data collection practices by designing data collection for non-binary individuals' instructing an IIT workflow for future effective implementation. A technical table was composed of members of the NEXUS team, Human Capital Directorate, ICT Directorate, GDPR Office, Project office, Data Analysis Office, Management Control Directorate, and Tenure Track Office. They worked to do a state of the art/as-is of the IIT situation, and they delivered a proposal for integration. After that the first draft of the workflow was prepared to collect data from non-binary people. A data protection analysis was also prepared related to the impact of non-binary people's data collection. In conclusion, the technical table includes the final version of the workflow. Indicators focused on the number of participants, number of meetings, meeting notes, report of analyses, first draft and final version of the workflow designed for IIT situation. To sum up, the

implementation was evaluated by positive collaboration, with extensive knowledge sharing, cross-functional teamwork, and effective exchange of ideas. Participants appreciated the opportunity to explore new possibilities, deepen their expertise, and work closely with colleagues from diverse fields, fostering innovation and interdisciplinary synergy.

Key Objective: Data collection

Implementation Date: December 2024

Formative Evaluation First Round

We had a focus group the 2nd of December 2024. We prepared three questions in Italian, asking to the participants to reply with keywords using Microsoft Form Clouds. Participants appreciated the opportunity to explore new possibilities, deepen their expertise, and work closely with colleagues from diverse fields, fostering innovation and interdisciplinary synergy. The results are available on the [Deliverable 3.2 Formative Evaluation Mid-Term Results](#)

Formative Evaluation Second Round

The action did not require a formative evaluation – second round.

Section Redesign Process

The implementation didn't meet any resistance. People have positively contributed to the realization of the activity. The action was evaluated and redesigned during two Evaluation and Redesign Workshops: the first one was held on 28 February 2025 during the site visit at the University of Le Mans with the participation of the NEXUS Team. The second workshop was held in May 2025 by the NEXUS Team. These workshops were both held after the end of the action because due to organizational change the previous outcome could change. In fact, in the first workshop the NEXUS Team highlighted the possibility that, due to internal organizational changes, the outcomes (long and short terms) were under discussion and could be changed. In the second workshop, the NEXUS Team highlighted the change of the short-term outcome: from the integration of non-binary subject data collection into IIT's data collection process to the implementation of the workflow of the data related to non-binary people. Tool: statistical reports of IIT population.

Outcome foreseen for Action 2: the integration of non-binary subject data collection into IIT's data collection process changed into the implementation of the workflow of the data related to non-binary people

Outcome achieved for Action 2: in progress

Action 3 - Influences of biases in decision-making (Twin Trio Action)

This action consisted of a training module oriented to reduce cognitive bias influence in key activities within organizational contexts, particularly in recruitment process, career evaluations and progression, and relational dynamics. For this action, an initial survey was conducted to assess the staff's knowledge and their expectations for training. Training contents were elaborated with the support of experts in the fields, and once set up, the GEP group worked also in logistic management (venue, material, transport, etc..) and delivery. After that, participants evaluated their degree of knowledge on the topic and the level of satisfaction. The indicators included the number of participants (attendance list), the external coaches engaged and their post-course evaluations to assess learned skills and overall course effectiveness, post-test questionnaire text, and so on.

Key Objective: Tackling biases in recruitment

Implementation Date: November 2024

Formative Evaluation First Round

The formative evaluation was conducted the 27th of Novembre 2024 with a tailored questionnaire on MachForm to evaluate both the course content and logistics. This form was shared at the end of the training. The workshop received highly positive feedback, with most participants rating their overall experience and event organization as "Very Satisfied." Most attendees reported being "Very" or "Extremely Aware" of how biases affect decision-making, and a significant number expressed confidence in applying what they learned in the future. The results are available on [Deliverable 3.2 Formative Evaluation Mid-Term Results](#)

Outcome foreseen for Action 3: the “Choose and define the training content and the expert” changed. Based on the outcomes of the action, guidelines (PDF document) will be developed on the topic. The document will be shared with PIs and administrative staff to support them in evaluation and recruitment activities. Tool: Internal HR focus group

Outcome achieved for Action 3: in progress

Formative Evaluation Second Round

The action did not require a formative evaluation in the second round.

Section Redesign Process

The action has been evaluated and redesigned during an Evaluation and Redesign Workshops held in May 2025 by the NEXUS Team. This workshop was held after the end of the action because due to organizational change the previous outcome could change. The only thing reported is in fact, the short-term outcome that is changed (initially Choose and define the training content and the expert) as follows: Revision of the course contents: Based on the outcomes of the action, guidelines (PDF document) will be developed on the topic. The document will be shared with PIs and administrative staff to support them in evaluation and recruitment activities. Tool: Internal HR focus group

Action 4 - Gender Equality and Intersectional Dimension in Research (Twin Trio Action)

The action focused on the integration of the gender dimension, among others, involved the development of guidelines aimed at researchers and PIs working in scientific contexts and research organizations. The action was carried out from May 2024 to February 2025 and included five activities to be implemented. Initially, meetings with colleagues from the Project Office and researchers at IIT were held to gather information, perspectives, and experiences on the topic (activity 1). Following this, a state-of-the-art review of similar guidelines and toolkits was conducted to understand what had already been produced at the national and European levels (activity 2). Once the findings had been collected, an outline and drafting of the various chapters were developed together with colleagues from the TRIO team. The guide was designed to be a versatile, useful, practical, and very clear tool. Once completed, it was shared with colleagues. (activity 3 and 4). Researchers, project managers, and professors were able to comment on and review the content, both within IIT and,

more importantly, within the TRIO team. Finally, the guidelines were published on the IIT intranet page and promoted through the Viva Engage channel dedicated to research sustainability. We reached 61 downloads from February to May 2025 (activity 5).

Key Objective: A gender approach in the research fields

Implementation Date: February 2025

Formative Evaluation – First Round

The action did not require a formative evaluation for the first round.

Formative Evaluation Second Round Results

Since the activity has been developed at Trio level, UN and UM prepared a questionnaire for their students and researchers to collect their feedback and comment on the guidelines. The university of Le Mans did the activity on 14 May 2025, engaging 14 participants. University of Niš prepared the initiative on 11 April 2025 for 22 participants. The guidelines were well received, especially in the STEM field. Participants valued clear definitions and useful checklists. They suggested adding more interactive exercises and inviting a PhD student to present relevant research.

Overview of the Formative Evaluation Second Round Results

The action successfully met its objectives, supporting the integration of gender and intersectional dimensions into research practices. The action was led by the NEXUS team (Lina Donnarumma and Martina Cicaloni) in collaboration with the D&I Office (Vanessa De Luca), with initial involvement from the Project Office. Responsibilities were clearly distributed, with NEXUS and D&I overseeing the preparation of a survey, workshop planning, expert identification, and management of logistics and materials. No new institutional bodies were established for the implementation, but external stakeholders (San Martino Hospital and Fondazione Bruno Kessler) have been engaged through the dissemination of the guidelines. The NEXUS team and D&I prepared the survey to assess awareness on the topic, gathered materials and literature for the workshop, identified experts for the workshop, organized the activity, and arranged logistics and materials (slides, Teams link, participant invitations, etc.). External stakeholders were involved in the content review phase for the initial part.

All planned activities were carried out on schedule, with no delays reported. Key results include:

- Writing an interview script to explore 3 main areas: 1) Regulatory framework of Gender Equality and Intersectional Dimension (G+D) in Research, 2) Challenges and Support, 3) Inputs for Guidelines. The text has been shared and commented on with the Partners via email. Internally we did three interviews with key-internal actors: one female P.I. in robotics with expertise in inclusive cognitive robotic, another female researcher expert in European Grants and project proposals, and two senior project officers (one female and one male) who support IIT researchers in various phases of grant applications. Interviews with researchers and project officers (three conducted internally)
- Collection and analysis of the most significant report/guidelines/toolkit/project deliverables on the topic of Gender Equality and Intersectional in research at European level - shared folder among IIT and Trio partners. Collection of over 15 key EU documents on Gender Equality and Intersectional in research
- Drafting, review, and publication of the guidelines, with 61 downloads recorded as of 28 May 2025
- Launch of an internal communication channel “Viva Engage” to gather feedback and ensure long-term sustainability

The action’s impact included strengthened research knowledge and improved alignment with European funding and research standards. The timeline was realistic; we didn’t face any delays. The action aligns with its objectives (Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content) and meets intersectional objectives because we include specific terminology, case studies, and analysis on the topic of inclusiveness. The topic is important for researchers and project officers. However, people still need valid sources and support in implementing gender and intersectional dimensions in research, European projects and planning. The successful implementation of the action required a diverse set of knowledge and skills. This included a deep understanding of European fundings, European programs and research opportunities. To build this expertise, we read a lot of materials related to the topics but also, we did interviews for collecting feedback and experience of IIT colleagues on the topic. No barriers were encountered. No unexpected outcomes. The team, composed of HR, D&I and Project Office, will collect comments and insight into the

guidelines through the 'Sustainability' channel on Viva Engage, where the guidelines will be shared via dedicated posts. They will monitor the number of downloads and interaction on the topic but also feedback on the contents.

Outcome foreseen for Action 4: Increased interest in Gender and Intersectional Dimensions in research.

Outcome achieved for Action 4: Increased interest in Gender and Intersectional Dimensions in research.

Section redesign process

The action didn't require any adjustment following the redesign process.

Action 5 - D&I Committee for Parents (already Parenting resource group) (Twin Trio Action)

The primary objective was to establish IIT's first D&I Parent Committee, a crucial step in fostering a more inclusive community for parents across the organization. This goal was achieved by carefully selecting committee members and formally engaging starting from a dedicated kick-off event, which laid the groundwork for future initiatives. In details, the implementation began with the identification of participants (activity 1 individuating IIT colleague's participants): among the parents registered in IIT (almost 400 people), the D&I team selected 10 potential members based on their parental roles and representation of key dimensions of diversity, including: gender, workplace location (periphery/headquarters), job role (administrative/scientific), children's age group, parent's age group, disability (personal or within the family), caregiving responsibilities, origin (Italian/foreign) (activity 2 Individual meetings with parents to propose the action and their engagement to the Committee). On 22 November 2024, the D&I team met with the selected colleagues to introduce the initiative. During the meeting, a Statement of Purpose was presented outlining the Committee's mission, objectives, structure, and initial action plan. Seven participants confirmed their commitment to joining the committee and expressed interest in extending the discussions to broader diversity-related (activity 3 Group establishment) experiences, such as the Trio initiatives. The 16th of December the kickoff meeting of the D&I Parent Committee took place online (activity 4 kick-off meeting).

Key Objective Design open call for community builders

Implementation Date: December 2024

Formative Evaluation First Round

The formative evaluation was conducted the 22nd of November 2024 through a focus group involving internal stakeholders and aiming to define the mission, priorities, and goals of the Parenting Research Group. The results are available on [Deliverable 3.2 Formative Evaluation Mid-Term Results](#)

Formative Evaluation Second Round

The action did not require a second round of formative evaluation.

Outcome foreseen for Action 5: Number of activities approved by the D&I Committee for Parents

Outcome achieved for Action 5: in progress not yet achieved

Section Redesign Process

The action was redesigned on 19 September 2024 because it had been negatively reviewed by the Scientific and General Director of the IIT. Their behavior was identified as “organizational inertia” that refers to the tendency of organizations to resist internal changes, even when the internal environment demands it. Due to this situation, the following activities were changed: the name of the action, input (IIT colleagues to join the D&I Committee for Parents), activities, outputs, outcomes (changed from Improvement of the parenting network and their visibility” to “Number of activities approved by the D&I Committee for Parents”) and impact. The audience and timeframe remained the same. Most of the changes were related to the engagement of the participants, to the goals of this parent's group, and to their effort in IIT. The action was implemented in December 2024, but it was included in an Evaluation and Redesign Workshop on May 2025 due to organizational changes that should impact on the activity nr 5 “Kick-off Meeting for a formal Committee for Parents” changed into “creation of an informal, self-managed communication group on Viva Engage, focused on internal IIT initiatives and regulatory aspects related to parenthood”. During the workshop, indicators were discussed and considered achieved (10 parents engaged with high level of diversity

(gender, role, geographic, disability, and others; 5 meetings scheduled and executed; 1 Committee formed). Resistance to the implementation was the low interest of the top management with respect to the possibility of creating a community of parents. The reasons are not yet fully clarified.

3.9 Koç University (KU)

The following table summarizes the monitoring, evaluation, and redesign process of the pilot actions carried out by Koç University within the NEXUS project.

Koç University				
GEP'Areas	# Pilot Actions	#Formative Evaluation I round	#Formative Evaluation II round	#Actions adjusted following the Redesign Process
Work-life balance and organizational culture Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment	2	2	1	2
Gender balance in leadership and decision making Data Collection	3	3	3	3
Gender equality in recruitment and career progression Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content				
Total	5	5	4	5

The following describes their 5 pilot actions, the findings from the second round of formative evaluation activities, and the redesign process carried out.

Action 1 - GBV Training and Awareness Online Module (Twin Trio Action)

The main objectives of this initiative were as follows:

- To enhance participants' understanding of the links between harmful social norms and sexual violence and harassment, emphasizing the risks of normalizing such norms and accepting abusive behavior.

- To help participants identify acts of sexual violence and harassment and understand their capacity to intervene as active bystanders.
- To empower students and staff to respond safely to witnessed incidents of sexual assault and abuse now they occur.
- To raise awareness about the vital role of active bystanders in addressing sexual violence and harassment within the university community.
- Creating a safer and more inclusive environment both on and off campus, by developing an online module based on skills and knowledge that raises awareness about GBV and provides strategies to combat it effectively across partner institutions and beyond.

Key Objectives: Develop a skill and knowledge-based online module to educate and raise awareness on GBV and provide strategies to both deal with and to combat it in partner institutions and beyond.

Implementation date: June 2025

Formative Evaluation First Round

The formative evaluation activities for this action involved the Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) workshop held on 26 November 2024, as part of the Study Visit of the Trio partners at TU Dublin. The activity focused on reviewing the progress of the module's development and assessing alignment with its objectives. Tools used during the evaluation included discussions and feedback sessions among the Gender Equality Plan (GEP) working group members from the participating Trio institutions. The workshop involved six participants (6 females), all GEP working group members, including representatives from TU Dublin, KU, and UNISOFIA. The focus of the formative evaluation activity was to refine the module's content, review the division of responsibilities, and ensure the inclusion of intersectional dimensions in the training materials. It was decided that the module's content would undergo further revision to explicitly address intersectional aspects such as gender identity, sexual orientation, disability, nationality, race, and ethnicity. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative Evaluation Second Round

The development of this action began in June 2024 with the design of a concrete project plan. During summer 2024, all foundational instructional and training materials were compiled. The module content was developed during the 2024-25 academic year. This work was carried out by Catherine Bolger, Caitriona Delaney, and Sara Clavero (TU Dublin), who met regularly during this period to discuss developments and make revisions. At the same time, monthly discussions took place with the trio partners to further define the scope and structure of the action. Once the module contents were drafted, they were shared with the trio partners for review. After these reviews were submitted, the TU Dublin team met to discuss the feedback and incorporated it into the draft module contents. The revised module was then sent to the trio partners. Koç University was responsible for the design of an awareness video to be included in the training module (plus a teaser video of 30 seconds for the social media dissemination). Each trio partner gathered feedback for final refinements from relevant stakeholders (including NGOs and persons responsible for GBV measures in other institutions in their respective countries). The module was finalized during the spring of 2025 and as of June 2025, the module has been fully integrated into the institutional GBV structures and is now available online and in effect on the NEXUS main website. The Formative second round was made when Monthly trio meetings and during Monitoring and Evaluation workshops with trio partner teams and institutional experts responsible for the action implementation. The last M&E workshop was held on 15 April 2025. Regular meetings were held with Gender Equality Office at Koç University and the designer team that created video animation for the GBV Modul

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

The Gender Equality Office at Koç University and the NEXUS staff team at Koç University worked on this action, and it oversaw developing the implementation by communication, reporting, and networking and designing the module. No external actors have been involved. The institutional framework for the implementation of the action was already well-established in the university. The initial timeline established during the action planning phase proved to be unrealistic due to the complexities involved in developing the action. As a result, adjustments have been made to the schedule. However, the module's launch date has been brought forward, moving from 8 March to 7 February 2025. The implementation of the action was aligned with its objectives and with

intersectional objectives: the module addressed intersecting aspects like sex, gender identity, sexual orientation, disability, nationality, race, and ethnicity. There were some deviations from the planned activities, and the action was redesigned. At the end, it was a trio action and TU Dublin developed module content, with inputs from GBV expert in TU Dublin, UNISOFIA and KU reviewing and updating module content. KU designed an awareness-raising video to be inserted in the course, UNISOFIA was responsible for the graphic design of the rest of the module. Technical expertise inhibits the implementation because the organizers of the action did not possess the technical skills necessary to develop the action. On the other hand, expertise on visual design training had been provided by Koç University design team.

No resistance was encountered, but the main barrier was the high resource demand for creating a professional-quality module. This was addressed by reallocating UNISOFIA's budget to KU for producing a professionally made awareness video, which is included in the module. Meanwhile, UNISOFIA utilized its in-house graphic design expertise. The action had no unexpected outcomes and after the end of NEXUS, the module will be hosted by the Smart Venice e-learning platform.

Outcome foreseen for Action 1: increase in materials to be used on the platform; accessible online GBV module for partner institutions and beyond; increased GBV awareness, intervention skills, and project visibility.

Outcome achieved for Action 1: increase in materials to be used on the platform; accessible online GBV module for partner institutions and beyond. It is too early to achieve the third outcome.

Section Redesign process

The First Monitoring and Evaluation Workshop between the trio partners was held on 25 September 2024 and the NEXUS group representatives participated in the meeting. The group focused on bystander intervention. The material for the online module was in the process of being gathered and compiled into a module. The proposed consultation with GBV expert stakeholders was discussed with a view to this happening in January 2025. No resistances have been encountered. It was decided that TU Dublin will continue to focus on bystander intervention. Problematic issues included the design of the module; how interactive the module is and issues with budget constraints. It was also

planned that while TU Dublin supplies contents for the module, UNISOFIA supplies the budget, and Koç University works on the design process.

The second evaluation and redesign workshop between the trio partners was held on 26 November 2024. The NEXUS group's representatives participated in the meeting. Trio partners agreed on the objectives and scope of the action, making adaptations to fit each institution's needs. These revisions were carried out with the support of Catherine Bolger, GBV training manager at TU Dublin and member of the GEP Working Group. Each partner, in turn, reviewed the timeline for the implementation of the action and a new timeline for each was agreed. For KU, implementation of the action specifically, the following modifications were made: in the Level of co-design (KU designed an awareness-raising video to be inserted in the course; experts reviewed and updated the module content); improving the Intersectional dimensions beyond gender (Sex and gender identity, sexual orientation, disability, nationality, race & ethnicity); in the inputs; in the activities, in the time frame, in the outputs, in the outcome and in the impact. Partners reviewed indicators and decided to add someone else. No resistances to implementation have been experienced so far, and none were foreseen either. Action 1 was modified as detailed above. The following action 2 and action 3 are reported together as already done for Twin Trio partners above, due to their simultaneous implementation during the project and the deep correlation.

Action 2 - Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression - a Needs Analysis and Action 3 - Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression and Success (Twin Trio Actions)

Action 2 consists of collecting the needs in relation to mentoring programs in partner institution; these needs will be the base to develop a mentoring program. Action 3 consists of developing a training program/manual for mentors with inclusivity at its core using the data gathered in the action "Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression - a Needs Analysis"

Action 2 Key objectives: To ascertain the base line of needs in relation to mentoring in partner institutions and to subsequently develop a mentoring program.

Action 3 Key Objectives: To develop a training program/manual for mentors with inclusivity at its core using the data gathered in the action "Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression - a Needs Analysis".

Action 2 Implementation date: January 2025

Action 3 Implementation Date: July 2025 (in progress)

Formative Evaluation First Round

The formative evaluation activities for this action involved the Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) workshop held on 26 November 2024 as part of the Study Visit of the Trio at TU Dublin. The workshop included six female participants, consisting of Gender Equality Plan (GEP) working group members from each of the Trio institutions. The evaluation session focused on assessing the progress of the action and identifying adjustments needed to align with its objectives. The evaluation reviewed the construction of the mentoring survey, which has been completed successfully. This survey, created collaboratively by the NEXUS doctoral scholarship holder Ayça Çavdar and the GEP Office, forms the foundation of the mentoring needs analysis. However, the subsequent steps—administering the survey, analyzing results, and disseminating findings—are still pending. The delay in administering the survey, initially planned three months earlier, was discussed, but other activities are expected to proceed on schedule. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative Evaluation Second Round

The Second round of the formative evaluation activity was made on 29 May 2025 through a focus group involving representatives from key university offices and academic units, 11 participants joined the focus group (faculty members, post doc, researcher, administrative coordinator, unit specialist, sustainability office). The Gender Equality Office and the NEXUS work group were responsible for this activity. The objectives of Action 2 and Action 3 were: assess baseline mentoring needs in partner institutions; develop an inclusive mentoring program/manual using data from the "Inclusive Mentoring Career Progression - Needs Analysis" action. Action 2 started in June 2024, with completion on track for December 2024 and Action 3 was delayed slightly to January 2025 but ended in May 2025. The activities have all been completed.

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

Gender Equality Office (under Office of Sustainability) in collaboration with Office of the Dean of Students, Alumni Office played a key role in coordination. Institutional support was reaffirmed, particularly for piloting the mentoring program in the upcoming term.

Action 2

The action was implemented by the NEXUS team and the Gender Equality Office. No external stakeholders were involved. Activities have been carried out as foreseen (Action 2: Survey administered and analyzed; needs documented). The timeline was realistic, and the timeline hadn't been delayed. The implementation was aligned with its objectives: Action 2 established evidence-based mentoring needs. The action meets its intersectional objectives because needs were identified and addressed including gender, age, parenthood, cultural background, academic rank, and career direction. The implementation changed over time: Action 2 transitioned from informal mentoring assumptions to a structured, intersectional informed system. The results of the actions in terms of gender equality and inclusivity dimensions were the following: Action 2 created institutional awareness around mentoring gaps. Action 2 has been fully accomplished.

Action 3

The action was built directly on Action 2's findings and involves broader collaboration, including career and alumni services. It involves planned participation of industry mentors and alumni, making it intersectoral. A formal program was developed to establish a mentoring structure tailored to specific themes and needs identified through Action 2 (the survey). Full institutional support was secured, and collaboration with diverse administrative and academic units was successfully achieved. The program was scheduled to launch in the 2025–26 academic year. The timeline was realistic, and the implementation hadn't been delayed. The implementation was aligned with its objectives: Action 3 uses this evidence to design a context-sensitive mentoring model. The main objective was to establish a mentoring structure that specifically addresses the career progression needs of early career researchers, particularly those from disadvantaged groups. The program was designed with this principle in mind and successfully achieves this goal. The action meets its

intersectional objectives because needs were identified and addressed including gender, age, parenthood, cultural background, academic rank, and career direction.

Action 3's mentoring format was designed to reflect these. There wasn't any deviation from the planned activities: Action 3 evolved to include thematic mentoring tracks and digital matching tools based on participant input. The factors that promoted the implementation of the action were the strong stakeholder engagement, the survey-driven design, and the interdepartmental collaboration. The factors that may inhibit the implementation of the action are the risk of low mentor participation or overreliance on voluntary labor. The implementation changed over time: Action 3 adapted the framework based on Action 2's data and GEP Refinement session feedback. The skills required for the project were present in the project team and supported by external advisors (Survey design, mentoring program planning, facilitation, intersectoral collaboration).

The barriers encountered were early scheduling challenges for the survey, and limited mentoring capacity. The solutions to overcome these barriers include task force creation, thematic structuring, and small-cohort pilot planning. No resistance was encountered. The results of the actions in terms of gender equality and inclusivity dimensions were the following: Action 3 was enabling a shift toward inclusive, intentional mentoring aligned with academic equity and retention goals. The program could be embedded into onboarding, career development structures, and alumni engagement strategies. Periodic review (every 2–3 years) will ensure continued relevance.

The outputs and outcomes: Mentoring supports underrepresented identities and life stages in academia. Anticipated long-term impacts include improved retention, satisfaction, and academic success; Action 3 is on track and designed using robust institutional feedback mechanisms.

The factors that facilitated and hindered the outcomes of the actions were: stakeholders buy-in, GEP alignment, existing program infrastructure. The factor that hindered was the capacity to scale mentoring without overburdening staff.

Outcome foreseen for Action 2: baseline needs assessment in relation to mentorship will be conducted; a mentoring training program (manual) will be developed

Outcome foreseen for Action 3: increase in materials available for mentoring; increase in the total inter-connectivity of research and innovation ecosystems; the career prospects of early career researchers (doctoral students, post docs, junior faculty) will be developed

Outcome achieved for Action 2: baseline needs assessment in relation to mentorship have been conducted; a mentoring training program (manual) has been developed

Outcome achieved for Action 3: increase in materials available for mentoring; the achieving of the other two outcomes is in progress.

Section Redesign process

The first evaluation and redesign workshop between the trio partners was held on 25 September 2024. The NEXUS group's representatives participated in the meeting.

Action 2: Focus on finding out what needs to happen to create a mentoring program for researchers that is inclusive TU Dublin changed its action from conducting a quantitative study to a qualitative study. Koç university decided to conduct surveys rather than interviews. No resistances have been encountered. No challenges are envisioned in terms of the monitoring and evaluation process. It was decided that Koç University would continue to finalise the report based on the research they conducted and subsequently share the findings with internal stakeholders for feedback on the proposed next steps.

The second evaluation and redesign workshop between the trio partners was held on 26 November 2024. The NEXUS group's representatives participated in the meeting. The action implementation was evaluated and redesigned by the trio partners with the support of Gerolmina di Nardo, Researcher Career Development Manager (TU Dublin). The redesign involved: the data collection (the data collection has been conducted through survey at KU between 12 December and 31 December); the inputs; the audience; the activities; the timeframe (the survey analysis was postponed to January 2025); the outputs; the outcome (baseline needs assessment in relation to mentorship has been conducted; a mentoring training program (manual) has been developed). Action-2 was modified as detailed above.

Action 3

The first evaluation and redesign workshop between the trio partners was held on 25 September 2024. The NEXUS group's representatives participated in the meeting. Manual/guidelines will be produced drawing from the data gathered in action 2. Indicators for this action were reviewed as the

focus on this action became producing a manual/guideline. As such the indicators include gathering and compiling materials for the manual/guidelines and were in process. No resistances had been encountered. The monitoring and evaluation plans for this action included ensuring that the materials available for mentors to ensure their mentoring practice is inclusive are increased. The evaluation activities selected for this action included consulting with internal and external mentoring experts. It was decided that this action would become more of a focus when action 2 was finalised however, we would continue to gather materials that may be useful for the manual/guidelines.

The second evaluation and redesign workshop between the trio partners was held on 26 November 2024. The NEXUS group's representatives participated in the meeting. Minimal adjustments were made, except for the timeframe:

- 13 January 2025—June 2025: Compile the mentoring program manual
- 2025/2026 Academic Year: Launch mentoring program

No resistance to implementation had been experienced so far, and none was foreseen either. Action 3 was modified as detailed above.

Action 4 - Skills Development Program (Partner Action)

The Skills development program was designed to support the career progression of early career researchers, including doctoral students, postdoctoral fellows, and junior faculty—with a special focus on those from underrepresented groups. The objective of the program is to foster critical transversal skills and strengthen participants' confidence in building successful and fulfilling academic and non-academic career trajectories. The program was structured as a flexible series of modular sessions and workshops spread throughout the academic year to accommodate the busy and diverse schedules of the targeted academic community. The design was conducted through a comprehensive survey conducted across all career stages, which revealed a strong demand for support in communication skills, particularly in engaging with non-academic audiences. In response, a pilot session was developed and implemented in May 2025, focusing on creative drama techniques to enhance scientists' and academics' communication skills beyond academia. The session was very well received and provided valuable insights not only thematically—demonstrating strong interest and need from the academic community—but also logistically, helping us refine our delivery model. Building on the lessons learned from this pilot, we have developed a workshop-based skills

development program centered around the most pressing needs identified through the survey. The full program was scheduled for launch in the 2025–26 academic year. A comprehensive survey was conducted for this Action. The survey results were discussed and evaluated with a large group of stakeholders from different academic disciplines and administrative units at KU over the spring of 2025.

Key Objectives: Establishing a skills development program

Implementation Date: The preparation started in Fall 2024 (first session to be held in February 2025)

Formative Evaluation First Round

The formative evaluation activities for this action were conducted through regular meetings with institutional experts and individuals responsible for its implementation. These meetings involved seven participants (6 female and 1 male), including early career researcher such as doctoral students, postdocs, and junior faculty, as well as the Gender Equality Coordinator, Behice Pehlivan, NEXUS doctoral scholarship holder Ayca Cavdar, and GEP specialist Ayca Uğur. The results are reported in the deliverable 3.2

Formative Evaluation Second Round

The second formative evaluation activity was held on 29 May 2025 during a GEP Refinement Session. Participants were 11 representatives from key university offices and academic units, all females (Faculty members, postdoctoral researchers, administrative coordinators, and specialists from units such as the Office of Sustainability), included people of NEXUS team. Participants evaluated the outcomes of pilot science communication training, discussed broader transversal skill needs, and made recommendations for scaling and institutionalizing the program. Key feedback focused on adaptability, intersectional dimensions, and embedding the program in graduate training or career development structures.

Overview of the formative evaluation second round

Gender Equality Office (now under the Office of Sustainability) coordinated the action with increasing support from academic departments and individual faculty members. It conducted a survey for needs analysis in skill development. Based on the needs, a pilot workshop was organized

in collaboration with faculty as trainers. No external actors were involved. No institutional body had been established for the action, but the program was well-positioned for integration into the Graduate School or Career Development Office in the next phase. Activities have been carried out as foreseen and all short- and medium-term outcome indicators have been achieved. The timeline was realistic, but the main challenge was planning recurring workshops while balancing academic calendars. The implementation of the action reached its objectives, also in terms of intersectional objectives. Participants expressed that confidence-building and academic navigation are influenced by identity, experience, and academic rank. Future sessions will focus more explicitly on marginalized groups (e.g., gender minorities, international researchers). No deviation from the planned activities. The factors that promoted the actions were the strong interest from participants, the low implementation costs, the high perceived value. The factors that inhibited the action were: limited faculty availability to facilitate sessions, need for long-term coordination structure. The implementation has changed over time because it was shifted from one-off training to a broader, modular program responsive to academic and emotional skill development needs. The skills required for the implementation of the actions were training design, facilitation, needs assessment, and program coordination. The current team possessed these, though scaling may require additional facilitators. The barriers encountered were faculty time constraints, difficulty scheduling across departments. Mitigation strategies included planning sessions during breaks and using external trainers. No resistance was encountered. Participants reported improved communication confidence and appreciation for peer interaction. The unexpected outcome was the enthusiasm around creating informal peer learning communities and sustained interest in workshops beyond science communication. The impact of the action will be ensured after the end of the implementation. In fact, the program can be housed under the Graduate Schools with rotating trainers and periodic review. Its modular structure supports easy replication. In terms of gender equality, the main results were the strong potential for promoting equity by addressing the unspoken challenges that disproportionately affect underrepresented groups in academia. The expected outcomes were achieved: pilot goals met; full implementation on track; program refined based on feedback and ready for institutional integration. The factors that facilitated the outcomes of the action were the strong participant demand, high relevance to academic culture. The factors that

hindered were the competing academic responsibilities and undervaluation of transversal skills in some departments

Outcomes foreseen for action 4: At least 10 researchers will be beneficiaries; improved workshops will be held; Evaluation survey results will be available.

Outcomes achieved for action 4: More than 10 early career researchers attended the pilot workshop and attendees filled out session evaluations; comprehensive, extended and improved workshops will be designed building upon the results of the pilot workshop.

Section Redesign process

The first evaluation and redesign workshop for actions designed outside the trio was held on 3 October 2024. The Gender Equality Team and the NEXUS Team participated in the meeting. It was a discussion about the survey and the workshop. During the discussion it emerged that the action took more time than expected and the workshop may be extended in January 2025.

Action 5 - Seminar Series on Anti-Feminist Algorithms and AI Bias (Partner Action)

This action is closely related to the information and communication technologies sector. The seminar series recruited experts as speakers in the program, also the professional sector was engaged in this event and was invited as an audience at the Formative evaluation activity (first round). The network analysis was done. One session is already being held (November 2024) and the expected number of participants was achieved for the first session. The second session had been held in March 2025.

Key Objectives: To raise awareness of misogynist backlash and AI bias on social media among the university community

Implementation Date: March 2025 (first workshop held in November 2024 and second workshop held in March 2025)

Outcomes foreseen for action 5: At least 2 seminars to be held under the specific topic and at least 20 participants attending as audience

Outcomes achieved for action 5: 2 seminars on Anti-Feminist Algorithms and AI Bias were held, and more than 20 participants attended the events

Formative Evaluation – First Round

The formative evaluation activities for this action involved weekly meetings with institutional experts and those responsible for the action's implementation. These meetings involved seven participants (6 females and 1 male), including staff and students from KU, with active contributions from Berehice Pehlivan, Ayça Çavdar, and Aycan Uğur. The discussions focused on refining the action's objectives, identifying panelists, specifying panel topics, and organizing logistics for the events. The results are reported in the [deliverable 3.2](#).

Formative Evaluation Second Round

The action did not require a formative evaluation – second round.

Section Redesign process

The first evaluation and redesign workshop for actions designed outside the trio was held on 3 October 2024. The Gender Equality Team and the NEXUS Team participated in the meeting. It was a discussion about network analysis, the sessions to be held, the number of participants, and the panelists. The action took more time than expected and the second seminar has been held on 7 March 2025. There might be a need for an extra budget for the second panel.

4. Overall Analysis

The pilot actions of the NEXUS project were 45, equivalent to 5 actions per partner. Thanks to the twin Trio system, the partners were grouped into 3 trios, and each trio designed and implemented a minimum of 3 common actions. Therefore, of the 45 pilot actions, 30 are common actions of the twin trios, and 15 are actions individually designed and implemented by the partners based on the Open Laboratory system. The actions are divided among partners as shown in Table nr.1

Table 1

Partner	Individual actions	Twin Trio actions	Grand Total
TU Dublin	2	3	5
FredU	1	4	5
UNISOFIA	2	3	5
UM	2	3	5
AGH	1	4	5
BZN	1	4	5
UN	2	3	5
IIT	2	3	5
KU	2	3	5
Grand Total	15	30	45

All the pilot actions designed and implemented pertain to one of the areas of the Gender Equality Plan. The following chart shows the distribution of the pilot actions among the original 5 recommended areas of the Gender Equality Plan (Gender equality in recruitment and career progression, Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment, Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content, Work-life balance and organizational culture, Gender balance in leadership and decision making) and also the Data Collection (added due to a common need to strengthen data collection process in various organizations). The following graph shows this distribution (Figure nr.1)

Figure nr. 1

The first round of Formative evaluation involved 43 pilot actions, predominantly in the following areas of the Gender Equality Plan: “*Gender equality in recruitment and career progression*”, “*Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment*”, “*Work-life balance and organizational culture*”. All partners, except IIT, made the formative evaluation first round for all their own 5 pilot actions. IIT made the formative evaluation in the first round only for 3 pilot actions. During the first round of Formative evaluation, the most used tools were: Focus Groups, meetings with experts, and Monitoring and Evaluation meetings of the twin trios.

Table 2 Formative Activities II round among partners

Partner	Formative Evaluation II round	Formative Evaluation I round
TU Dublin	5	5
FredU	4	5
UNISOFIA	5	5
UM	5	5
AGH	5	5
BZN	5	5
UN	5	5
IIT	2	3
KU	4	5
Grand Total	40	43

The second round of Formative evaluation involved 40 pilot actions, predominantly in the following areas of the Gender Equality Plan: *“Gender equality in recruitment and career progression”*, *“Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment”*, *“Work-life balance and organizational culture. It was like the first round”* (Figure 2).

Six partners (TU Dublin, UM, Un, AGH, BZN and UNISOFIA) conducted a formative evaluation for all 5 pilot actions. The other three partners (FredU, IIT, KU) conducted the second round of formative evaluation only for the actions that were implemented in the first part of the year 2025.

The second round of formative evaluation was mostly conducted on the residual pilot actions and, for some partners, on all 5 pilot actions. During the second round of formative evaluation, the tools most used were: ex-post surveys, meetings with experts, and focus groups. The first round of formative activities involved 96% of overall 45 pilot actions. The second round of formative activities involved 89% of overall 45 pilot actions. The percentage of use of the types of activities useful for

carrying out the formative evaluation of the first and second rounds is represented in the following chart (Figure 5).

Figure nr. 5

It should be noted that the methodologies used for formative evaluation varied between the first and second rounds, with a higher percentage of use of survey/questionnaire, workshops and Meetings with stakeholders in the second round, compared to a higher percentage of use of other tools like focus groups, meeting with experts and other tools in the first round.

Figure nr.2 (Distribution of the second round of formative activities among GEP areas and Data Collection)

During the NEXUS Project, 36 actions were adjusted following the redesign process. In detail, 27 of the 45 NEXUS trios pilot actions and 9 individual actions were subjected to adjustments following the redesign process, distributed among the various partners as shown in the following table 3.

Table 3

Partner	Individual actions adjusted	Trio actions adjusted	Grand Total
TU Dublin		3	3
FredU	1	4	5
UNISOFIA		3	3
UM	1	2	3
AGH		4	4
UN	2	3	5
IIT	2	1	3
KU	2	3	5
Grand Total	9	27	36

As part of the redesign process, 36 out of the 45 pilot actions, including 27 actions designed within the twin trio framework, were adjusted during the implementation. Considering the 45 pilot actions, 20% of individual actions and 60% of twin trio actions have been adjusted. The adjustments mainly focused on redesigning areas such as activities, time frames, and output.

The adjustments primarily concerned actions in the GEP areas of “*Gender equality in recruitment and career progression*”, “*Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment*”, and “*Work-life balance and organizational culture*”.

Figure 3 (Distribution of the actions adjusted as part of the redesign process among the GEP areas and Data Collection)

In general, the implementation of the actions began in the second half of 2024. In fact, in 2024, the implementation of 43 out of 45 actions was initiated. Referring to the months in which the actions were implemented, we can note that 20% of pilot actions were completed by the month of December 2024; 14% of actions were implemented and concluded by the month of February 2025; 53% of actions were completed by the month of June 2025; 11% of the actions were completed by the month of August 2025. The following chart shows the cumulative number of completed pilot actions by each month represented. (Figure nr. 4).

Figure nr. 4

There is a critical issues for the following action:) for Bay Zoltan, the action related to the elimination of biases has experienced significant delays due to funding issues, and having found a possible solution, the action is in progress and is expected to be implemented in the fall of 2025; 3) for Koc University, the action of Inclusive Mentoring and Career Progression and Success is in progress because the mentoring program (action 3) will be launched in the 2025–26 academic year. Overall, given the heterogeneity of the actions and partners, what has been achieved represents an excellent result.

Conclusions

The second round of formative evaluation activities, along with the outcomes of the evaluation and redesign workshops, has brought to light several cross-cutting insights shared among the project partners.

The first key observation concerns the redesign of efforts undertaken by all partners. This highlights the importance of adopting a structured Project Management approach when designing actions within a Gender Equality Plan (GEP). Such an approach not only supports the initial planning phase but also enables continuous monitoring of activities, outcomes, and KPIs. Indeed, GEP actions, like all change management processes, require ongoing adjustments and refinements. This is consistent with the European Institute for Gender Equality's (EIGE) guidance, which emphasizes that monitoring and evaluation are essential to ensure the transformative potential of GEPs and to maintain stakeholder engagement [1].

A second important insight relates to the **positive impact of intersectorality and intersectionality on the design of actions**. The involvement of co-designers representing diverse perspectives and personal experiences has proven essential in developing truly inclusive initiatives.

Quantitative data from the NEXUS project shows that 45 targeted actions were co-designed and piloted across seven EU Member States and two Associated Countries. These actions include:

- The introduction of bias awareness training could lead to increasing applications from underrepresented groups also in STEM fields (*"Influence of Bias in Decision Making"* Twin Trio IIT, UM, UN).
- The establishment of intersectional mentoring programs, which paired early-career researchers with mentors across gender, cultural, and disciplinary lines—benefiting more participants in the first year (*"Action 2 - Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression - a Needs Analysis and Action 3 - Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression and Success"* Twin Trio KU, TU Dublin, UNISOFIA).
- The implementation of inclusive training, reaching academic and administrative staff (*"Skills Development Program"* KU, *"Inclusive Mentoring for holistic success"* UNISOFIA, *"Fostering Empowerment for women at work"* UM)

- The creation of institutional dashboards for real-time monitoring of gender-disaggregated data, enabling more agile decision-making and accountability (“*Implementation of the GEAM tool*” AGH, “*Data Collection and Percentage Monitoring on students, PhD, Academics...*” UNISOFIA).

The main takeaway from this analysis is that the methodology adopted by the NEXUS project, spanning from capacity building to monitoring and evaluation, if appropriately streamlined and simplified, could serve as an effective tool for drafting and implementing the next generation of Gender Equality Plans. These future plans should aim not only to address gender disparities but to promote broader inclusion across multiple dimensions. The NEXUS methodology, grounded in participatory design and continuous feedback loops, offers a replicable model for institutions seeking to embed inclusivity into their research and innovation ecosystems [2].

5. Summative Evaluation Report

This chapter presents the summative evaluation findings of the project. The following sections details results derived from comprehensive **interviews and focus groups** conducted throughout June and July 2025, involving Smart Venice and all nine project partners. Details on each topic are as follows, with partners’ contributions and a final overview of the main challenges and barriers.

Interview structure and questions

Online semi-structured interviews were carried out between 09/06/2025 and 04/07/2025. Following introductory questions regarding the interviewee’s perception of potential challenges and overall views on the project’s impact, the interview was structured in four key sections:

- 1. Inclusiveness and the GEP: the organization’s approach/policies towards inclusion, and how they may have changed over the past two years.*
- 2. Institutional commitment: leadership engagement in the project and initiatives supporting gender and intersectional equality generally.*

3. Institutional change processes: the project's impact, for instance in relation to the GEP, the integration of NEXUS actions in existing frameworks, or new approaches to data collection.

4. A view to the future: gaps that could be addressed in the future through new steps or actions.

Focus group structure and questions

The agenda was structured in four blocks. A Mentimeter question was used as an engaging starting point/icebreaker for each block, to collect initial responses from each participant and provide potential topics for discussion, where relevant. The four key sections of the discussion were:

1. Implementation: the implementation process, including challenges experienced and observed, the formative evaluation and re-design process, and responses observed by stakeholders internally to the organization (e.g., staff, students).

2. Collaboration: the co-creation and overall collaboration process, including collaboration in the twin trios and engagement of external stakeholders.

3. Institutional commitment: institutional commitment, for instance in relation to resources made available for project activities, engagement of middle and senior management, general commitment and institutional steps towards the sustainability of NEXUS actions.

4. A view to the future: gaps that could be addressed in the future through new steps or actions.

The results of the summative evaluation activity emerging from each partner institution are presented in the following paragraphs.

5.1 Technological University of Dublin (TU Dublin)

The TU Dublin summative evaluation took place through one focus group with 5 people (including two members of the NEXUS team) held on 24 June 2025, and two individual interviews conducted on 16 June 2025 and 26 June 2025. Overall, participants saw the NEXUS project as a valuable opportunity to pilot innovative actions on gender and intersectional equality.

Summative evaluation findings	
Intersectoral collaboration/co-design process	NEXUS supported TU Dublin in collaboration with other universities, which proved valuable for mutual learning. The academic sector is seen as more advanced in DEI, limiting opportunities for reciprocal knowledge exchange. The capacity-building sessions were positively received for raising awareness, particularly around intersectionality, though there was a desire for more actionable guidance on how to translate learning into institutional practice.
Institutional commitment	<p>TU Dublin demonstrates strong formal commitment to gender and intersectional equality through initiatives like Athena Swan and the appointment of a DEI director. However, this commitment is not always consistently translated into action. DEI is often deprioritized during crises or competing demands, and too much responsibility is placed on individual champions. External projects like NEXUS struggle to gain leadership attention unless closely aligned with internal strategies. Overall, the commitment is visible but sometimes more symbolic than deeply embedded.</p> <p>TU Dublin participants rated the institutional commitment on these topics 3.2 out of 5, reflecting a moderate level of perceived engagement overall.</p>

Institutional change	<p>The project played a key role in raising awareness of gender and intersectional equality. The integration of NEXUS activities into the Athena Swan framework was impactful but challenging to implement. Despite this, the project was seen as aligned with TU Dublin’s institutional culture and values. Internal stakeholders responded positively to the project, recognizing its high impact within the institution. However, while the project contributed to important shifts, particularly in drawing attention to the need for more robust data collection and analysis, embedding these changes into institutional policies and practices was constrained by limited resources. Broader implementation efforts were challenged by competing priorities, financial constraints, and a lack of institutional prioritization of DEI initiatives, which are sometimes viewed as additional burdens. Scheduling difficulties and bureaucratic delays further hindered sustainability and the pace of change.</p> <p>Sustainability: Participants stressed that short-term projects are not sufficient to drive lasting change. Sustained impact requires long-term funding, alignment with institutional strategies, and formal embedding of actions. Despite that, many initiatives still rely on voluntary staff input, which was seen as unsustainable.</p>
Future through new steps or actions	<p>Efforts are underway to institutionalize some actions, such as integrating training into employment contracts, but progress is gradually increasing. Importantly, participants emphasized that sustainability also means flexibility. Action plans should be adaptable to “living documents” that respond to changing needs and contexts in higher education.</p>

5.2 Frederick University (FredU)

As part of the summative evaluation activities at Frederick University, one online focus group and four online interviews were conducted. The first one was on the 3rd of June with 4 participants, 2 of whom were NEXUS team members. Four interviews were conducted, on the 1st, the 12th and the 17th of June 2025, and the last one on the 4th of July 2025. The NEXUS project has significantly contributed to increased awareness and the development of new policies and tools within the university, fostering an openness to change.

Summative evaluation findings	
Intersectoral collaboration/co-design process	<p>In the summative, FredU underlined significant comments in the Twin Trio collaboration and in external stakeholder engagement.</p> <p>The "Co-creation Twin Trio" initiative proved to be exceptionally fruitful for the university, creating a dynamic environment where all partners actively supported each other in finding solutions. This collaborative process was particularly engaging due to the strong sense of mutual support. Furthermore, the broader intersectoral collaboration fostered through this project offered significant learning opportunities and facilitated a valuable exchange of feedback and good practices among all involved. (Example of how to face disabilities inside the university, and in designing actions thanks to Open Lab)</p>
Institutional commitment	<p>The governance of the university actively works to promote gender equality, a commitment reflected in several initiatives, trainings, and seminars directed at both staff and students by the university management. Key examples of this institutional dedication to equality and inclusion include the decision to apply for the prestigious Athena Swan Bronze Award and the continued implementation of the GEAM tool. However, areas for improvement persist; one interviewee noted that management's commitment varies between the academic and administrative areas. While there's currently organizational commitment at the structural level, beyond specific individuals, future leadership changes could potentially impact this sustained effort.</p> <p>FredU participants rated the institutional commitment on these topics 4.5 out of 5.</p>

Institutional change	<p>The NEXUS project clearly had a positive effect on the organization, leading to increased awareness of gender equality and intersectionality within the institution and generally over recent years. This was further amplified by increased collaborations with other universities. A significant achievement was the integration of NEXUS actions into institutional routines, alongside a notable improvement in both quantitative and qualitative data collection. However, achieving full sustainability and institutional change faces several barriers. Cultural resistance and stereotypes remain, including pushbacks against gender-inclusive language, which some perceive as a luxury rather than a necessity. There's also a lack of awareness among students, particularly regarding inclusive language. The highly centralized structure of the university presents a potential challenge, making it difficult to ensure broad participation and engagement.</p> <p>Sustainability: A future leadership change could support those who work in gender and diversity by investing money and concrete efforts. In addition, all the action has been valued as sustainable by the group.</p>
Future through new steps or actions	N/A

5.3 Sofia University (UNISOFIA)

The summative evaluation at the University of Sofia included one online focus group held on 20 June 2025 with six participants (four of whom were members of the NEXUS team), and two individual interviews conducted on 18 and 27 June 2025. The findings highlight a strong institutional commitment to gender and intersectional equality, with active support from senior leadership.

Summative evaluation findings	
Intersectoral collaboration/co-design process	Three main aspects emerged from the evaluation. First, intersectoral collaboration was highlighted as particularly valuable, allowing participants to compare experiences and learn from the practical knowledge of external stakeholders. Second, the co-creation process, including both the twin trio and Open Lab activities, helped raise awareness on unfamiliar topics and supported the adaptation of good practices to the local context. Third, capacity building played a key role in increasing awareness and interest in gender equality and inclusivity across the institution.
Institutional commitment	Management support for the NEXUS project was generally positive, despite some delays caused by bureaucratic procedures. A strong dedication to structural change was evident, with senior leadership including two Vice Rectors and a Dean actively participating in the GEP working group, demonstrating that gender and intersectional equality are prioritized at the highest levels. Additionally, the NEXUS team successfully fostered cross-departmental collaboration by connecting units such as HR and academic departments and engaging staff from various roles, which enhanced communication with leadership and helped translate proposals into concrete actions. UNISOFIA participants rated the institutional commitment on these topics 4.6 out of 5
Institutional change	Significant progress has been made over the years in gender equality, reflected in strong participation in NEXUS training and engagement activities, leading to a shift in institutional culture. The changes introduced through NEXUS are poised to become part of regular

	<p>practices and policies, serving as a foundation for updating the current GEP. Improvements in data collection are already underway, though further enhancements in data processing and analysis are needed. Integrating an intersectional approach has proven manageable, and the institutional changes driven by NEXUS such as mentoring programs and psychological support are sustainable. Challenges include bureaucratic processes and maintaining initial project momentum. Additionally, attention has been given to improving the physical environment and accommodation for students and staff with disabilities.</p> <p>Sustainability: Integrating an intersectional approach has proven manageable, and the institutional changes driven by NEXUS such as mentoring programs and psychological support are sustainable.</p>
Future through new steps or actions	N/A

5.4 University of Le Mans (UM)

The summative evaluation of the University of Le Mans engaged one focus group with 4 participants (2 of whom NEXUS team members) and two online interviews on the 12th and the 27th of June 2025. Overall, the evaluation suggests that while Le Mans University has made meaningful progress in promoting gender equality and initiating innovative actions through the NEXUS project, sustained efforts are needed to strengthen coordination and ensure broader engagement.

Summative evaluation findings	
Intersectoral collaboration/co-design process	The main findings from the co-design process at Le Mans University highlight that collaboration within the twin trio enabled the integration of diverse perspectives and complementary contributions, leading to high-quality outcomes and strengthening the culture of gender equality. At the same time, intersectoral collaboration with external stakeholders enriched training activities and facilitated the development of new partnerships, contributing to internal learning and the long-term sustainability of the actions (example: local network on sexual health with around 30 partners, including CSOs and public institutions).
Institutional commitment	Regarding the level of commitment from management to the actions developed through the next project, participants reported significant challenges related to funding, which slowed down implementation and limited the ability to engage and reward participants. In April 2025, the organization voted for new management that has shown enthusiasm for bottom-up initiative developed within the NEXUS framework. Despite this, intersectional inequalities appear to remain insufficiently addressed, with the intersectional dimension often misunderstood. UM participants rated the institutional commitment on these topics 2.3 out of 5
Institutional change	At Le Mans University, equality is currently a priority, and awareness on the topic has increased. The NEXUS project positively contributed to a change in mindset and generated interest in its activities. Progress was made in data collection, with efforts to better measure and publish results. Participants expressed the wish for DEI training to become mandatory, as is the case for safety training. However, the intersectional

	<p>approach remains insufficiently understood, partly due to the language barrier, as some training sessions were held in English.</p> <p>Sustainability: NEXUS actions considered innovative compared to existing ones have been integrated into the newly approved GEP. Despite these advancements, several challenges were identified: linguistic barriers, coordination and scheduling across departments proved difficult; staff participation was limited due to time constraints; the visibility of actions was low; and structural limitations and internal resistance hindered broader engagement.</p>
<p>Future through new steps or actions</p>	<p>N/A</p>

5.5 AGH University of Science and Technology (AGH)

The AGH University of Kraków conducted one online focus group and three online interviews for their summative evaluation. The online focus group took place on 23 June 2025, with 5 participants, two of whom were NEXUS Team members. The online interviews were conducted on 9 and 23 June, and 1 July 2025. While facing challenges such as cultural resistance, participation issues, and administrative burdens, the university is making strides in integrating DEI initiatives, as evidenced by the strengthened GEP and the ongoing development of inclusive practices.

Summative evaluation findings	
Intersectoral collaboration/co-design process	Collaboration within the Twin trio was beneficial for recognizing diverse European needs and approaches, though it faced challenges with external participant engagement and misaligned academic schedules. Intersectoral collaboration proved fruitful and significant, enabling AGH to support other organizations in developing their initial Gender Equality Plans, making a considerable local impact.
Institutional commitment	Lower levels of commitment from top management might be attributed to prevailing organizational and political trends. To support a focus on intersectionality and mitigate political sensitivities, the working group's name was subsequently changed to the 'Equality Group' AGH participants rated institutional commitment on these topics 3.2 out of 5.
Institutional change	Internal stakeholders responded enthusiastically, noting visible improvements in gender equality and inclusion, with e-courses and the project's European framework boosting legitimacy and awareness. The GEAM survey was crucial, revealing resistances but also guiding improved communication and the development of the new, four-year GEP, now among the best in Polish universities. NEXUS actions, GEP, and DEI frameworks are well-aligned, with training significantly impacting awareness and data collection from an intersectional perspective. While NEXUS actions are expected to be sustainable, including onboard new staff and students, their long-term viability is contingent in the broader political context. Barriers to change include

	<p>cultural resistance, challenges in participation, fragmented data, insufficient leadership support, administrative burdens, and difficulties in measuring e-learning impact.</p> <p>Sustainability The partner will work on these actions even after the project. However, they also mentioned that the sustainability of NEXUS actions and other initiatives for gender and intersectional equality are contingent on the broader political context, and that therefore advances made towards equality and inclusion are fragile.</p>
<p>Future through new steps or actions</p>	<p>In terms of changes to the GEP, the new version has recently been finalized, and it will be valid for four years.</p>

5.6 Bay Zoltán Nonprofit Ltd. for Applied Research (BZN)

BZN did one focus group and two interviews in the summative evaluation activities. The first one was on 26 June 2025 with 6 participants (2 of whom are NEXUS team members) and the two interviews on 13 and 20 June 2025. Overall, their experiences can be valued positively, with a range of improvement in participant engagement, external stakeholders and DEI regulations and procedures.

Summative evaluation findings	
Intersectoral collaboration/co-design process	The intersectoral collaboration experience supported the organization in the implementation and evaluation of the actions, with those stakeholders within the same sector. However, this experience remains invisible to colleagues outside the NEXUS team.
Institutional commitment	While the Bay Zoltán Research Centre is a leader in Hungary regarding management's commitment to institutional change for alleviating gender and intersectional inequalities. Management members did recognize the value of the NEXUS project for fostering collaborations with other Hungarian organizations involved in sister projects. However, there is no internal budgetary support for such initiatives, and management would be indifferent to staff seeking further grants for similar projects to NEXUS. BZN participants rated the institutional commitment on these topics 3.2 out of 5.
Institutional change	NEXUS has had a very significant impact on the GEP itself, so work must continue to gain broader support. It played an important role in shaping the framework among DEI, regulation and processes.
Future through new steps or actions	N/A

5.7 University of Niš (UN)

The summative evaluation of the University of Niš took place through one focus group with 10 participants (3 of whom NEXUS team members) and two online interviews on the 12th and the 27th of June 2025.

Summative evaluation findings	
Intersectoral collaboration/co-design process	<p>Intersectoral collaboration within the NEXUS project was seen as a valuable and enriching aspect of the initiative. It was particularly useful to observe how other organizations approached similar topics, offering new perspectives and insights that informed local strategies.</p> <p>The co-creation process within the twin trios was another strong point, allowing participants to gain a deeper understanding of the project’s methodology and structural approach to designing and implementing actions. Additionally, the Capacity Building Program was perceived as a positive and beneficial experience, enhancing participants’ skills and reinforcing their ability to contribute effectively to institutional change efforts.</p>
Institutional commitment	<p>There was a strong level of commitment and support for the NEXUS project from the management of the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering; however, this was not mirrored at the university-wide level. Support from the Rector and the Rector’s Office was limited, partly due to the high degree of autonomy granted to individual faculties. More broadly, when considering the management’s commitment to institutional change aimed at addressing gender and intersectional inequalities within the organization beyond the NEXUS project, a clear gap emerged between rhetorical support for gender equality as a guiding value and principle, and the concrete allocation of funding and resources needed to implement meaningful change.</p> <p>UN participants rated the institutional commitment on these topics 3.3 out of 5</p>

Institutional change	<p>The NEXUS project received positive feedback from both participants and stakeholders and is widely regarded as the starting point of a broader institutional change process. Even though this positive feedback, the project also faced important contextual challenges, such as entrenched cultural and societal norms, broader political obstacles, and internal cultural resistance, including horizontal segregation within the faculty. It has been actively publicized online, increasing visibility and awareness, while information about NEXUS actions is accessible on the faculty website and available to students, contributing to transparency and engagement.</p> <p>Sustainability: the NEXUS Team collaborated with the Legal and HR departments to incorporate the project's actions into the Gender Equality Plan (GEP), and discussions took place regarding the financial support necessary to implement the GEP effectively.</p>
Future through new steps or actions	<p>Several future priorities emerged: a) involving more external experts to deliver or support activities such as dedicated lectures; b) increasing the participation of management in workshops and events; c) engaging student representatives, including in leadership roles related to project activities; d) organizing annual workshops and trainings to address staff and student turnover; e) clarifying and making more transparent the procedures for reporting sexual harassment; f) and publishing more accessible and transparent reports on both planned and completed actions.</p>

5.8 Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia (IIT)

The summative evaluation at the Italian Institute of Technology (IIT) included one online focus group held on 5 June 2025 with ten participants (two of whom were members of the NEXUS team), and four individual interviews conducted on 10th, 18th, 20th and 26 June 2025. Overall, the evaluation suggests that while IIT has laid important groundwork for change, further efforts are needed to embed DEI values more consistently across all levels of the organization.

Summative evaluation findings	
Intersectoral collaboration/co-design process	Intersectoral collaboration at the Italian Institute of Technology (IIT) was seen as an opportunity for learning, particularly through comparisons with other organizations. Focus group participants highlighted that such exchanges could offer valuable insights and best practices. However, collaboration with stakeholders from different sectors such as industry was considered more challenging than other RPOs who have a similar mission to IIT, due to differing missions and operational approaches.
Institutional commitment	Perceptions of institutional commitment at IIT were mixed. While some interviewees acknowledged a degree of interest and support from the institution, others described the overall situation as inadequate. A key concern raised was the disconnect between formal policies and their practical implementation what appears solid on paper and often contrasts with more complex realities. Several participants highlighted that many initiatives related to gender equality and intersectionality originate from bottom-up efforts, in the absence of visible leadership or structured communication from top management, including the Executive Committee. IIT participants rated the institutional commitment on these topics 1.4. out of 5
Institutional change	Participants reported that diversity, equity and inclusion (DEI) are supported by an established institutional culture, with backing from various internal offices. Several interviewees noted that prior initiatives had already laid the groundwork for promoting inclusivity, even before the NEXUS project. While a persistent gap between policy and practice

	<p>remains a challenge, participants observed that the organization’s approach to inclusiveness has evolved positively in recent years, following a clear trajectory of growth.</p> <p>However, from their point of view NEXUS was perceived as having a significant and positive impact, especially training and workshops. Concerns were raised regarding the risk of raising expectations through data collection particularly when not linked to concrete measures and the importance of integrating such efforts with broader strategies and activities. Nonetheless, participants stressed the need for stronger institutional embedding of such actions to ensure long-term sustainability.</p> <p>Sustainability: Work is currently underway to revise and adapt the Gender Equality Plan (GEP) based on the lessons learned through NEXUS. Some actions like the workshop on harassment might be mandatory for all people in IIT.</p>
<p>Future through new steps or actions</p>	<p>Participants suggested working on a) transparency and communication to all staff and students, as well as using existing data to share information about the current situation, b) focusing communications on the fact that the benefits of DEI initiatives positively affect everyone, not just specific groups</p>

5.9 Koç University (KU)

The summative evaluation at Koç University was conducted through one focus group held on 10 June 2025 with seven participants (including two members of the NEXUS team), and two individual interviews carried out on 16 and 17 June 2025. The report highlights that Koç University has made notable progress in embedding gender equality into its institutional framework, with increasing emphasis on sustainability, intersectoral collaboration, and the need to ensure long-term, systemic change.

Summative evaluation findings	
Intersectoral collaboration/co-design process	Intersectoral collaboration was identified as a key strength. The mentorship program linking students with industry professionals was particularly valued. Alumni are viewed as important connectors between academic and professional spheres. Participants saw strong potential to expand cooperation with the private sector, public institutions, and NGOs, supporting the long-term advancement of gender and intersectional equality initiatives.
Institutional commitment	<p>Several comments highlighted that while there is some visible support, gender equality is often deprioritized in favor of more immediate concerns such as recruitment, infrastructure, and crisis response. Some participants acknowledged signs of progress, including a balanced gender distribution in recruitment. However, gaps remain in policies, especially those supporting working parents, such as improved access to university daycare services. Within departments, passive resistance and a lack of ownership at leadership levels were reported as obstacles to advancing equality-related initiatives. Support for the NEXUS initiative was described as stronger at the beginning of the project and less visible over time. Participants stressed the need for continuous endorsement across administrative transitions to maintain momentum.</p> <p>KOC participants rated the institutional commitment on these topics 3.3 out of 5</p>

Institutional change	<p>The project led to several institutional developments, including comprehensive gender equality training delivered to students, faculty, and staff, alongside a noticeable increase in awareness across the university community. A decline in student reports related to sexual violence was interpreted as evidence of heightened awareness and improved access to relevant support services. Participants expressed strong interest in the data gathered through NEXUS initiatives, highlighting its potential for use across multiple departments and in tracking progress over time. Nonetheless, there is still a recognized need to enhance data collection practices, improve internal communication, and ensure broader dissemination. Presenting concrete data was seen to strengthen the credibility and visibility of gender equality efforts.</p> <p>Sustainability emerged as a key theme in the findings, especially in connection with the recent structural change that repositioned the Gender Equality Office under the broader umbrella of the Sustainability Office. Although this shift initially generated confusion among staff and students, it is now increasingly perceived as a strategic and meaningful integration framing gender equality as an essential component of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and indicating continued institutional commitment.</p>
Future through new steps or actions	<p>Looking ahead, gender equality and intersectionality initiatives at Koç University are expected to become more deeply embedded in institutional structures and procedures. There is a clear ambition to build on the lessons learned from the previous GEP and the NEXUS experience to shape future efforts.</p>

Cross-Partner Trends and Key Findings

The summative evaluation of the NEXUS project provides evidence of the project's institutional impact across nine European research institutions. The evaluation focused on three key areas: **institutional commitment, institutional change, and intersectoral collaboration/co-creation**. The findings reveal that **interinstitutional collaboration** (via the Twin Trios and Open Labs) promoted knowledge exchange and mutual learning, though engagement with non-academic sectors remained challenging. **Institutional commitment** to gender and intersectional equality was often inconsistent, with strong support from individual champions but weaker structural embedding and resource allocation. **Tangible institutional changes** included improvements in Gender Equality Plans (GEPs), enhanced awareness of intersectionality, and some integration of inclusive training and data collection processes. **The capacity-building program** was well received, though there remains a need for more practical tools and sustained follow-up.

Barriers identified

Barriers such as limited resources, resistance to gender-related concepts, low engagement, and the politicization of DEI topics still pose significant challenges. The summative evaluation revealed a rich and nuanced picture of the institutional transformations supported by the NEXUS project. Despite contextual differences among partners, several **shared trends and systemic challenges** emerged:

a. Intersectoral Collaboration and Co-Creation

- All partners reported that the **Twin Trio model** fostered valuable mutual learning and exchange of good practices. The model was particularly effective in promoting reflection, adaptation, and creativity in designing inclusive actions. Some partners mentioned difficulties in collaborating within the twin trios due to misaligned timelines/calendars and other differences in their approaches.
- External stakeholder engagement was generally more challenging, especially beyond academia. Collaboration was strongest within the university/research sector and depended heavily on existing networks and individual commitment.

- The co-design process enhanced institutional ownership and encouraged more inclusive and context-sensitive approaches, although coordination difficulties and time constraints sometimes limited deeper collaboration.

b. Institutional Commitment

- A **disconnect between formal commitment and resource allocation** was reported by almost all partners. While management often expressed support for DEI principles, sustained investments, especially in staff time and budgets—were lacking.
- **Middle and senior management engagement** varied significantly, with stronger involvement typically observed at faculty or department levels rather than top institutional leadership.
- **Volunteerism and personal motivation** often sustain DEI actions, raising concerns about long-term sustainability without structural support or mandates.

The perception of institutional commitment was measured during the focus groups through responses to the following question: *“How committed would you say your organization and management are to gender and intersectional equality?”*. The level of commitment was rated on a scale from 1 to 5.

c. Institutional Change

- Most partners observed that NEXUS **strengthened existing DEI frameworks**, particularly by enhancing the visibility of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) and mainstreaming intersectional thinking.
- Positive changes were reported in areas such as **data collection practices**, the integration of **inclusive training into institutional practices**, and the **revision or extension of existing GEPs**.
- Challenges to change included **bureaucratic inertia**, **cultural resistance**, and the need to **institutionalize pilot actions** within longer-term policy cycles (e.g., Athena Swan frameworks or national equality laws).

d. Awareness and Capacity Building

- The capacity building program was generally appreciated and considered effective in **raising awareness on intersectionality and gender equality**.

- However, **practical application** and **follow-up actions** varied across partners. In some institutions, the training content was integrated into onboarding and researcher development programs; in others, dissemination and institutional embedding remained limited.

e. Barriers and Risks

- Commonly cited barriers included:
 - **Resource constraints** (budget, time, staff),
 - **Leadership turnover** and policy discontinuity,
 - **Perceived low prioritization** of DEI in times of institutional crisis,
 - **Cultural and political resistance** to gender and intersectionality, especially in conservative contexts.

Despite these challenges, many partners viewed NEXUS as a **starting point for deeper change**, creating a foundation for future work and triggering internal reflections on inclusion and equity.

6. Annexes Documentation Submitted to the project's SharePoint

Separate links from the project's SharePoint are provided for each partner, granting access to the **Monitoring and Evaluation Plan** document, the **Evaluation and Redesign Workshops Reporting** document, and the **Formative Evaluation Reporting** document.

Technological University of Dublin (TU Dublin), Ireland

Monitoring and Evaluation Plan: [NEXUS D3.1 TU Dublin Monitoring and Evaluation 120724.docx](#)

Evaluation and Redesign Workshops Reporting: [03_Evaluation & Redesign workshops reporting TUDublin.docx](#)

Formative Evaluation Reporting: [04_Formative evaluation reporting TUDublin.docx](#)

Summative Evaluation Report: [NEXUS project - Summative Evaluation Report_TUD.pdf - All Documents](#)

Koç University (KU), Turkey

Monitoring and Evaluation Plan: [KOÇ 01_Monitoring and evaluation plan template_rev SV.docx](#)

Evaluation and Redesign Workshops Reporting: [03_Evaluation & Redesign workshops reporting template KU.docx](#)

Formative Evaluation Reporting: [04_Formative evaluation reporting template KU.docx](#)

Summative Evaluation Report: [NEXUS project - Summative Evaluation Report_KU.pdf - All Documents](#)

Sofia University (UNISOFIA), Bulgaria

Monitoring and Evaluation Plan: [01_Monitoring and evaluation plan template \(1\).docx](#)

Evaluation and Redesign Workshops Reporting: [03_Evaluation & Redesign workshops reporting template Sofia University.docx](#)

Formative Evaluation Reporting: [04_Formative evaluation reporting Sofia University.docx](#)

Summative Evaluation Report: [NEXUS project - Summative Evaluation Report_UNISOFIA.pdf - All Documents](#)

Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia (IIT), Italy

Monitoring and Evaluation Plan: [Annex 01_Monitoring IIT.docx](#)

Evaluation and Redesign Workshops Reporting: [Annex 3_IIT Evaluation & Redesign workshops reporting template.docx](#)

Formative Evaluation Reporting: [Annex 4_IIT Formative evaluation reporting template.docx](#)

Summative Evaluation Report: [NEXUS project - Summative Evaluation Report_IIT.pdf - All Documents](#)

University of Le Mans (UM), France

Monitoring and Evaluation Plan: [01_Monitoring and evaluation plan UM.docx](#)

Evaluation and Redesign Workshops Reporting: [03_Evaluation & Redesign workshops reporting template LMU.docx](#)

Formative Evaluation Reporting: [04_Formative evaluation reporting template.docx](#)

Summative Evaluation Report: [NEXUS project - Summative Evaluation Report_UM.pdf - All Documents](#)

University of Nis (UN), Serbia

Monitoring and Evaluation Plan: [01_Monitoring and evaluation plan_UN.docx](#)

Evaluation and Redesign Workshops Reporting: [03_Evaluation & Redesign workshops reporting UN.docx](#)

Formative Evaluation Reporting: [04_Formative evaluation reporting UN.docx](#)

Summative Evaluation Report: [NEXUS project - Summative Evaluation Report_UN.pdf - All Documents](#)

Frederick University (FredU), Cyprus

Monitoring and Evaluation Plan: [01_Monitoring and evaluation plan FredU.docx](#)

Evaluation and Redesign Workshops Reporting: [03_Evaluation & Redesign workshops reporting template.docx](#)

Formative Evaluation Reporting: [04_Formative evaluation reporting FredU.docx](#)

Summative Evaluation Report: [NEXUS project - Summative Evaluation Report_FredU.pdf - All Documents](#)

Bay Zoltán Nonprofit Ltd. for Applied Research (BZN), Hungary

Monitoring and Evaluation Plan: [01_Monitoring and evaluation plan BZN.docx](#)

Evaluation and Redesign Workshops Reporting: [03_Evaluation & Redesign workshops reporting-BZN.docx](#)

Formative Evaluation Reporting: [04_Formative evaluation reporting template-BZN.docx](#)

Summative Evaluation Report: [NEXUS project - Summative Evaluation Report_BZN.pdf - All Documents](#)

AGH University of Science and Technology (AGH), Poland

Monitoring and Evaluation Plan: [01_Monitoring and evaluation plan agh.docx](#)

Evaluation and Redesign Workshops Reporting: [03_Evaluation & Redesign workshops reporting agh.docx](#)

Formative Evaluation Reporting: [04_Formative evaluation reporting agh.docx](#)

Summative Evaluation Report: [NEXUS project - Summative Evaluation Report_AGH.pdf - All Documents](#)

References

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[2] **Twinning Research and Innovation Institutions to Design and Implement Inclusive GEPs,** Link: [Twinning Research and Innovation Institutions to Design and Implement ...](#)

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UN Women (2015), How to manage gender-responsive evaluation: Evaluation handbook. <https://www.unwomen.org/sites/default/files/2022-05/UN-Women-Evaluation-Handbook-2022-en.pdf>